

European Schools Project on Alcohol & other Drugs

ESPAD 2019 IRELAND

TobaccoFree Research Institute Ireland
for the Department of Health

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**ESPAD 2019:
European Schools Project on
Alcohol and Other Drugs in Ireland.**

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TobaccoFree Research Institute Ireland
for the Department of Health

An Roinn Sláinte
Department of Health

The Department of Health

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Foreword

The ESPAD Ireland 2019 Report is the seventh Irish data-collection wave of the European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) carried out in Ireland.

Data included in the sample reported here and submitted to ESPAD Europe consists of survey results from 1967 students born in 2003, who were 15-16 years old at the time of the survey which was performed in a sample of Irish schools from March to June 2019. These serial data sets enable us to monitor trends in alcohol, tobacco, gaming, internet usage as well as a number of other behaviors including illicit drug usage such as cannabis. So that now we can examine changes over the past 24 years in a wide number of behaviors.

During that time more than a half a million second level European students have answered the ESPAD questionnaire. The first ESPAD report, with data from 1995, included information from 26 countries including Ireland, while the present seventh report scheduled for publication in November 2020 contains results from more than 35 countries. ESPAD is probably the most accessed source of reliable information on young people's substance use in Europe with participation by countries within and outside the EU.

The ESPAD project was initiated in 1993 by the Swedish Council for Information on Alcohol and Other Drugs (CAN) as a follow-up of a test of a European school-survey questionnaire funded by the Pompidou Group at the Council of Europe in a pilot study in 1986–1988. ESPAD also has an established contact with the European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA) in Lisbon. This co-operation has deepened in later years and has included support for data collection, analysis and reporting as well as the hosting of an ESPAD Project Meeting and is now a shared project. Students' participation is voluntary and anonymous and no results are presented for individuals or single classes. Apart from using a common questionnaire on a commonly defined target population and data collection period, field work practices as well as capture, cleaning, delivery and analyses of the data are carried out in standardized fashion. The data collections in individual countries are funded through national sources. In our case work on this report would not have been possible without financial support from the Dept. of Health tender for Research Services for the European Schools Service Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) 2019.

We acknowledge institutional support from Focas Institute TU Dublin, the support of our colleagues, Dr Zubair Kabir, UCC Dr Mark Ward, TCD, Dr Helen McAvoy IPH, Seefin Data Management Limited and Prof Mark Morgan DCU whose pioneering work and approach to this project we try to follow.

We would particularly like to express our gratitude to all those who made this project possible, especially school principals, teachers, research assistants and others who facilitated us with the data collection and especially the Irish school students throughout the country without whom there would be no survey.

Luke Clancy

D.G. Tobacco Free Research Institute Ireland, Dublin June 2020

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	1
Background	1
Executive Summary	2
1. METHODOLOGY	6
Aims of the Study	6
Sample and Recruitment.....	6
ESPAD 2019 Questionnaire	7
Ethical Issues	8
Data Collection Entry and Analysis	8
2. SUBSTANCE USE IN IRELAND 1995-2015	9
Alcohol Use	9
Heavy episodic drinking.....	10
30-day cigarette use	11
Lifetime cannabis use	12
Lifetime inhalant use	13
Lifetime use of tranquilizers without prescription.....	14
Lifetime use of other substances.....	15
Summary.....	16
3. DRINKING AND ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION	20
Alcohol Consumption.....	20
Reports of being drunk	21
Consequences of alcohol use	27
Drinking Motivation	29
Summary.....	30
Factors Related to Alcohol Consumption	31
4. SMOKING AND TOBACCO PRODUCTS CONSUMPTION	41
Smoking.....	41
Factors related to smoking	47
Summary.....	71
E-CIGARETTES AND WATER PIPES	72
Factors related to e-cigarette use	79
5. CANNABIS USE	86
Cannabis Use	86
Factors related to cannabis use	93
6. USE OF OTHER SUBSTANCES	106
Substance use.....	106
Energy Drinks.....	113
Factors related to substance use.....	116
7. INTERNET, GAMING AND GAMBLING	128
Internet use.....	128
Gambling	131

Summary	134
8. SUBSTANCE USE IN IRELAND TO DATE	135
Alcohol Use	135
Heavy episodic drinking	135
Current smoking	136
Lifetime use of cannabis	137
Lifetime Inhalant Use	137
Lifetime use of tranquilizers without prescription	138
Use of Illicit Drugs other than Cannabis	138
REFERENCES	140
Appendix 1: Data Collection Materials	143
Appendix 2: Questionnaire used for ESPAD Ireland 2019	148

ESPAD 2019 NATIONAL REPORT

Introduction

This report is based on data gathered for the European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) Survey carried out in Ireland in 2019. The ESPAD survey takes place concurrently every four years in some 35 European countries and is based on a common set of questions and methodology. This series of studies began in 1995 following an initiative by the Swedish Council for Information on Alcohol and Other Drugs (CAN) to connect with researchers in other European countries, including Ireland, with a view to conducting a common survey on the usage of tobacco, alcohol and illegal drugs in the school-going population. The main aim of the ESPAD survey is to monitor trends in alcohol and other drug use among 15-16 year olds and to compare trends between countries and groups of countries. In doing so, researchers compile a large database of information that can play an integral role in the planning and implementation of future initiatives and policies. Ireland has participated in every phase of data collection since the launch in 1995 (Hibell *et al.*, 2004, 2008, 2012; ESPAD Group *et al.*, 2016; Taylor *et al.* 2015).

Background

The health impacts of tobacco, alcohol, and substance use, on both individuals and society at large, are widely established (Goldstein *et al.*, 2003; Kabir *et al.*, 2009; Gakidou *et al.*, 2017; Amalia *et al.*, 2020). The negative effects of excessive substance use are universally recognized and addressed through a number of strategies at local, national, and international levels (Strang *et al.*, 2012; Healthy, 2013). In order to continually generate effective and relevant policy, it is crucial for policy makers to have access to rigorous, up-to-date data on substance use trends. Monitoring tobacco, alcohol, (Eriksen *et al.*, 2013 WHO, 2014); and drug use among young people, in particular, is vital as it has proven to be a rapidly changing phenomenon with varied implications (Johnston *et al.*, 2015).

For example, alcohol consumption among teenagers has been associated with physical health issues, mental health issues, and key risk-taking behaviours such as aggressive behaviour, driving while under the influence, and/or unprotected sex (Bonomo *et al.*, 2001; Swahn *et al.*, 2004; Wells, Horwood and Fergusso, 2004). Tobacco use among young people has long been established as a predictor of continued tobacco use, which remains one of the leading causes of preventable disease worldwide. Illicit drug use among young people has been associated with adult drug-use, psychosis, behavioural problems, and antisocial behaviour (Arseneault *et al.*, 2002; Van Os *et al.*, 2002; Eaton *et al.*, 2012). In Ireland, a number of studies have monitored substance use among young people over the past two decades. However, the two main longitudinal studies operating in Ireland have been the Health and Behaviour of School-Aged Children Study (HBSC) and the ESPAD study.

The HBSC study is a cross-sectional study conducted in collaboration with the World Health Organization (WHO) Regional Office for Europe. The study targets school-going children between the ages of 9-18 and aims to gain insights into their health, well-being, and social contexts. Data collection occurs every four years

throughout most European countries, including Ireland. To date, surveys have been conducted in 1998, 2002, 2006, 2010, 2014 and 2019. The most recent data collection wave found a decrease in alcohol and tobacco use among the target population, mirroring the downward trend in previous HBSC data collection waves (Gavin *et al.*, 2013, 2014) 2020)

Similar results were found in the 2015 ESPAD data collection waves in Ireland. A slight increase in tobacco use was reported. More students had tried alcohol in their lifetime. There was also a slight increase in those who used alcohol regularly. Cannabis use remained consistent with previous years, while there was a slight increase in students who had tried inhalants.

Executive Summary

The European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) Survey collects comparable data on substance use among European students aged 15 and 16 years in order to monitor trends in alcohol and drug use, as well as gambling, gaming and internet use within and between countries and groups of countries. To date, Ireland has participated in seven data-collection waves that have been conducted across 39 countries in Europe. In the Irish 2019 data-collection wave, a total of 1949 students aged 15-16 years old (born in 2003), from a stratified random sample of 50 post-primary schools, completed a questionnaire on issues including alcohol use, cigarette smoking and e-cigarette use, cannabis and other illegal drug use, gambling, gaming, and internet use.

This report presents key findings from the 2019 ESPAD survey in Ireland and provides information on prevalence of substance use (alcohol, cigarettes, e-cigarettes, illicit drugs, inhalants and new psychoactive substances), perceived availability of substances, age of initiation of substance use, and prevalence of internet use, gaming and gambling. Associated factors including gender, social class, familial and peer variables are also examined for each behaviour.

In relation to alcohol, 73% of respondents had tried alcohol and 41% were current users (had used alcohol in the previous 30 days), while 16% reported having been drunk in the previous 30 days. Among boys, the most popular alcoholic drinks were beer (36%) and cider (32%) while, among girls, spirits (32%) and cider (25%) were the most popular. As in previous surveys, age 15 years (52%) was the most common age at which students first drank alcohol, followed by age 14 (28%). Increased alcohol use was associated with lower parental education levels and lower parental monitoring, as well as with truancy, lower school grades, and peer alcohol use. The reasons given most frequently for using alcohol were to make social gatherings more fun (49%) and to help respondents “to enjoy a party” (48%). Asked about consequences of alcohol use, damaging or losing property was the most frequently reported (10%), followed by serious argument (7%) and injury/accident (7%). 3% reported unwanted sexual attention as a negative outcome of alcohol, representing about 60 young people, more girls than boys. Since 1995, when Ireland first participated in ESPAD, there has been a significant reduction in alcohol consumption among students aged 15-16 years. However, our trend analyses in this wave indicate that, since 2015, there has been a slight increase in current alcohol use and also in heavy episodic

drinking.

Smoking remains a notable issue for adolescents. 32% of respondents had tried smoking and 14% were current smokers, with 5% smoking daily. Again, the majority (63%) of students reported starting to smoke at age 14 or 15. Equally, the majority (61%) reported that it was easy to access cigarettes. Smoking was associated with truancy and lower grades, as well as with perceived relative wealth, lower parental education, parental monitoring, parental rule setting, parental support, relationship with parents, and also peer use of smoking, alcohol, cannabis and other substances. Our trend analyses showed that, despite a reduction of over two-thirds since 1995 (the second largest decline of any of the seven major indicators of the ESPAD survey in Ireland), slightly more students reported smoking in 2019 than in 2015, and this was pronounced for boys.

Of concern were the numbers of adolescents reporting e-cigarette use. Because of their recency in the Irish market, this is only the second time that respondents to ESPAD were questioned about e-cigarettes. More students report using e-cigarettes in 2019 than in 2015, and the use of e-cigarettes among students is now more common than cigarette smoking. Almost four in 10 students (39%) had tried e-cigarettes and almost one in 5 (18%) were current users, making both ever-use and current use of e-cigarettes higher than use of combustible cigarettes. As with smoking, boys (46%) were more likely than girls (33%) to have tried e-cigarettes and also to be current users (23% vs 14%). When asked about their reasons for trying e-cigarettes, two-thirds (66%) said that it was “out of curiosity” and 29% said that it was because their friends offered it. Only 3% said that it was “to stop smoking cigarettes”. This point was further reinforced when respondents were asked about their tobacco use when they first used an e-cigarette. More than two-thirds of respondents (68%) had never smoked cigarettes, while 24% smoked occasionally, and only 9% smoked regularly.

Students were asked about their ever-use and current use of a range of illegal drugs and other substances. Cannabis was the most-used drug with almost one student in 5 (19%) having tried cannabis and almost one in 10 (9%) having used it in the previous 30 days. Boys were more likely than girls to be users, and girls were more likely to perceive risk in regular or occasional cannabis use. More boys (22%) than girls (13%) had also tried unsuccessfully to stop using cannabis. Early initiation into cannabis use was particularly evident with almost four out of 5 users (79%) having first tried cannabis at the age of 14 or 15 years. Access to cannabis was reported as fairly or very easy by 42% of students. Cannabis use was associated with socio-economic status, truancy and absenteeism, lower school grades, and lower parental monitoring.

Regarding other substance use, inhalants were the most commonly used substance (10% ever-use), with students also reporting use of painkillers (5%), alcohol with pills (4%), cocaine (3%), and ecstasy (3%), among others. Almost one in 5 students reported that access to cocaine and/or ecstasy was “easy”. We found that illicit substance use was associated with socio-economic status, truancy, lower school grades, low parental monitoring, and peer substance use. Our trend analyses showed that, between 2015 and 2019, there were no changes in the use of cannabis, inhalants and tranquilizers. However, we observed a decrease in the use of illicit drugs other than cannabis and, in fact, of all seven indicators (alcohol, smoking, etc.), it was in this area that the largest reduction occurred.

In relation to gambling, the majority (84%) of respondents had not gambled in the previous 12 months. Gambling is a particularly gendered activity, in terms of frequency, intensity and use of internet to gamble for money. More boys (23%) than girls (7%) reported that they had gambled in the previous 12 months. 12% of students gambled monthly or less, and 2% gambled more than twice a month. Betting on sports or animals (horses, dogs) was the most common gambling activity (15%), followed by lotteries (12%), cards or dice (9%), and slot machines (8.4%). The Lie/Bet questionnaire, a two-question screening tool was used to evaluate problem gambling behaviour. Of those who had gambled in the previous 12 months (n=300), 26% reported that they had felt the need to bet more and more money, and 12% reported that they had to lie to people important to them about how much they gambled.

Students reported on their internet and gaming activities. More than a third of respondents (37%) spent 2-3 hours on social media on a typical school day, and even more (39%) spent more than 6 hours on social media on a typical non-school day. Significant gender differences were observed for non-school day internet use with girls (98%) spending more hours on social media than boys (96%) did. Almost two-thirds (64%) strongly or partly agreed that they spend too much time on social media and 57% agreed that their parents say they spend too much time on social media. Problem internet use was assessed with three item statements and a majority of students either strongly agreed (26%) or partly agreed (37%) that they spend too much time on social media, while a third (33%) strongly or partly agreed that they get in a bad mood when unable to spend time on social media. Regarding gaming, students were asked how many hours they spent playing games with other people using a computer, tablet, console, smartphone or other electronic device during the previous 30 days. 44% spent some time playing games on a school day and 56% spent some time playing games on a typical non-school day. About a fifth (20%) agreed that they spend too much time gaming and also that their parents (23%) say they spend too much time gaming. More boys (84%) than girls (29%) spent time playing games on a typical non-school day.

In the past 25 years, repeated ESPAD surveys of 15-16-year olds in Ireland have reported major reductions in alcohol consumption, smoking and the use of many substances. The largest reductions have been in the use of illicit drugs which, between 1995 and 2019, fell by 69% and in cigarette smoking which fell by 66%. In the same period there has been a 41% decrease in alcohol consumption and a 30% reduction in heavy episodic ['binge'] drinking. Observations regarding illicit drug use in the 1995-2019 time period are also positive suggesting a halt or even a reversal. There is cause for concern, however. Our trend analyses from 2015 to 2019 show that these declining figures have not continued for all substances and, in fact, have begun to increase again for some. Since 2015, increases have been observed in current alcohol use (14%), heavy episodic ['binge'] drinking (18%), current smoking (8%), and cannabis use (5%). Of particular note is the 50% rise in e-cigarette current use, suggesting that the popularity of e-cigarettes is on the rise among young people in Ireland. These results call for continued targeted high-intensity campaigns and education initiatives, as well as policy and legislative change to protect adolescent health.

SAMPLE & METHODS

ESPAD survey Ireland, 2019

The European School Survey Project
On Alcohol and Other Drugs
www.espad.org

- 1 Describes the use of various substances and risk behaviors among adolescents
- 2 Monitors trends in substance use in Europe over the past 24 years (1995-2019)
- 3 Examines relevant influences on these behaviors

1949 Students
took part in the survey

Students were born in 2003
15 or 16 years old in 3rd, 4th & 5th year

50 Schools

took part in the survey

SCHOOLS WERE RANDOMISED AND STRATIFIED BY

- Geographical region
- School type
- Religious affiliation
- Gender
- Disadvantage status

49% were male students

51% were female students

ESPAD Ireland is one of 35 ESPAD Europe Countries

1. METHODOLOGY

Aims of the Study

The main purpose of the European School Survey Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) is to collect comparable data on substance use among European students aged 15 and 16 in order to monitor trends within, as well as between, countries. The 2019 wave of the ESPAD survey marked the seventh occasion that Ireland has participated in this collaborative international project. Additional aims of the project include:

- To describe the prevalence of the use of alcohol and other drugs among students born in 2003 (aged 15-16 years old);
- to compare prevalence and other relevant influences with ESPAD data gathered over the past twenty-four years;
- to provide the opportunity for comparison between European countries regarding substance use; and
- to indicate main trends in substance use over time.

Sample and Recruitment

The target population of the study was students born in 2003, who were 15-16 years old at the time of the survey. A list of all secondary schools in Ireland was compiled from Department of Education and skills (Education.ie, 2014). The schools were then divided into geographic regions based on Ireland's regional authorities: Border, West, Midlands, Mid-East, Dublin, South-East, South-West, and Mid-West. A proportional number of schools from each region was calculated, as was a proportional number of schools based on school type (secondary, vocational, community/comprehensive), religious affiliation (Roman Catholic, church of Ireland, inter-denominational), gender (males, females, mixed), and school-level disadvantage status (DEIS vs. non-DEIS). Schools were randomly arranged in a list and selected incrementally (every third, fourth, etc.) based on the total number of schools required from the region. Totals were calculated in each of the stratification categories and adjustments were made in required areas (i.e. DEIS status) by returning to the list and taking the next available school on the list after the rejected school.

Principals from each school were mailed a personalized letter via post introducing the ESPAD study and explaining its purpose, along with a letter from the Department of Health in support of the project (see Appendix 1). We also sent this information to all principals via email when available. We asked all principals to return an enclosed postcard (stamped and addressed) with the name of a cooperating/coordinating teacher who would be the point of contact for participation. In the initial letter to principals, it was emphasized that participation was voluntary but appreciated.

Among schools who agreed to participate, a cooperating teacher was identified, as per previous ESPAD administrations. This strategy aims to streamline the data collection process by appointing a key liaison and reducing the amount of coordinating and involvement required by administrators (Morgan 2008, 2012). Upon receipt of the cooperating teacher's contact details, we established contact either by phone or email to provide additional information regarding the project; specifically, we informed teachers about the targeted sample.

The majority of students born in 2003 were in the 4th year in school (frequently in Transition Year). However, there were also targeted students in 3rd and 5th year. Following the lead of previous EPSAD administrations, the following strategy was adopted: in every participating school, one 4th year class was selected. Then, in half the schools, a third-year class was selected and in the other half, a fifth year class was selected. The ultimate aim was to target two classes in each school, including a 4th year and either a 3rd year or a 5th year.

After making contact with the cooperating teacher, we determined the number of students in 4th class and one of the other

participating classes (3rd or 5th), as well as the target administration date, and we mailed the cooperating teacher a package with the following enclosed:

- Information sheets for parents and students
- Non-consent forms for parents
- Questionnaires
- Envelopes for completed questionnaires
- A manual for the cooperating teacher, outlining administration instructions
- A pre-paid return envelope for completed questionnaires¹

Cooperating teachers confirmed an administration date and were responsible for administering the questionnaire in their school. The instructions to cooperating teachers emphasised the following: (1) participation was voluntary: no-one was required to participate if they did not wish to be involved; (2) it was important that the students take the completion of the questionnaire seriously; and (3) it was crucial that they realize that their responses are confidential and anonymous. After completing the questionnaire, they returned the data (in individually sealed envelopes) to TFRI for processing. Survey data was collected from 3,565 young people in Ireland from 50 randomly selected post-primary schools.

ESPAD 2019 Questionnaire

The basic ESPAD questionnaire is agreed by an international committee and all countries use this same instrument. However, individual countries are allowed to make amendments and additions that are specifically related to their unique national circumstances. This section provides an overview of the 2019 questionnaire, including mention of the modifications that were unique to the Irish measure. A full version of this questionnaire is included in Appendix 2.

Introduction/Demographics

This section of the questionnaire concerned demographic and related background information, including age, gender and average grade in school. Other questions related to pastimes, including hobbies, reading and sports.

Cigarette Smoking

This section included questions on cigarette smoking, including lifetime use and current frequency. It also questioned ease of access to cigarettes, the perceived risk of smoking occasionally or heavily, and the age at which respondents started smoking. Questions regarding the use of e-cigarettes were also included; in particular, the reason for first using an e-cigarette, respondents' lifetime and current use of e-cigarettes and the respondents' tobacco-smoking status at the time they started using e-cigarettes.

Alcohol Consumption

This section focused on alcohol consumption, including the number of occasions the respondents had drunk alcohol over their lifetimes, during the last year and during the last month. Other questions related to the age of their first drinking experience, particular alcoholic beverages consumed during the last 30 days and peer drinking and drunkenness and binge drinking. A number of questions focused on the last occasion that the respondent had consumed alcohol, including the amount drunk, where the alcohol was obtained and the extent to which they felt drunk on this occasion. Other questions asked about the number of times of feeling drunk (lifetime, last year, last month) and whether or not respondents had experienced a range of consequences of alcohol consumption. Finally, they were asked where they consumed the alcohol on the last occasion when they drank.

Cannabis Use

This section includes the number of occasions cannabis was used during their lifetime, the previous 12 months and the

previous 30 days, the age of initiation, perceived ease of access to cannabis, the perceived risk of trying cannabis once or twice and using it occasionally and regularly. Cannabis refusal skills were explored by asking how many times the respondent has had the opportunity to use marijuana without using it. The questionnaire also included the 7-item Cannabis Abuse Screening Test (Legleye *et al.*, 2007) in order to assess cannabis-related problems and items on cannabis cliques and peer cannabis use.

Illicit Drug Use

This section included a number of questions regarding the use of illicit substances, such as ecstasy, cocaine, heroin, amphetamines, methamphetamines, crack, magic mushrooms, LSD, anabolic steroids, GHB. Respondents were also asked about their use of legal substances in order to ‘get high’, such as tranquilisers without a prescription, inhalants, painkillers and alcohol with pills, and new substances, or ‘legal highs’. Questions about lifetime and 12-month use, perceived ease of access, perceived risk and age of initiation were also included.

Ethical Issues

Obtaining informed consent is a standard ethical procedure in human-based research. It involves making participants aware of the nature of the research and disclosing information to enable them to make an informed decision regarding participation. In order to properly inform participants about the nature of the research and their rights as participants, it is important to provide all stakeholders with targeted and accessible information. All principals, teachers, and students were provided with population-tailored information sheets prior to survey administration. All parties were informed that participation was voluntary, anonymous, and confidential. Parents were provided with a non-consent form, allowing them to opt-out of the research if they were uncomfortable with their child’s participation. Students were also informed that they could skip any questions that they did not want to answer and that the survey was not a test, nor part of any mandatory coursework (Appendix 1). Given the potentially sensitive nature of some of these questions, students were provided with envelopes along with their surveys. After they completed the questionnaire, they sealed their responses in an envelope, ensuring that other students and/or teachers could not see their answers. Prior to commencing field work, ethical approval was granted by Dublin Institute of Technology’s Ethics Committee.

Data Collection Entry and Analysis

Data collection began in March 2019 and continued through to May 2019. All data was subsequently entered exactly as it appeared in the survey. Data was entered manually into SPSS v22 by Seefin Data Ltd. Data entry was cross-checked via double entry for 20% of surveys. The dataset was cleaned and respondents with high levels of missing responses or patterns of extreme, low-frequency responses (or ‘mischievous responders’) were removed (see Appendix 3). All descriptive statistics were calculated in SPSS v22.

3,565 surveys were completed by young people from 50 randomly selected post-primary schools and received by the TobaccoFree Research Institute. Of these participants, 1,967 were born in 2003 and will be included in the international ESPAD dataset. Once the dataset was cleaned and ‘mischievous responders’ or non-responders were removed, 1,949 were retained for analysis. This included 946 male students (48.5%) and 1003 female students (51.5%).

2. SUBSTANCE USE IN IRELAND 1995-2015

One of the main objectives of the ESPAD project is to track changes in substance use over time. To date, there have been seven survey waves with data collection taking place every four years from 1995. Twenty countries participated in all waves, including Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Faroe Islands), Eastern Europe (Croatia, Czech, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Slovak Rep, Slovenia, Ukraine) and Southern Europe (Cyprus, Italy, Malta, Portugal), as well as Ireland. Data from these twenty countries were combined centrally by ESPAD to produce the trend average (ESPAD 20).

The ESPAD 20 data for use of various substances was compared to Ireland's data from each wave from 1995 to 2015. These key substances and behaviours were 30-day alcohol consumption, heavy episodic drinking, current smoking and lifetime use of cannabis, inhalants, tranquilisers and other substances. The data was also broken down by gender, although the gender differences in each European country were obscured in the ESPAD 20 average.

Alcohol Use

Alcohol use over the past 30 days was examined revealing a large decline for Ireland. Alcohol use in Ireland peaked in 1999 at 74% after which there was a steep decline among Irish youth. By 2015, the last 30 days prevalence of alcohol use among Irish youth was 36%. There were smaller differences between male and female students in Ireland. In 1999, 2003, 2011 and 2015, more female students drank alcohol, while in 2007, more male students did.

In ESPAD 20, alcohol use over the past 30 days revealed a decline since 1995 and male students had a slightly higher prevalence of alcohol consumption although there was no difference in alcohol consumption between male and female students in 2015 for ESPAD 20.

Alcohol use past 30 days						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	69%	69%	69%	58%	53%	56%
1999	73%	75%	74%	62%	57%	60%
2003	71%	74%	73%	63%	59%	61%
2007	57%	56%	56%	59%	58%	58%
2011	48%	52%	50%	58%	53%	56%
2015	35%	37%	36%	48%	48%	48%

Table 2.1: Alcohol use in the past 30 days since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.1: Alcohol use in the past 30 days from 1995 to 2015 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Heavy episodic drinking

Heavy episodic drinking was examined, and in Ireland, this behaviour increased between 1995 and 1999 and was constant between 1999 and 2003. Although data was missing for Ireland for 2007, a steep decline was observed between 2003 and 2011, a reduction from 57% to 40%. There was further decline in the average prevalence of heavy episodic drinking in Ireland, with the prevalence in 2015 reaching 28%.

In ESPAD 20, there was an increase in heavy episodic drinking from an average of 35% in 195 to 48% in 2015. There were also noticeable differences in heavy episodic drinking among male and female students in ESPAD 20 with more male students than female students participating in this behaviour.

Heavy episodic drinking past 30 days						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	52%	42%	47%	41%	29%	35%
1999	57%	56%	57%	46%	34%	40%
2003	57%	57%	57%	45%	35%	40%
2007	-	-	-	45%	41%	43%
2011	40%	41%	40%	43%	38%	41%
2015	28%	28%	28%	49%	46%	48%

Table 2.2: Heavy episodic drinking in the past 30 days from 1995 to 2015 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.2: Heavy episodic drinking in the past 30 days since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

30-day cigarette use

In Ireland in 1995, the prevalence of smoking in the last 30 days was 41%; however, Ireland has also demonstrated a clear decline in smoking with a prevalence of 13% in 2015. There was a particularly steep decline between 2003 and 2007, the period when the Smoke-Free Workplaces legislation was introduced. Consistently more female than male students smoked in Ireland although there was no gender difference in 2015. The difference was smaller in 2011 than in previous years, as the smoking rate for male students did not decline between 2007 and 2011.

Compared to Ireland, current smoking was much higher among the ESPAD 20 average although there was a general decline in current smoking from 32% in 1995 to 21% in 2015. Slightly more male than female students smoked in the ESPAD 20 average

Cigarette use during the last 30 days						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	37%	45%	41%	34%	30%	32%
1999	32%	42%	37%	37%	34%	35%
2003	28%	37%	33%	35%	33%	34%
2007	19%	27%	23%	28%	29%	28%
2011	19%	23%	21%	30%	29%	29%
2015	13%	13%	13%	22%	21%	21%

Table 2.3: Current cigarette use since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.3: 30-day cigarette use since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime cannabis use

The prevalence of cannabis use among students was examined. There was a steep decline in Irish cannabis use between 2003 and 2011, as there was in smoking tobacco. There was however an increase in lifetime cannabis use in the ESPAD 20 average from 11% in 1995 to 16% in 2015

For both Ireland and ESPAD 20, more male students used cannabis than female students, with the exception Irelands peak of 39% in 2003, when slightly more female than male students used cannabis.

Lifetime use of cannabis						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	42%	31%	37%	13%	8%	11%
1999	35%	29%	32%	19%	12%	15%
2003	38%	39%	39%	22%	16%	19%
2007	23%	17%	20%	20%	14%	17%
2011	22%	15%	18%	20%	14%	17%
2015	22%	16%	19%	19%	14%	16%

Table 2.4: Lifetime use of cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.4: Lifetime use of cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime inhalant use

Lifetime use of inhalants in Ireland showed a decline from a high of 22% of 1999 to 9% in 2011 and a slight increase to 10% in 2015. Data on lifetime use of inhalants was not collected from Ireland in 1995.

Female students had a higher rate of inhalant use than did male students in all data collection years except 1999 where male students had a higher rate and in 2015 where male and female students had a similar rate of inhalant use (10%-10%). In the ESPAD 20 average, there was a contrasting trend lifetime inhalant use between 8-10% until 2015 where there was a noticeable decline to 7%. Male students had a higher or equal rate of inhalant use with the exception of 2015 where female students had a slightly higher rate of inhalant use.

Lifetime use of inhalants to get high						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	-	-	-	10%	8%	9%
1999	22%	21%	22%	9%	7%	8%
2003	14%	21%	18%	10%	8%	9%
2007	14%	16%	15%	9%	8%	8%
2011	8%	11%	9%	10%	10%	10%
2015	10%	10%	10%	6%	7%	7%

Table 2.5: Lifetime use of inhalants since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.5: Lifetime use of inhalants since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime use of tranquilizers without prescription

Overall, there was a low percentage of respondents using tranquilisers without a prescription (10% or lower in all waves) in both Ireland and ESPAD 20. In Ireland, tranquiliser use declined from 7% in 1995 to 2% in 2003 and subsequently increased slightly to 3%. The lowest prevalence in the Irish data occurred in 2003, a year when cannabis use was particularly high. In ESPAD 20, use of tranquilizers without prescription averaged 6-8 across all waves.

A higher percentage of female students than male students used tranquilisers in 1995 and 2007, but fewer female students used tranquilisers in 1999. In ESPAD 20, more females than males used tranquilisers without prescription.

Lifetime use of tranquilizer without prescription						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	6%	9%	7%	6%	10%	8%
1999	5%	4%	5%	6%	9%	8%
2003	2%	2%	2%	5%	8%	7%
2007	2%	4%	3%	5%	9%	7%
2011	3%	3%	3%	6%	9%	7%
2015	3%	3%	3%	5%	8%	6%

Table 2.6: Lifetime use of tranquilizers since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.6: Lifetime use of tranquilizers since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime use of other substances

Illicit drug use has fallen dramatically from 16% in 1995 to 9% in 1999 and fell again from 10% in 2007 to 6% in 2011. However, there was a slight increase in illicit drug use in Ireland in 2015 (7%). In ESPAD 20, use of other substances increased from 3% in 2015 to 6 percent in 1999 and has remained at 6% since 1999.

There was a change in differences between male and female students in Ireland across the six waves. In Ireland, a higher percentage of male students used illicit drugs in 1995, 1999, 2011 and 2015, while a higher percentage of female students used illicit drugs in the intervening years, 2003 and 2007. In ESPAD 20, the gender differences remained constant across all waves.

Lifetime use of illicit drugs other than cannabis						
Year	Ireland			ESPAD 20		
	Male	Female	All	Male	Female	All
1995	19%	12%	16%	4%	2%	3%
1999	11%	8%	9%	7%	5%	6%
2003	8%	10%	9%	6%	5%	6%
2007	9%	10%	10%	7%	6%	6%
2011	8%	5%	6%	7%	5%	6%
2015	8%	6%	7%	5%	7%	6%

Table 2.7: Lifetime use of illicit drugs other than cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Figure 2.7: Lifetime use of illicit drugs other than cannabis from 1995 to 2015 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Summary

In Ireland, the use of alcohol, alcohol in excessive quantities, cigarettes, cannabis, inhalants, tranquilisers without a prescription and other illicit drugs has fallen over the six data collection waves from 1995 to 2015. While alcohol use and heavy episodic drinking increased between 1995 and 1999 and cannabis use increased between 1999 and 2003, the use of these substances subsequently fell, with an overall decrease by 2015. Particularly large declines have been observed for ‘other’ illicit drugs (-56%), inhalants (-55%) and tranquilisers (-57%) between 1995 and 2015, with cannabis use (-49%) and smoking (-68%) prevalence falling by half or more. Drinking alcohol and heavy episodic drinking reduced by the smallest proportions but were still reduced by 48% and 40% respectively.

In contrast, the ESPAD 20 average observed decreases in alcohol use (-14%), smoking (-34%), inhalants (-13%) and tranquilisers (-25%) only. There was an increase in cannabis (45) and use of other illicit substances (67%). However, the nature of the trend average obscures changes occurring in individual countries or regions.

Percentage change in substance use						
Substance	Ireland			ESPAD		
	1995	2015	% change	1995	2015	% change
Alcohol Use	69%	36%	-48%	56%	48%	-14%
Heavy episodic drinking	47%	28%	-40%	35%	48%	0%
Smoking	41%	13%	-68%	32%	21%	-34%
Cannabis	37%	19%	-49%	11%	16%	+45%
Inhalants (<i>from 1999</i>)	22%	10%	-55%	8%	7%	-13%
Tranquilizers	7%	3%	-57%	8%	6%	-25%
Other illicit substances	16%	7%	-56%	3	5%	+67%

Table 2.8: Lifetime use of illicit drugs other than cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

ALCOHOL

ESPAD
The European School Survey Project
On Alcohol and Other Drugs

73% Of respondents had consumed alcohol in their lifetime

Beer (33%) and Cider (32%) were the most popular among male students

Spirits (31%) and Cider (28%) were the most popular among female students

Wine was the least popular

17% vs 15%
More girls than boys reported drunkenness in the last 30 days.

Most students first drank alcohol at age 15 (32%) or 14 (29%)

Most students first got drunk aged 15 (52%) or 14 (28%)

29% Drank 5+ drinks on one occasion in the last 30 days

Most frequent reasons for alcohol use

- "to make social gatherings more fun" (49%)
- "helps me to enjoy a party" (48%)

NEGATIVE OUTCOMES FROM ALCOHOL USE

DUE TO ALCOHOL

Girls (3%) were more likely than boys (2%) to be victims of unwanted sexual advances

Girls (9%) were more likely than boys (4%) to be involved in an accident or injury

28% perceived ease of access to alcoholic drinks

71% perceived great risk in consuming 4 to 5 drinks nearly every day

3. DRINKING AND ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION

ESPAD 2019 included a number of items related to alcohol consumption over lifetime, the last 12 months and the last 30 days, being drunk, consumption of particular drinks, perceived access to alcohol, age of drinking initiation, binge-drinking and experienced consequences of alcohol use. Socioeconomic status, school attendance and attainment, parental monitoring, household type and peer alcohol use were examined to see if these were related to alcohol consumption in this cohort. This chapter discusses the main results regarding drinking and alcohol consumption and factors related to drinking and alcohol consumption.

Alcohol Consumption

Lifetime Alcohol Consumption

Respondents were asked about their lifetime alcohol consumption. Table 3.1 shows that 27.4% (n=516) of students had never consumed alcohol in their lifetime compared to a total of 72.6% (1364) who had consumed alcohol.

There were statistically significant differences in lifetime alcohol consumption by gender¹, with 72.4% of females (n=700) and 72.7% males (n=664) reporting having had alcohol in their lifetime.

Lifetime Alcohol Consumption* <i>*number of occasions</i>	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	249	27.3	267	27.6	516	27.4
Once or Twice	151	16.5	180	18.6	331	17.6
3 to 5 times	120	13.1	136	14.1	256	13.6
6 to 9 times	106	11.6	103	10.7	209	11.1
10 to 19 times	113	12.4	138	14.3	251	13.4
20 to 39 times	67	7.3	74	7.7	141	7.5
40 times or more	107	11.7	69	7.1	176	9.4
Total	913	100.0	967	100.0	1880	100.0

Table 3.1: Lifetime alcohol consumption by gender

Alcohol consumption in the last 12 months

When students were asked to consider how often they had consumed alcohol in the last 12 months (Table 3.2), 65.2% (n=1228) in total reported that they had consumed alcohol in the last 12 months with 4.1% (77) reporting that they had consumed alcohol over 40 times. There were statistically significant differences by gender in alcohol consumption in the last 12 months². More male students (5.4%, n=50) than female students (2.8%, n=27) reported consuming alcohol 40 times or more.

¹ Lifetime: [$\chi^2(6)=13.714$, $p=0.033$, Cramer's $V=.085$]

² 12 months: [$\chi^2(6)=12.440$, $p=0.053$, Cramer's $V=.053$]

Alcohol consumption in the last 12 months* *number of occasions	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	318	34.6	338	35.0	656	34.8
Once or Twice	180	19.6	210	21.7	390	20.7
3 to 5 times	119	13.0	137	14.2	256	13.6
6 to 9 times	101	11.0	116	12.0	217	11.5
10 to 19 times	98	10.7	98	10.1	196	10.4
20 to 39 times	52	5.7	40	4.1	92	4.9
40 times or more	50	5.4	27	2.8	77	4.1
Total	918	100.0	966	100.0	1884	100.0

Table 3.2: Alcohol consumption in the last 12 months by gender

Alcohol consumption in the last 30 days

As can be seen from Table 3.3, 40.8% (779) reported that they had consumed alcohol in the last 30 days and were considered current drinkers as compared to 59.2% (n=1131) who had not had alcohol in the last 30 days. More male (42.1%, n=393) than female students (39.5%, n=386) reported using alcohol in the last 30 days³.

Number of occasions of consuming alcohol- 30 days	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	541	57.9	590	60.5	1131	59.2
Once or twice	208	22.3	239	24.5	447	23.4
3 to 5 times	87	9.3	94	9.6	181	9.5
6 to 9 times	49	5.2	32	3.3	81	4.2
10 times or more	49	5.2	20	2.1	70	3.7
Total	934	100.0	976	100.0	1910	100.0

Table 3.3: Alcohol consumption in the last 30 days by gender

Reports of being drunk

Lifetime drunkenness

Overall, 64.3% of students had never been drunk in their lifetime compared to 35.7% (n=715) who had. Results (Table 3.4) also show that 16.3% (n=313) had been drunk once or twice in their lifetime compared to only a small number of students (1.5%, n=30) who had been drunk more than 40 times. There were no statistically significant differences in lifetime alcohol consumption by gender⁴ although more females (36.8%, n= 363) than males (34.5%, n=322) reported being drunk in their lifetime.

³ 30 days: [X²(6)=18.731, p=0.005, Cramer's V=.099]

⁴ Lifetime: [X²(6)=7.665, p=0.264, Cramer's V=.063]

Number of occasions drunk in lifetime	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	610	65.5	624	63.2	1234	64.3
Once or twice	135	14.5	178	18.0	313	16.3
3 to 5 times	77	8.3	88	8.9	165	8.6
6 to 9 times	43	4.6	45	4.6	88	4.6
10 to 19 times	31	3.3	27	2.7	58	3.0
20 to 39 times	19	2.0	12	1.2	31	1.6
40 times or more	17	1.8	13	1.3	30	1.5
Total	932	100.0	987	100.0	1949	100.0

Table 3.4: Number of occasions drunk in lifetime by gender

Being drunk in the past 12 months

Overall, 32% (n=612) of students reported being drunk in the last 12 months and 17.5% of students reported being drunk once or twice in the last twelve months (Table 3.5). There were no statistically significant differences in drunkenness in the past 12 months by gender⁵. However, Table 3.5 shows that more females (33.7%, n=332) than males (30.3%, n=280) had been drunk in the past 12 months.

Number of occasions drunk in the last 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	644	69.7	654	66.3	1298	68.0
Once or twice	144	15.6	190	19.3	334	17.5
3 to 5 times	65	7.0	68	6.9	133	7.0
6 to 9 times	30	3.2	43	4.4	73	3.8
10 to 19 times	27	2.9	19	1.9	46	2.4
20 to 39 times	9	1.0	6	0.6	15	0.8
40 times or more	5	0.5	6	0.6	11	0.5
Total	924	100.0	986	100.0	1910	100.0

Table 3.5: Drunkenness in the past 12 months by gender

Being drunk in the past 30 days

As can be seen in Table 3.6, 16.1% (309) reported being drunk in the last 30 days and 12.8% (n=245) reported being drunk once or twice in the past 30 days. Again, more females (17.1%, n=168) than males (15.1%, n=141) reported being drunk in the last month. Statistically significant differences were observed for alcohol consumption in the last 30 days by gender⁶.

⁵ 12 months: [$\chi^2(6)=8.874$, $p=0.181$, Cramer's $V=.068$]

⁶ 30 days: [$\chi^2(6)=16.234$, $p=0.013$, Cramer's $V=.092$]

Number of occasions drunk in the last 30 days	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	790	84.9	817	82.9	1607	83.9
Once or twice	103	11.1	142	14.4	245	12.8
3 to 5 times	26	2.8	11	1.1	37	1.9
6 to 9 times	5	0.5	10	1.0	15	0.8
10 to 19 times	5	0.5	1	0.1	6	0.3
20 to 39 times	1	0.1	2	0.2	3	0.2
40 times or more	1	0.1	2	0.2	3	0.2
Total	931	100.0	985	100.0	1916	100.0

Table 3.6: Drunkenness in the past 30 days by gender

Level of intoxication

Students were asked to indicate how drunk they were the last day they drank alcohol on a scale of 1 to 10 with 1 representing “Not at all” and 10 representing “Heavily intoxicated”. Responses are presented in Table 3.7. There was no statistically significant difference in the mean score on the drunkenness scale⁷ between male (M=5.50, SD=4.05) and female students (M=5.89, SD=4.04), with male and female students being equally likely to report intoxication including heavy intoxication.

Drunkenness scale	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	262	28.3	241	24.5	503	26.3
2	70	7.6	77	7.8	147	7.7
3	80	8.6	57	5.8	137	7.2
4	49	5.3	64	6.5	113	5.9
5	33	3.6	51	5.2	84	4.4
6	47	5.1	53	5.4	100	5.2
7	57	6.2	58	5.9	115	6.0
8	43	4.6	49	5.0	92	4.8
9	14	1.5	23	2.3	37	1.9
Heavily intoxicated	37	4.0	27	2.7	64	3.4
Never drank alcohol	233	25.2	285	28.9	518	27.1
Total	925	100.0	985	100.0	1910	100.0

Table 3.7: Level of intoxication last day drank

Consumption of particular drinks

Particular drinks consumed in the past 30 days

Table 3.8 shows the results of students’ responses regarding consumption of particular drinks in the past 30 days. The most consumed drink in the last 30 days was cider (28.5%, n=552), followed closely by beer (27.3%, n=529) and spirits (27.1%, n=524). The least consumed drink was wine (8.3%, n=161). As can be seen in Table 3.8, females consumed more

⁷ Level of Intoxication: [t(1908)= -2.126, p=.705]

premixed drinks, wine and spirits than males did, while males consumed more beer and cider than did females. There were statistically significant differences by gender in the consumption of all alcoholic drinks (beer⁸, cider⁹, premixed drinks¹⁰, wine¹¹ and spirits¹²).

Types of beverage	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Beer	339	36.1	190	19.1	529	27.3
Cider	303	32.2	249	25.0	552	28.5
Premixed drinks (sprints, alcopops)	90	9.6	186	18.7	276	14.2
Wine	53	5.6	108	10.8	161	8.3
Spirits	204	21.7	320	32.1	524	27.1

Table 3.8: Consumption of particular drinks in the last 30 days by gender

Perceived access to alcohol

Students were asked how difficult they thought it would be to get particular alcoholic drinks. Table 3.9 shows the results of students' responses for each category by type of alcoholic drink. Results show that the majority of students believed it would be 'fairly easy' or 'very easy' to obtain all types of alcoholic drinks mentioned. A high number of students also thought it would be 'very easy' to obtain Cider (36.5%, n=707) or beer (35.8%, n=693). Only 8.5% (n=165) believed it would be impossible to obtain spirits compared to 30.65 (n=592) who said it would be 'very easy' to access.

Type of beverages	Impossible		Very difficult		Fairly difficult		Fairly easy		Very easy		Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Beer	98	5.1	108	5.6	248	12.8	683	35.3	693	35.8	105	5.4	1935	100.0
Cider	108	5.6	114	5.9	262	13.5	603	31.2	707	36.5	141	7.3	1935	100.0
Premixed drinks (sprints, alcopops)	141	7.3	176	9.1	309	16.0	544	28.1	545	28.2	220	11.4	1935	100.0
Wine	123	6.4	190	9.8	350	18.1	564	29.2	525	27.2	181	9.4	1933	100.0
Spirits	165	8.5	179	9.3	284	14.7	546	28.2	592	30.6	168	8.7	1934	100.0

Table 3.9: Perceived access by beverage type

Students who responded 'don't know' to perceived access to particular alcoholic drinks were categorized by gender. As can be seen in Table 3.10, a higher number of students answered 'don't know' when asked how difficult it would be to obtain premixed drinks (10.8%, n=220). Results also show that more male than female students did not know how difficult it would be to get premixed drinks and wine.

⁸ Beer: [X²(1)=70.491, p<.001, Cramer's V=.091]

⁹ Cider: [X²(1)=12.512, p<.001, Cramer's V=.080]

¹⁰ Premixed drinks: [X²(1)=32.658, p<.001, Cramer's V=.130]

¹¹ Wine: [X²(1)=17.129, p<.001, Cramer's V=.094]

¹² Spirits: [X²(1)=26.489, p<.001, Cramer's V=.117]

Don't know	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Beer	46	4.9	59	5.9	105	5.4
Cider	64	6.8	77	7.7	141	7.3
Premixed drinks (sprints, alcopops)	112	12.0	108	10.8	220	11.4
Wine	94	10.0	87	8.7	181	9.4
Spirits	78	8.3	90	9.0	168	8.7

Table 3.10: Responded 'Don't know' by beverage type and gender

Age of Initiation

Age of first trying alcohol

Students were asked at what age they first drank alcohol (at least one glass). Due to low number of responses in certain age groups, responses were recoded into '12 years or younger', '13 years old', '14 years old', '15 years old', and '16 years or older' and results are presented in Table 3.11.

Age of first trying alcohol	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	308	32.2	322	32.2	630	32.6
12 years or younger	160	17.1	105	10.5	265	13.7
13 years old	98	10.5	98	9.8	196	10.1
14 years old	162	17.3	222	22.2	384	19.9
15 years old	189	20.2	233	23.3	422	21.8
16 years or older	18	1.9	19	1.9	37	1.9
Total	935	100.0	999	100.0	1934	100.0

Table 3.11: Age of first trying alcohol by gender

The most common age for trying alcohol was 15 years (21.8%, n=422), closely followed by 14 years (19.9%, n=384). Results also show that more female students first tried alcohol at age 15 (23.3%, n=233) and 14 (22.2%, n=222) than did male students [15 (20.2%, n=189), 14 (17.3%, n=162)], while males were more likely to report early initiation at age 12 years of less. There were statistically significant differences in age of first trying alcohol by gender¹³

¹³ Age of first trying alcohol: [$\chi^2 (8) = 30.309, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .125$]

Figure 3.1: Age of first trying beer by gender

Age of first getting drunk

Students were also asked at what age they first got drunk. Again, due to low number of responses in certain age groups, responses were recoded into ‘12 years or younger’, ‘13 years old’, ‘14 years old’, ‘15 years old’, and ‘16 years or older’ and the results are presented in Table 3.12. Most students (60.3%, n=1152) had never been drunk while the majority of students who said that they had “got drunk on alcohol” had done so at 15 years old (20.5%, n=392). There were statistically significant differences between male and female students¹⁴ in reported age of first getting drunk.

Age of first getting drunk	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	565	61.1	587	59.5	1152	60.3
12 years or younger	22	2.4	9	0.9	31	1.6
13 years old	46	5.0	25	2.5	71	3.7
14 years old	102	11.0	113	11.4	215	11.3
15 years old	164	17.7	228	23.1	392	20.5
16 years or older	25	2.7	25	2.5	50	2.6
Total	924	100.0	987	100.0	1911	100.0

Table 3.12: Age of first getting drunk by gender

Binge-Drinking

Binge-drinking during the last 30 days

Students were asked on how many occasions over the last 30 days they had consumed five or more drinks on one occasion (heavy episodic drinking or “binge” drinking). Responses presented in Table 3.13 show that while 67.5% students (n=1307) had not consumed 5 or more drinks in the last 30 days, 18.2% (n=351) had done so once or twice in the last 30 days and 14.4% (n=278) had done so more than 3 times in the last 30 days. No statistically significant differences between male and

¹⁴ First feeling drunk [$\chi^2(8) = 23.722, p=.003, \text{Cramer's } V=.111$]

female students¹⁵ were observed regarding the number of binge-drinking occasions.

Binge-drinking occasions	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	629	67.0	678	68.0	1307	67.5
Once	91	9.7	94	9.4	185	9.6
Twice	69	7.3	97	9.8	166	8.6
3 to 5 times	91	9.7	84	8.4	175	9.0
6 to 9 times	33	3.5	30	3.0	63	3.3
10 times or more	26	2.8	14	1.4	40	2.1
Total	939	100.0	997	100.0	1936	100.0

Table 3.13: Binge-drinking in the last 30 days by gender

Consequences of alcohol use

Experienced consequences of alcohol use

Students were asked if they had experienced any of a number of negative consequences while under the influence of alcohol during the last 12 months. Results are presented in Table 3.14, showing the percentage who answered yes to each item and including the results of the chi-square test for each item.

Experienced consequences of alcohol use in the last 12 months	Male		Female		Total		Chi-Square Test
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Involved in a fight	54	5.8	43	4.3	97	5.0	$X^2(1) = 2.089, p = .148$ Cramer's $V = .033$
Injury or accident	46	4.9	92	9.2	138	7.2	$X^2(1) = 13.358, p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .083$
Damaged or lost property	72	7.7	137	13.8	209	10.8	$X^2(1) = 18.449, p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .098$
Been in a serious argument	50	5.4	78	7.9	128	6.7	$X^2(1) = 4.825, p = .028$ Cramer's $V = .050$
Victim of robbery or theft	11	1.2	16	1.6	27	1.4	$X^2(1) = .624, p = .430$ Cramer's $V = .018$
Been in trouble with the police	42	4.5	35	3.5	77	4.0	$X^2(1) = 1.226, p = .268$ Cramer's $V = .025$
Hospitalized due to severe intoxication	11	1.2	8	0.8	19	1.0	$X^2(1) = .694, p = .405$ Cramer's $V = .019$
Hospitalized due to accident or injury	7	0.8	7	0.7	14	0.7	$X^2(1) = .017, p = .896$ Cramer's $V = .003$
Sexual intercourse without condom	34	3.6	32	3.2	66	3.4	$X^2(2) = .562, p = .755$ Cramer's $V = .017$
Victim of unwanted sexual advance	15	1.6	33	3.3	48	2.5	$X^2(2) = 6.647, p = .036$ Cramer's $V = .058$
Deliberate self-injury	17	1.8	18	1.8	35	1.8	$X^2(2) = .021, p = .990$ Cramer's $V = .003$
Drunk-driving	9	1.0	8	0.8	17	0.9	$X^2(2) = .916, p = .633$ Cramer's $V = .022$
Drunk-driving accident	6	0.6	2	0.2	8	0.4	$X^2(2) = 4.710, p = .095$ Cramer's $V = .049$
Swimming in deep water	20	2.1	16	1.6	36	1.8	$X^2(2) = 4.496, p = .106$ Cramer's $V = .048$

Table 3.14: Consequences of alcohol consumption

¹⁵ First feeling drunk [$X^2(8) = 23.722, p = .003, \text{Cramer's } V = .111$]

The most commonly reported negative consequences of alcohol use in the last 12 months (Table 3.14) were “damaged or lost property” (10.8%, n=209), “injury or accident” (7.2%, n=138), “been in a serious argument” (6.7%, n=128), “involved in a fight” (5.0%, n=98), and “been in trouble with the police” (4.0%, n=77). As can be seen in Table 3.14, female students (13.8%, n=137) were more likely to damage or lose property than were male students (7.7%, n=72). Similarly, female students (9.2%, n=92) were more likely to have an injury or be involved in an accident than were male students (4.9%, n=46). Female students (3.3%, n=33) were also more likely to be victims of unwanted sexual advance (1.6%, n=15) while under the influence of alcohol. Results also show that more male than female students reported having been involved in a fight, drunk-driving accidents, hospitalized due to intoxication, and in trouble with the police while under the influence of alcohol.

Perceived risk

Students were asked how much they thought people risked harming themselves physically or in other ways if they consumed one or two drinks nearly every day, four to five drinks nearly every day, and five or more drinks nearly every weekend. Results are presented in Table 3.15.

Number of drinks	No risk		Slight risk		Moderate risk		Great risk		Don't know	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
One or two drinks nearly every day	153	7.9	382	19.8	804	41.7	529	27.4	60	3.1
Four to five drinks nearly every day	94	4.9	66	3.4	329	17.2	1355	70.6	74	3.9
Five drinks or more nearly every weekend	135	7.0	204	10.6	613	31.8	875	45.4	101	5.2

Table 3.15: Perceived risk of different levels of drinking

Results presented in Table 3.15 and Figure 3.2 show that more students perceived great risk from consuming four to five drinks nearly every day (70.6%, n=1355) compared to 4.9% (n=94) who answered no risk.

Students also perceived drinking five drinks or more every weekend as risky (45.4%, n=875), compared to 7% (n=135) who answered no risk. 27.4% (n=529) of students also said drinking one or two drinks nearly every day had great risk while 42.7% (n=804) said moderate risk and 19.8% (n=382) said slight risk. Only 7.9% (n=153) said there was no risk in consuming one or two alcoholic drinks nearly every day.

Figure 3.2: Perceived risk of different levels of alcohol consumption

Figure 3.2 shows that students were cognizant of the risks associated with alcohol consumption. Drinking one or two drinks nearly every day was perceived by 68% of students as carrying “great or moderate risk”; consuming four to five drinks nearly every day was perceived by 71% as carrying “great risk”, and consuming five drinks or more nearly every weekend was perceived by 45% as carrying “great risk” (by 77% as carrying “great or moderate risk”).

Drinking Motivation

Students were asked why they drank. From on a number of items, respondents could select more than one reason. As can be seen in Table 3.16, which shows the percentages of students who answered yes to each item, the most popular reasons for drinking over all were: “to makes social gatherings more fun” (48.6%, n=939); “to enjoy parties” (48.4%, n=933) and “it’s fun” (47.9%, n=924). The least popular motivations for drinking were “to be liked” (12.8%, n=247) and “to get high” (16.3%, n=314).

Drinking motivation	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
To enjoy parties	443	47.4	490	49.3	933	48.4
Helps when feeling depressed or nervous	151	16.2	217	21.8	368	19.1
To cheer up	177	18.9	251	25.2	428	22.2
Like the feeling	367	39.1	377	38.0	744	38.5
To get high	159	17.0	155	15.6	314	16.3
To make social gatherings more fun	455	48.5	484	48.7	939	48.6
To fit in with a group	192	20.6	221	22.2	413	21.4
Improves parties and celebrations	422	45.1	475	47.8	897	46.5
To forget about problems	161	17.2	232	23.3	393	20.4
It’s fun	430	46.1	494	49.7	924	47.9
To be liked	120	12.9	127	12.7	247	12.8
Not to feel left out	168	18.0	223	22.4	391	20.2

Table 3.16: Drinking motivation by gender

Summary

Students were asked several questions regarding their alcohol use, alcohol-related behaviour's and beliefs about alcohol. Overall, 72.6% of respondents had consumed alcohol in their lifetime. 65.2% of students had consumed alcohol in the last 12 months and 40.8% had consumed alcohol in the last 30 days. 35.7% of students had ever been drunk in their lifetime and 16.1% had been drunk in the last 30 days with more females (17%) than males (15%) reporting drunkenness.

With regards to type of drinks consumed in the past 30 days, cider was the most consumed drink (29%) and more males (32%) than females (25%) had consumed cider in the past 30 days. The least popular drinks were wine (8%) and premixed drinks (14%). 18.2% of respondents had engaged in binge drinking once or twice in the last 30 days and 14% had done so more than 3 times in the last 30 days. Males (20%) and females (23%) first tried alcohol at age 15, and males (18%) and females (23%) had first been drunk at age 15.

Students were asked about the consequences they had experienced while under the influence of alcohol in the last 12 months. The most common consequence of alcohol consumption was damaging or losing property (10.8%). 7.2% of students had sustained an injury or accident, 6.7% had been involved in a serious accident, 5% had been involved in a fight, and a further 4% had been in trouble with the police. Female students (13.8%) were more likely to damage or lose property than were male students (7.2%) and were more likely than males to have an injury or be involved in an accident than males. Females were also more likely than males to be victims of an unwanted sexual advance while under the influence of alcohol. Males were more likely to be involved in a fight, drunk-driving accidents, hospitalized due to intoxication and been in trouble with the police while under the influence of alcohol than females.

Students were asked how difficult they thought it would be to get particular alcoholic drinks. Most students thought it would be 'very easy' to obtain Cider (36.5%), premixed drinks (28.2%), spirits (30.6%) or beer (35.8%) and 29.2% thought it would be 'fairly easy' to obtain wine.

Students were asked how much they thought people risked harming themselves physically or in other ways if they consumed one or two drinks nearly every day, had five drinks nearly every day or had five or more drinks in one occasion nearly every weekend. Almost half of students perceived moderate risk to drinking one or two drinks every day. Over two-thirds (70.6%) of students said that there was a great risk to drinking four to five drinks every day and 45.4% thought that there was a great risk to having five drinks or more nearly every weekend.

When asked about their motivations for drinking, the most popular reason was to make social gatherings more fun and drinking to be liked was the least popular reason reported.

Factors Related to Alcohol Consumption

Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status was measured by the educational level of students' fathers and mothers. Statistically significant associations were found between the father's¹⁶ and mother's¹⁷ education and the student's lifetime alcohol consumption. Results show that students whose father received only primary education were the most likely to have drunk alcohol twenty times or more in their lifetime (26.1%, n=12) and those whose fathers completed third level were the least likely (13.9%, n=120). By contrast, students whose mothers had completed their education at or before the end of primary schooling were less likely to consume alcohol twenty times or more (10%, n=2) than students whose mothers had secondary (23.4%, n=128) or third-level (14.1%, n=156) education (Table 3.17). Significant associations were also found between fathers'¹⁸ and mothers' ¹⁹ education and respondents' alcohol consumption in the last 30 days.

Father's Education										
Lifetime drinking (number of occasions)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	12	26.1	131	19.3	273	31.5	86	36.6	502	27.5
1-2 times	8	17.4	122	17.9	157	18.1	39	16.6	326	17.8
3-9 times	7	15.2	183	26.9	217	25.0	43	18.3	450	24.6
10-19 times	7	15.2	100	14.7	100	11.5	34	14.5	241	13.2
20 times or more	12	26.1	144	21.2	120	13.9	33	14.0	309	17.0
Total	46	100.0	680	100.0	867	100.0	235	100.0	1828	100.0
Mother's Education										
Lifetime drinking (number of occasions)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	9	45.0	96	17.6	329	29.8	69	42.3	503	27.4
1-2 times	2	10.0	110	20.1	192	17.4	21	12.999	325	17.7
3-9 times	5	25.0	134	24.5	286	25.9	29	17.8	454	24.8
10-19 times	2	10.0	79	14.4	141	12.8	19	11.7	241	13.1
20 times or more	2	10.0	128	23.4	156	14.1	25	15.3	311	17.0
Total	20	100.0	547	100.0	1104	100.0	163	100.0	1834	100.0

Table 3.17: Lifetime alcohol consumption by Fathers education

School

Absences

Lifetime and current alcohol consumption were compared with missing school due to various reasons and results are presented in Table 3.18. There were statistically significant associations between lifetime alcohol consumption and missing school due

¹⁶ Fathers education – lifetime drinking: [$X^2(12) = 55.163, p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .100$]

¹⁷ Mothers education-lifetime drinking: [$X^2(12) = 65.576, p < .001$, Cramer's $V = .109$]

¹⁸ Fathers education – 30 day drinking: [$X^2(16) = 69.782, p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .097$]

¹⁹ Mothers education-30 day drinking: [$X^2(16) = 36.934, p = .002$, Cramer's $V = .071$]

to illness²⁰, missing school because of skipping²¹, and missing school for other reasons²². Results shows that 66.7% (n=550) of students who had not missed school due to illness have tried alcohol and out of those who had missed 5 to 6 days of school due to illness, 77.6% (n=142) had tried alcohol in their lifetime. Similarly, of students who had skipped school for 7 or more days, 92% (n=23) had tried alcohol in their lifetime. This number fell to 69% (n=880) for students who had never skipped school. 81.3% (n=65) of students who were absent from school for other reasons had tried alcohol in their lifetime compared to 68.8% (n=594) of students who had not missed school for other reasons.

Lifetime alcohol consumption												
	No days		1 day		2 days		3 to 4 days		5 to 6 days		7 or more days	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Absence due to illness	550	66.7	263	78.0	200	79.1	142	77.6	55	83.3	44	66.7
Skipping school	880	69.0	202	89.4	-	-	43	91.5	17	89.5	23	92.0
Other reason	594	68.8	270	75.0	156	79.2	119	75.3	41	77.4	65	81.3
Current alcohol consumption												
	No days		1 day		2 days		3 to 4 days		5 to 6 days		7 or more days	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Absence due to illness	281	33.7	153	44.6	121	47.3	85	46.5	37	54.4	32	45.7
Skipping school	454	35.2	144	62.6	-	-	31	64.6	12	60.0	23	79.3
Other reason	325	37.0	144	39.8	92	45.8	77	47.8	25	46.3	45	55.6

Table 3.18: Lifetime and current alcohol consumption by reason for missing school

Alcohol consumption in the last 30 days was also significantly associated with missing school due to illness²³, skipping²⁴ and other reasons²⁵. As shown in Table 3.18, of students who had missed 5 to 6 days of school due to illness, about half (54.4%, n=37) had had alcohol in the last 30 days. Of students who had not missed school, a higher percentage (66.3%, n=553) were not current drinkers. 79.3% (n=23) of students who skipped school on 7 or more days were current drinkers compared to 35.2% (n=454) who had not skipped school. Similar results were observed for those who had missed school for other reasons (see Table 3.18).

²⁰ Lifetime alcohol consumption and absence due to illness: [$X^2(5)=32.102$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.136$]

²¹ Lifetime alcohol consumption and skipping school: [$X^2(4)=58.002$, $P<.001$, Cramer's $V=.189$]

²² Lifetime alcohol consumption other reasons: [$X^2(5)=15.742$, $p=.008$, Cramer's $V=.096$]

²³ Current alcohol consumption and absence due to illness: [$X^2(5)=32.253$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.136$]

²⁴ Current alcohol consumption and skipping school: [$X^2(4)=93.943$, $P,.001$, Cramer's $V=.241$]

²⁵ Current alcohol consumption other reasons: [$X^2(5)=18.690$, $p=.002$, Cramer's $V=.104$]

Figure 3.3: Skipped school by alcohol consumption in the last 30 days

Figure 3.4: Missed school for other reasons by alcohol consumption in the last 30 days

School grade

Average grade in school was significantly associated with lifetime alcohol²⁶ (Table 3.19). A lower percentage of students (67.3%, n=569) who reported that their average grades were mostly A and B had tried alcohol in their lifetime compared with students who reported that their average grades were mostly D (77.6%, n=159). More students with E grades or lower were current drinkers (42.9%) than those with A grades (36.8%). However, this association did not reach statistical significance²⁷.

²⁶ Lifetime alcohol consumption and parental monitoring: $X^2(3) = 140.742, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .278$

²⁷ Current alcohol consumption and average grade: $[X^2(3) = 12.237, p = .007, \text{Cramer's } V = .082]$

Average grade	A and B		C		D		E or lower	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have tried alcohol	569	67.3	563	77.1	159	77.6	23	69.7
Current drinkers	312	36.8	310	42.1	103	49.3	15	42.9

Table 3.19: Lifetime and current alcohol consumption by average grade

Figure 3.5 Current alcohol consumption by reported average grade

Parenting

Parental monitoring on Saturday nights

Students were asked if their parents know where they spend Saturday nights. Responses presented in Table 3.20 show that more students (96.2%, n=151) whose parents sometimes know where they are on Saturday nights have tried alcohol²⁸. Similarly, considerably more students whose parents sometimes know where they are on Saturday nights were current drinkers²⁹ (72.1%, n=116). There was a significant association between parental monitoring and alcohol consumption.

Parental Monitoring	Know always		Know quite often		Know sometimes		Usually don't know	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have tried alcohol	741	63.7	383	87.6	151	96.2	53	77.9
Current drinkers	363	30.7	229	52.1	116	72.1	45	63.4

Table 3.20: Lifetime and current alcohol consumption by parental monitoring.

²⁸ Lifetime alcohol consumption and parental monitoring: $X^2(3)= 140.742, p<.001, \text{Cramer's } V=.278]$

²⁹ Current alcohol consumption and parental monitoring: $X^2(3)= 152.806, p<.001, \text{Cramer's } V=.287]$

Figure 3.6: Current drinking by parental monitoring.

Household

Table 3.21 shows the number of students who had tried alcohol and who were current drinkers by household type. 74.7% (n=280) of students in one-parent households had tried alcohol, compared to 66.7% (n=12) in other households and 72.2% (n=1049) in households with two or more parents (including step-parents). Household type was not significantly associated with lifetime or current drinking³⁰.

Alcohol consumption	Two parents or more		One parent		Other	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
30 days	596	40.35	161	42.4	7	36.8
Lifetime	1049	72.2	280	74.7	12	66.7

Table 3.21: Alcohol consumption by household type

Peer substance use

Students were asked how many of their friends use various substances and the response categories were “none”, “a few”, “some”, “most” or “all”. They were asked about smoking cigarettes, drinking alcohol, getting drunk, smoking cannabis, using inhalants, tranquilisers or ecstasy.

Peer alcohol use

Students were asked how many of their friends drink alcoholic beverages (beer, cider, premixed drinks, wine, spirits) and get drunk. There was no statistically significant association between lifetime³¹ alcohol consumption and peer alcohol use although the number who had tried alcohol rose with the number of peers who had taken alcohol. 73.9% (n=112) of students who had tried alcohol in their lifetime reported that all of their friends drink alcohol, closely followed by 73.6% (n=466) who said most, 73.4% (226) who said some and 72.5% (n=358) who said only a few of their friends drink alcohol. Similar results were

³⁰ Lifetime drinking and household type: [χ^2 (2)=1.275, p=.529]; Current drinking and household type: [χ^2 (2)=.629, p=.730]

³¹ Lifetime alcohol consumption and peer alcohol use: [χ^2 (4)=2.979, p=.561, Cramer's V=.041]

observed for current drinkers as 49% (n=77) of students who said that all their friends used alcohol were current drinkers compared to 37.3% who said that none of their friends drank alcohol although these results were not statistically significant³².

Peer alcohol use	None		A few		Some		Most		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have tried alcohol	148	67.8	358	72.5	226	73.4	466	73.6	112	73.9
Current drinkers	81	37.3	192	38.2	135	42.9	264	41.0	77	49.0

Table 3.22: Lifetime and current alcohol consumption by peer alcohol use

Figure 3.7: Current drinking by peer alcohol use

Students were asked how many of their friends get drunk and responses are shown in Table 3.22. There was a significant association between lifetime drinking and peer drunkenness³³. 71.9% (n=82) of students who answered that all their friends get drunk had tried alcohol in their lifetime, and just two-thirds (66.2%, n=215) who said that none of their friends get drunk reported that they had tried alcohol. Similarly, there was a significant association between current alcohol consumption and peer drunkenness³⁴. Half of students (50.4%, n=59) who said that all of their friends get drunk reported that they were current drinkers themselves compared to 33.2% (n=108) who said none of their friends get drunk.

Peer drunkenness	None		A few		Some		Most		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have tried alcohol	215	66.2	372	77.0	303	73.2	337	72.5	82	71.9
Current drinkers	108	33.2	209	42.5	181	42.8	191	40.4	59	50.4

Table 3.23: Lifetime and current alcohol consumption by peer drunkenness

³² Current alcohol consumption and peer alcohol use: [$X^2(4)=7.503, p=.112, \text{Cramer's } V=.064$]

³³ Lifetime alcohol consumption and peer drunkenness: [$X^2(4)=11.648, p=.020, \text{Cramer's } V=.080$]

³⁴ Current alcohol consumption and peer drunkenness: [$X^2(4)=13.489, p=.009, \text{Cramer's } V=.086$]

Figure 3.8: Current drinking by peer drunkenness

Summary

Fathers' and mothers' education levels were positively associated with students' lifetime alcohol consumption. 73% of students whose fathers had completed primary school or less had tried alcohol compared to 68.5% of students whose fathers had completed third-level education. By contrast, students whose mothers had completed their education at or before the end of primary schooling were less likely to consume alcohol twenty times or more (10%) than students whose mothers had secondary (23.4%) or third-level (14.1%) education. Skipping school and absence from school due to illness and other reasons were significantly associated with lifetime and current alcohol consumption. 66.7% of students who had not missed school due to illness had tried alcohol with this number rising to 77.6% of students who had missed 5 to 6 days of school due to illness. Similarly, of students who had skipped school for 7 or more days, 92% had tried alcohol in their lifetime. This number fell to 69% for students who had never skipped school. 81.3% of students who were absent from school for other reasons had tried alcohol in their lifetime compared to 68.8% of students who had not missed school for other reasons. Among students who had missed 5 to 6 days of school due to illness, about half had had alcohol in the last 30 days. Of students who had not missed school, a higher percentage (66.3%) were not current drinkers. 79.3% of students who skipped school on 7 or more days were current drinkers.

Average grade in school was significantly associated with lifetime alcohol use. A lower percentage of students with A and B (67.3%) had tried alcohol in their lifetime compared to students who had E or lower (69.7%). However, D students had the highest rate of lifetime alcohol consumption at 77.6%.

There was a significant association between parental monitoring of Saturday nights and alcohol consumption. Noticeably more students (96.2%) whose parents know sometimes where they are on Saturday nights have tried alcohol than those whose parents always know (63.7%). Similarly, 72% of students whose parents sometimes know where they are and 63.4% of students whose parents usually don't know where they are on Saturday nights were current drinkers compared to 30.7% whose parents always know where they are on Saturday nights.

There was a significant association between lifetime and current drinking and peer drunkenness. 71.9% of students who answered that all their friends get drunk had tried alcohol in their lifetime, and 66.2% who said that none of their friends get drunk reported that they had tried alcohol. Similarly, half of students (50.4%) who said that all of their friends get drunk

reported that they were current drinkers themselves compared to 33.2% who said none of their friends get drunk.

SMOKING

ESPAD
The European School Survey Project
On Alcohol and Other Drugs

32% of students had ever smoked

14% of students smoked in the last 30 days

5% of students smoked daily

63%
first smoked aged 14-15

28%
began smoking daily aged 14-15

Male students started smoking at an earlier age than female students (**14.4 years vs 15 years**)

61%
of students perceived easy to access cigarettes

70% perceived a great risk in smoking a pack or more a day

34%
of students perceived moderate risk from smoking occasionally

LOWER PARENTAL EDUCATION

PERCEIVED RELATIVE WEALTH

SKIPPING SCHOOL

LOWER SCHOOL GRADE

LOW PARENTAL MONITORING

Smoking was associated with:

POOR RELATIONSHIP WITH PARENTS

PEER SMOKING, ALCOHOL, CANNABIS USE AND OTHER SUBSTANCES

LOW FAMILY SOCIAL SUPPORT

PARENTAL RULE SETTING

E-CIGARETTES

39% had ever used an e-cigarette
Higher than smoking tobacco (**32%**)

Used an e-cigarette in the past 30 days

Higher than smoking (14%)

Similar to smoking (63% first used aged 14-15)

46% vs 33%
More male students than female students had **ever used** e-cigarettes $p < .001$

20% vs 12%
In the last 30 days, more male than female students had **ever used** e-cigarettes $p < .001$

REASONS FOR TRYING E-CIGARETTES

Tobacco use when first used an e-cigarette

4. SMOKING AND TOBACCO PRODUCTS CONSUMPTION

ESPAD 2019 included a number of items on tobacco smoking over the respondents' lifetimes and during the previous month, perceived ease of obtaining cigarettes, perceived risk of smoking, and age of initiation. A wealth of demographic and social information was also collected, allowing a basic investigation of some factors associated with smoking behaviour. Socioeconomic status, school attendance and attainment, relationship with parents and parenting style, and peer substance use were examined to see if they were related to smoking in this cohort. Lastly, students' use of e-cigarettes (Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems, ENDS) was described, along with the reasons reported for using e-cigarettes and their tobacco smoking habits at the time of the survey and when they first tried e-cigarettes.

Smoking

Lifetime smoking

Students were asked on how many occasions they had smoked cigarettes (excluding e-cigarettes) in their lifetime. Responses are presented in Table 4.1. Results show that more than two-thirds of students (68.4%, n=1328) reported that they had never smoked a cigarette in their lifetime, while 31.6% (n=614) of students had ever smoked in their lifetime. 11% (n=213) had only smoked cigarettes once or twice in their lifetime. 7.2% (n=139) of students reported that they had smoked more than 40 times in their lifetimes. There was a statistically significant difference in lifetime smoking by gender³⁵. More male students (33.3%, n=313) than female students (30.1%, n=301) had smoked cigarettes in their lifetimes and more male students than female students had smoked 40 or more cigarettes.

Occasions Smoked	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	628	66.7	700	69.9	1328	68.4
Ever smoked	313	33.3	301	30.1	614	31.6
<i>1-2 times</i>	104	11.1	109	10.9	213	11.0
<i>3-5 times</i>	42	4.5	54	5.4	96	4.9
<i>6-9 times</i>	30	3.2	26	2.6	56	2.9
<i>10-19 times</i>	23	2.4	37	3.7	60	3.1
<i>20-39 times</i>	27	2.9	23	2.3	50	2.6
<i>Over 40</i>	87	9.2	52	5.2	139	7.2
Total	941	100.0	1001	100.0	1942	100.0

Table 4.1: Lifetime cigarette smoking by gender

Smoking during the last 30 days

Students were asked about their cigarette smoking (excluding e-cigarettes) during the last 30 days (Table 4.2). 85.6% (n=1664) reported that they had not smoked cigarettes in the last 30 days compared to 14.4% (n=281) who responded that they had. 7.2% (n=141) reported that they had smoked less than one cigarette per week and 5.3% (n=103) reported smoking

³⁵ Lifetime smoking by gender: [$\chi^2(6)=16.368, p=.012, \text{Cramer's } V=.092$]

daily. There were significant differences in current smoking between male and female students ³⁶as more male students reported smoking in the last 30 days (16.2%, n=153) than did female students (12.8%, n=128).

30-day smoking	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	791	83.8	873	87.2	1664	85.6
Smoked in last 30 days	153	16.2	128	12.8	281	14.4
<i>Less than 1 cigarette per week</i>	71	7.5	70	7.0	141	7.2
<i>Less than 1 cigarette per day</i>	19	2.0	18	1.8	37	1.9
<i>Daily</i>	63	6.7	40	4.0	103	5.3
<i>1-5 cigarette per day</i>	34	3.6	29	2.9	63	3.2
<i>6-10 cigarette per day</i>	9	1.0	7	0.7	16	0.8
<i>11-20 cigarette per day</i>	12	1.3	1	0.1	13	0.7
<i>More than 20 cigarettes per day</i>	8	0.8	3	0.3	11	0.6
Total	944	100.0	1001	100.0	1945	100.0

Table 4.2: Smoking during the last 30 days

Age of Initiation

The age of first cigarette smoking has been linked with an increased likelihood of future daily and heavy smoking, and likelihood of quitting (Bonnie, Stratton and Kwan, 2015) . Therefore, knowing the age that adolescents smoke their first cigarette and begin to smoke on a daily basis can inform targeted prevention efforts. When students were asked at what age did they smoke their first cigarette, of those who had smoked a cigarette, 35.8% (n=227) were 15 years old, followed by those who responded that they were 14 years (27.4%, n=174) when they smoked their first cigarette (Table 4.3). Male students tended to smoke their first cigarettes at a younger age (mean=14.4 years, SD= 1.82) than female students (mean=15 years, SD= 1.42)³⁷.

Figure 4.1: Age of students when they first smoked a cigarette by gender

³⁶ Current smoking by gender: [$\chi^2(6)=14.644, p=.023, \text{Cramer's } V=.087$]

³⁷ Age of initiation by gender: [$t(633)=-4.129, p<.001$]

Smoking on a daily basis

Out of students who reported smoking, 36.1% (n=62) of those who reported smoking daily were 15 years old followed by 26.2% (n=45) who were 14 years old at initiation. Additionally, 97 out of the 171 daily smokers were males and 75 were females (Table 4.4, Figure 4.2). The mean age for male students who were daily smokers was 14.7 years (SD=1.91) and 15 years (SD=1.60) for females³⁸.

Age began daily smoking	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
9 years old or less	7	7.2	3	4	10	5.8
10 years old	1	1.0	2	2.7	3	1.7
11 years old	6	6.2	1	1.3	7	4.1
12 years old	6	6.2	3	4.0	9	5.2
13 years old	11	11.3	8	10.7	19	11.1
14 years old	24	24.7	21	28.0	45	26.2
15 years old	30	30.9	32	42.7	62	36.1
16 years old or older	12	12.4	5	6.6	17	9.8
Total	97	100.0	75	100.0	171	100.0

Table 4.4: Age respondent began daily smoking

Figure 4.2: Age of students when they first smoked a cigarette and began smoking daily

Figure 4.2 shows the ages at which students first smoked a cigarette and when they began smoking daily. The most frequent age for age first smoking a cigarette and smoking daily is 15 years.

Perceived access to cigarettes

When students were asked how difficult they thought it would be to access cigarettes, over one-third (38.2%, n=740) responded that it would be 'fairly easy' and another 23.2% (n=449) thought that it would be 'very easy' to obtain a cigarette. Only 5.5% (n=107) responded that it would be impossible.

³⁸ Age of starting to smoke daily by gender: [t(170)=-1.076, p=.283]

Statistically significant differences were observed in perceived access to cigarettes by gender³⁹. More males (27.9%, n=263) than females (18.6%, n=186) believed it would be ‘very easy’ to access cigarettes.

Perceived access to cigarettes	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Impossible	51	5.4	56	5.6	107	5.5
Very difficult	79	8.4	103	10.3	182	9.4
Fairly difficult	118	12.5	143	14.3	261	13.5
Fairly easy	330	35.1	410	41.1	740	38.2
Very easy	263	27.9	186	18.6	449	23.2
Don’t know	100	10.6	100	10.0	200	10.3
Total	941	100.0	998	100.0	1939	100.0

Table 4.5: Perceived access to cigarettes by gender

Perceived risk of cigarette smoking

Students were also asked how much they thought people risked harming themselves if they smoked cigarettes occasionally (Table 4.6), and 12.7% (n=245) believed that there are no risks. Most students believed that there is a moderate risk (34%, n=658) or a slight risk (27.4%, n=531), and 22.7% (n=440) believed that there is a great risk. More male students perceived that there is no risk (15.2%, n=142) from smoking occasionally than did female students (10.3%, n=103), while more female students perceived a slight or moderate risk. The differences in perceived risk of occasional smoking between male and females were statistically significant⁴⁰.

Risk of occasional smoking	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	142	15.2	103	10.3	245	12.7
Slight risk	239	25.5	292	29.2	531	27.4
Moderate risk	309	33.0	349	34.9	658	34.0
Great risk	208	22.2	232	23.2	440	22.7
Don’t know	38	4.1	23	2.3	61	3.2
Total	936	100.0	999	100.0	1935	100.0

Table 4.6: Perceived risk of occasional cigarette smoking by gender

Students were also asked how much they thought people risked harming themselves if they smoked a pack or more of cigarettes a day. A majority of respondents (69%, n=1359) believed that there was a great risk and 15.8% (306) responded ‘moderate risk’. 6% (n=116) believed that there was no risk in smoking a pack or more a day. Statistically significant differences were observed between male and females⁴¹ as more male students (8.6%, n=81) than female students (3.5%, n=35) perceived that there was no risk. More female (73.7%, n=734) than male students (65.7%, n=616) perceived a great risk in smoking a pack or more a day.

³⁹ Perceived access by gender: [$X^2(5) = 25.994, p < .001$; Cramer’s $V = .116$]

⁴⁰ Perceived risk of occasional smoking by gender; [$X^2(4) = 16.894, p = .002$, Cramer’s $V = .093$]

⁴¹ Perceived risk of smoking a pack a day by gender: [$X^2(4) = 32.682, p = .000$, Cramer’s $V = .130$]

Risk of smoking a pack or more a day	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	81	8.6	35	3.5	116	6.0
Slight risk	52	5.5	54	5.4	106	5.5
Moderate risk	152	16.2	154	15.5	306	15.8
Great risk	616	65.7	734	73.7	1359	69.8
Don't know	37	3.9	19	1.9	56	2.9
Total	938	100.0	996	100.0	1934	100.0

Table 4.7: Perceived risk of smoking a pack or more a day by gender

Familial rules on cigarette smoking

Students were asked about the rules and restrictions on cigarette smoking when they were in the family car. The majority of students (76.5%, n=1315) reported that no one is allowed to smoke in the family car. Only 8.9% (n=153) reported that smoking is allowed as long as the window is down, closely followed by 7.2% (n=124) who said that they never drive in cars with people who smoke. There were no significant differences in rules on cigarette smoking in family car by gender⁴² (Table 4.8)

Rules on cigarette smoking in family car	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No one is allowed to smoke	661	78.4	654	74.6	1315	76.5
Smoking is allowed as long as the window is down	68	8.1	85	9.7	153	8.9
There are no rules or restrictions	27	3.2	20	2.3	47	2.7
I never drive in cars with people who smoke	50	5.9	74	8.4	124	7.2
Don't know	37	4.4	44	5.0	81	4.7
Total	843	100.0	877	100.0	1720	100.0

Table 4.8: Rules of cigarette smoking in family car by gender

Students were also asked about rules on cigarette smoking in the house and responses are presented in Table 4.9. Just over half of students (56.4%, n=972) reported that no one is allowed to smoke inside or outside the house. Another 27.3% (n=470) reported that no one is allowed to smoke inside the house but are allowed smoke outside the house. 4.8% (n=82) responded that adults are allowed to smoke in the room and 2.2% (n=39) said there are no restrictions on smoking in their house. Again, there were no significant differences in rules on cigarette smoking in respondents' houses by gender⁴³.

⁴² Rules and restriction on cigarette smoking in family car by gender: [$X^2(4) = 7.549, p = .110$. Cramer's $V = .066$

⁴³ Rules and restriction on cigarette smoking in family the house by gender: [$X^2(5) = 8.421, p = .135$. Cramer's $V = .069$

Rules on cigarette smoking in the house	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No one is allowed to smoke inside or outside the house	489	57.7	483	55.1	972	56.4
No one is allowed to smoke inside, but outside is OK	238	28.1	232	26.5	470	27.3
Adults are allowed to smoke anywhere in the house	27	3.2	27	3.1	54	3.1
Adults are allowed to smoke in some rooms	34	4.0	48	5.5	82	4.8
There are no rules or restrictions on smoking	13	1.5	26	2.9	39	2.2
Something else	46	5.5	61	6.9	107	6.2
Total	847	100.0	877	100.0	1724	100.0

Table 4.9: Rules of cigarette smoking in the house by gender

Students were also asked about their willingness to quit and to set a quit date. Only 6.7% (n=15) of students who were current smokers expressed a willingness to quit and 8.2% (n=16) expressed a willingness to set a quit date.

Willingness to quit	Yes		No		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Willingness to quit in the next month	15	6.7	209	93.3	224	100.0
Willingness to set a quit date	16	8.2	180	91.8	196	100.0

Table 4.10: Willingness to quit and set a quit date

Summary

Overall, 31.6% reported that they had ever smoked and 14.4% had smoked at least once in the last 30 days. More male students (16.2%) than female students (12.8%) reported smoking in the last 30 days. Of those who had ever smoked a cigarette, 35.8% were 15 years old when they first smoked. Male students reported smoking their first cigarettes at a younger age than female students (14.4 years compared to 15 years). 61% of students perceived it would be easy to obtain a cigarette. Only 5.5% responded that it would be impossible. Students were also asked how much they thought people risked harming themselves if they smoked cigarettes occasionally and if they smoked a pack or more cigarettes a day. Most students believed that there is a moderate risk (34%) or a slight risk (27.4%) of smoking occasionally, 70% believed that there was a great risk and 6% answered that they perceived no risk from smoking one or more packs of cigarettes per day.

Factors related to smoking

Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status was measured by the educational level of students' parents and perceived wealth of student's family compared to peers (Table 4.11, Figure 4.3). Both a father's and mother's education were significantly associated with a student's lifetime smoking⁴⁴. About 72% (n=646) of students whose fathers received a third-level education had never smoked compared with 57.5% (n=27) of students whose fathers received only primary education or less. Having more educated fathers seemed to be a protective factor (p<.001) as only 4.9% (n=44) of students whose fathers had third-level education smoked more than 40 cigarettes in their lifetimes. Maternal education was also significantly associated with lifetime smoking⁴⁵. Of students whose mothers had third-level education, 71.8% (n=816) had never smoked cigarettes compared to 5.5% (n=62) who had ever smoked over 40 cigarettes.

Father's Education										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	27	57.5	457	65.1	646	72.1	139	66.5	1269	68.5
1-2	2	4.3	81	11.5	103	11.5	20	9.6	206	11.1
3-39	11	23.4	99	14.1	103	11.5	36	17.2	249	13.4
40+	7	14.8	65	9.3	44	4.9	14	6.7	130	7.0
Total	47	100.0	702	100.0	896	100.0	209	100.0	1854	100.0
Mother's Education										
Lifetime Smoking (number of occasions)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	12	60.0	351	61.9	816	71.8	104	69.8	1283	68.5
1-2	1	5.0	68	11.9	127	11.2	12	8.1	208	11.1
3-39	3	15.0	90	15.9	131	11.5	25	16.8	249	13.3
40+	4	20.0	58	10.2	62	5.5	8	5.3	132	7.1
Total	20	100.0	567	100.0	1136	100.0	149	100.0	1872	100.0

Table 4.11: Lifetime smoking by father's and mother's education

⁴⁴ Lifetime smoking by father's education: [χ^2 (9)= 26.857, p<.001, Cramer's V=.073]

⁴⁵ Lifetime smoking by mother's education: [χ^2 (9)= 30.899, p<.001, Cramer's V=.076]

Figure 4.3: Stacked bar chart of lifetime smoking by Father's education level

Fathers'⁴⁶ and mothers'⁴⁷ education was also significantly associated with current smoking and having more educated parents seemed to be a protective factor against smoking (Table 4.12). Respondents whose fathers had primary education only were more likely to report smoking everyday (14.9%, n=7) compared to respondents whose fathers had third-level education (2.8%, n=26). Similar rates were observed for maternal smoking.

Father's Education										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	33	70.2	578	82.4	800	89.1	180	85.3	1618	85.7
Less than one per week	3	6.4	63	9.0	56	6.3	15	7.1	138	7.3
Less than one a day	4	8.5	14	2.0	16	1.8	2	1.0	36	1.9
Every day	7	14.9	46	6.6	26	2.8	14	6.6	95	5.0
Total	47	100.0	701	100.0	896	100.0	244	100.0	1857	100.0

Mother's Education										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	N	%	N	%	N
None	12	60.0	458	80.6	1014	89.0	123	82.5	1607	85.7
Less than one per week	1	5.0	59	10.4	62	5.4	16	10.7	138	7.3
Less than one a day	3	15.0	11	2.0	20	1.8	1	0.6	36	1.9
Every day	4	20.0	40	7.0	43	3.8	9	6.0	96	5.1
Total	20	100.0	568	100.0	1139	100.0	149	100.0	1876	100.0

Table 4.12: Current smoking by father's and mother's education

⁴⁶ Current smoking by father's education: [$X^2(9)=40.852, p<.001; \text{Cramer's } V=.086]$

⁴⁷ Current smoking by mother's education: [$X^2(9)= 59.222, p<.001; \text{Cramer's } V=.102]$

Self-reported relative wealth of the family was significantly associated with lifetime⁴⁸ and current⁴⁹ smoking (Table 4.13, Figure 4.4). Respondents who perceived their family to be ‘very much less well off’ (25%, n=8) and ‘less well off’ (16.4%, n=24) were most likely to have ever smoked 40 cigarettes or more in their lifetime. Those who perceived their family to be ‘better off’ (73.75%, n=427) were the most likely to abstain from cigarettes. Similarly, respondents who perceived their family to be ‘very much less well off’ were more likely to smoke cigarettes every day (29.1%, n=8) compared to those who were ‘better off’ (3.55%, n=20) and ‘about the same’ (3.8%, n=31). However, respondents who perceived their family to be ‘better off’ were the least likely to be current smokers (89.1%, n=517).

Perceived relative wealth														
Lifetime smoking*(number of occasions)	Very much better off		Much better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		(Very) much less well off		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	49	51.6	146	69.2	427	73.7	568	69.9	79	54.1	17	52.1	1286	68.6
1-2	17	17.9	22	10.4	49	8.5	99	12.1	20	13.7	2	8.4	209	11.1
3-39	16	16.8	36	17.1	75	13.0	94	11.6	23	15.8	5	14.5	249	13.3
40+	13	13.7	7	3.3	28	4.8	52	6.4	24	16.4	8	25.0	132	7.0
Total	95	100.0	211	100.0	579	100.0	813	100.0	146	100.0	32	100.0	1876	100.0

Perceived relative wealth														
Current Smoking (number of cigarettes)	Very much better off		Much better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		Very much less well off		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	72	75.8	183	86.3	517	89.1	713	87.6	105	71.9	22	66.7	1612	85.79
Less than one a week	10	10.5	13	6.1	37	6.4	57	7.0	17	11.6	1	2.1	135	7.2
Less than 1 a day	3	3.2	10	4.7	6	1.0	13	1.6	3	2.1	1	2.1	36	1.9
Every day	10	10.5	6	2.9	20	3.5	31	3.8	21	14.4	8	29.1	96	5.1
Total	95	100.0	212	100.0	580	100.0	814	100.0	146	100.0	24	100.0	1879	100.0

Table 4.13: Lifetime and current smoking by perceived wealth

Figure 4.4: Stacked bar chart of current smoking by relative perceived wealth

⁴⁸ Lifetime smoking by perceived relative wealth: [$\chi^2 (18) = 76.285, p < .001; \text{Cramer's } V = .116$]

⁴⁹ Current smoking by perceived relative wealth: [$\chi^2 (18) = 92.966, p < .001; \text{Cramer's } V = .128$]

In summary, socioeconomic status measured by the self-reported relative wealth of the family and the parental education was associated with current and lifetime smoking, and associations were statistically significant.

School

Previous studies have suggested that smoking is associated with disengagement from school (Minkkinen *et al.*, 2019; Taylor *et al.*, 2015). Skipping class, missing school due to illness, missing classes for other reasons and reporting lower average academic grades were all found to be strongly associated with lifetime and current smoking in this cohort.

Absences

Students were asked how many days they had missed one or more lessons during the last 30 days because they had skipped or ‘cut’ school. Of the students who reported that they had skipped school on 7 or more days, 40% (n=12) had smoked 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetime and 34.5% (n=10) smoked every day. Of students who had not skipped school in the last 30 days, 73.6% (n=962) had never smoked a cigarette in their lifetime and 89.5% (n=1171) were not current smokers. Overall there was a significant relationship between skipping school and lifetime⁵⁰ and current⁵¹ cigarette smoking (Table 4.14).

Skipping School										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	962	73.6	110	47.2	27	39.1	10	33.3	1109	67.7
1-2	133	10.2	37	15.9	11	15.9	2	6.7	183	11.2
3-39	154	11.8	51	21.9	15	21.7	6	20.0	226	13.8
40+	57	4.4	35	15.0	16	23.3	12	40.0	120	7.3
Total	1306	100.0	233	100.0	69	100.0	30	100.0	1638	100.0
Skipping School										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1171	89.5	163	70.0	45	65.2	15	51.7	1394	85.1
Less than one per week	81	6.2	29	12.4	8	11.6	2	6.9	120	7.3
Less than one a day	18	1.4	11	4.7	2	2.9	2	6.9	33	2.0
Every day	38	2.9	30	12.9	14	20.3	10	34.5	92	5.6
Total	1308	100.0	233	100.0	69	100.0	29	100.0	1639	100.0

Table 4.14: Lifetime and current smoking by skipping school

⁵⁰ Lifetime smoking by skipping school: [χ^2 (9)= 16.903, p<.001, Cramer’s V=.182]

⁵¹ Current smoking by Skipping school: [χ^2 (9)= 152.006, p<.001, Cramer’s V=.176]

Figure 4.5: Stacked bar chart of lifetime smoking by skipping school

Missing school due to illness was also significantly associated with lifetime⁵² and current⁵³ smoking. Results presented in Table 4.15 and Figure 4.6 show that 18.6% (n=13) of students who had missed school for 7 or more days due to illness smoked over 40 cigarettes in their lifetime and 14.3% (n=10) smoked every day. 89.3% (n=750) of students who had not missed any school due to illness in the last 30 days had abstained from smoking during the same period, as well as over their lifetimes (74.6%, n=627).

Absences due to illness										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	627	74.6	400	65.2	164	63.6	33	47.1	1224	68.7
1-2	75	8.9	77	12.6	30	11.6	13	18.6	195	11.0
3-39	101	12.0	85	13.9	39	15.1	11	15.7	236	13.2
40+	37	4.4	51	8.3	25	9.7	13	18.6	126	7.1
Total	840	100.0	612	100.0	258	100.0	70	100.0	1781	100.0
Absences due to illness										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	750	89.3	515	83.9	210	81.4	50	71.4	1525	85.6
Less than one per week	51	6.1	52	8.5	19	7.4	7	10.0	129	7.2
Less than one a day	12	1.4	15	2.4	5	1.9	3	4.3	35	2.0
Every day	27	3.2	32	5.2	24	9.3	10	14.3	93	5.2
Total	840	100.0	614	100.0	258	100.0	70	100.0	1782	100.0

Table 4.15: Lifetime and current smoking by absence due to illness

⁵² Lifetime smoking by absence due to illness: [χ^2 (9)= 47.017, p<.001, Cramer's V=.094]

⁵³ Current smoking by absence due to illness: [χ^2 (9)= 36.933, p<.001, Cramer's V=.083]

Figure 4.6: Stacked bar chart of lifetime smoking by absences due to illness

Similar results were also observed for students who were absent from school in the last 30 days due to other reasons. Missing school due to other reasons was significantly associated with current smoking⁵⁴ but not lifetime smoking⁵⁵.

Absences due to other reasons										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	604	68.3	402	69.6	146	66.7	55	67.9	1207	68.5
1-2	99	11.2	61	10.6	23	10.5	10	12.4	193	11.0
3-39	130	14.7	73	12.6	26	11.9	10	12.3	239	13.5
40+	51	5.8	42	7.2	24	10.9	6	7.4	123	6.9
Total	884	100.0	578	100.0	219	100.0	81	100.0	1762	100.0
Absences due to other reasons										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		1-2 days		3-6 days		7 or more days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	770	87.0	495	85.9	185	84.5	64	78.1	1514	85.9
Less than one per week	58	6.5	53	9.2	14	6.4	4	4.9	129	7.3
Less than one a day	15	1.7	9	1.6	3	1.4	2	2.4	29	1.7
Every day	42	4.8	19	3.3	17	7.7	12	14.6	90	5.1
Total	885	100.0	576	100.0	219	100.0	82	100.0	1762	100.0

Table 4.16: Lifetime and current smoking by absence due to other reasons

⁵⁴ Current smoking by absence due to other reasons: [χ^2 (9)= 27.147, p=.001]

⁵⁵ Lifetime smoking by absence due to other reasons: [χ^2 (9)= 9.211, p=.418, Cramer's V=.0417].

Average Grade

Students' average grade was significantly associated with lifetime⁵⁶ and current⁵⁷ smoking. 75.4% (n=645) of students who reported that their average grades were mostly A and B had never smoked in their lifetimes or in the past 30 days (91.6%, n=784). Equally, only about 3.3% (n=28) of students who scored mostly A and B had ever smoked more than 40 cigarettes and smoked everyday (1.9%, n=16). Conversely, those who reported lower average grades smoked more both in their lifetimes and everyday as shown in Table 4.17 and Figure 4.7.

Average Grade										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	A and B (70 - 100%)		Mostly C (51- 69%)		Mostly D (40 to 50%)		E or lower (39% or less)		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	645	75.4	491	65.2	126	59.2	18	48.7	1280	68.9
1-2	81	9.5	102	13.5	19	8.9	4	10.8	205	11.0
3-39	101	11.8	96	12.7	44	20.7	4	10.8	245	13.2
40+	28	3.3	64	8.5	24	11.3	11	29.7	127	6.8
Total	855	100.0	753	100.0	213	100.0	37	100.0	1857	100.0
Average Grade										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	A and B (70 - 100%)		Mostly C (51- 69%)		Mostly D (40 to 50%)		E or lower (39% or less)		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	784	91.6	629	83.5	165	77.1	20	55.6	1598	86.0
Less than one per week	43	5.0	66	8.8	19	8.9	5	13.9	133	7.2
Less than one a day	13	1.5	15	2.0	6	2.8	1	2.8	35	1.9
Every day	16	1.9	43	5.7	24	11.2	10	27.8	93	5.0
Total	856	100.0	753	100.0	214	100.0	36	100.0	1859	100.0

Table 4.17: Lifetime and current smoking by average school grade

⁵⁶ Lifetime smoking by average grade: [χ^2 (9)= 83.977, $p < .001$,]

⁵⁷ Current smoking by average grade: [χ^2 (9)=93.989, $p < .001$]

Figure 4.7: Current smoking by average school grade

Relationship with Parents and Home environment

Students were asked a number of questions about their relationship with their parents and the parenting style used in their families. These questions included 5 items on parental regulation⁵⁸, namely rule-setting and monitoring, and 4 items on family social support (Bjarnason, 1994), involving both emotional and financial support, as well as how satisfied the student is with their relationship to each parent.

Rule-setting

Students were asked if their parents set definite rules about what students could do inside and outside the home. Rule setting outside the home was significantly associated with lifetime⁵⁹ and current⁶⁰ smoking (Table 4.18). 70.7% (n=324) of students whose parents almost always set rules for outside the home had never smoked and had not smoked at all in the last 30 days (86.2%, n=395). Compared with students whose parents almost always set rules outside the home for them, students whose parents almost never set rules were more likely to have smoked 40 cigarettes or more in their lifetime (11.2%, n=23), and were more likely to smoke every day (8.8%, n=18).

⁵⁸ 4 items adapted from Thorlindsson & Thoroddur (1999) and an additional item from Finnish Juvenile Health Habit Study from 1977 (Ahlström, S., 1977).

⁵⁹ Lifetime smoking by rule setting outside home: [χ^2 (12)= 32.913, $p < .001$; Cramer's $V = .116$]

⁶⁰ Current smoking by rule setting outside home: [χ^2 (18)= 92.966, $p < .001$; Cramer's $V = .128$]

Rule-setting outside the home												
Lifetime smoking*(number of occasions)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	324	70.7	371	71.8	329	72.9	159	63.3	120	58.5	1303	69.0
1-2	52	11.4	50	9.7	55	12.0	26	10.4	26	12.7	209	11.1
3-39	51	11.1	74	14.3	45	9.8	42	16.7	36	17.6	248	13.1
40+	31	6.8	22	4.3	28	6.1	24	9.6	23	11.2	128	6.8
Total	458	100.0	517	100.0	457	100.0	251	100.0	205	100.0	1888	100.0
Rule-setting outside the home												
Current Smoking (number of cigarettes)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	N	%	N	%	N
Not at all	395	86.2	461	89.2	405	88.4	202	80.2	166	81.0	1629	86.2
Less than one a week	29	6.3	34	6.6	30	6.6	23	9.1	19	9.3	135	7.1
Less than 1 a day	12	2.6	7	1.4	4	0.9	9	3.6	2	1.0	34	1.8
Every day	22	4.8	15	2.9	19	4.1	18	7.1	18	8.8	92	4.9
Total	458	100.0	517	100.0	458	100.0	252	100.0	205	100.0	1890	100.0

Table 4.18: Lifetime and current smoking by rule setting outside home

Parental Monitoring

Students were asked if their parents know where they are and who they spend time with in the evenings. A higher proportion of students whose parents almost always know where they are had never smoked cigarettes in their lifetimes (76.95%, n=893) and were not current smokers (90.6%, n=1055). Students whose parents seldomly know where they are were more likely to have smoked more than 40 cigarettes in their lifetimes (16.5%, n=13) and to smoke every day (12.7%, n=10). There was a significant association between parental monitoring of where students are and lifetime⁶¹ and current⁶² smoking (Table 4.19).

⁶¹ Lifetime smoking by parental monitoring of where students are: [χ^2 (12)= 140.252, $p < .001$,]

⁶² Current smoking by parental monitoring of where students are: [χ^2 (12)= 90.420, $p < .001$]

Parental monitoring of where students are												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	893	76.9	237	62.6	91	48.4	34	43.0	41	55.4	1296	68.9
1-2	105	9.0	56	14.8	24	12.8	16	20.3	7	9.5	208	11.1
3-39	123	10.6	53	14.0	46	24.5	16	20.3	12	16.2	250	13.3
40+	41	2.5	33	8.7	27	14.4	13	16.5	14	18.9	128	6.8
Total	1162	100.0	379	100.0	188	100.0	79	100.0	74	100.0	1882	100.0

Parental monitoring of where students are												
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1055	90.6	317	83.6	145	76.7	52	65.8	52	71.2	1621	86.0
Less than one per week	62	5.3	33	8.7	20	10.6	11	13.9	10	13.7	136	7.2
Less than one a day	15	1.3	5	1.3	7	3.7	6	7.6	1	1.4	34	1.8
Every day	32	2.7	24	6.3	17	9.0	10	12.7	10	13.7	93	4.9
Total	1164	100.0	379	100.0	189	100.0	79	100.0	73	100.0	1884	100.0

Table 4.19: Lifetime and current smoking by parental monitoring of where students are in the evenings

A similar pattern was observed for students whose parents almost never know who they are with (Table 4.20). These students were more likely to have smoked 40 or more cigarette in their lifetimes (18.5%, n=17), and to smoke every day (15.4%, n=14). Again, parental monitoring of who students are with in the evening was found to be significantly associated with lifetime and current smoking⁶³, with students whose parents seldom or almost never know who they are with in the evening being most likely to experiment with cigarettes, and those whose parents almost always know where they are being most protected from lifetime and current smoking.

⁶³ Lifetime smoking by parental monitoring of who students are with: [χ^2 (12)= 117.14, p<.001,]. Current smoking by parental monitoring of who students are with: [χ^2 (12)= 70.109, p<.001]

Parental monitoring of who students were with												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	812	75.9	282	67.6	106	51.7	54	54.0	47	51.1	1301	69.1
1-2	102	9.5	60	14.4	21	10.2	12	12.0	13	14.1	208	11.0
3-39	114	10.7	49	11.8	52	25.4	18	18.0	15	16.3	248	13.2
40+	42	3.9	26	6.2	26	12.7	16	16.0	17	18.5	127	6.7
Total	1070	100.0	417	100.0	205	100.0	100	100.0	92	100.0	1884	100.0
Parental monitoring of who students were with												
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	967	90.3	357	85.6	164	79.6	71	71.0	67	73.6	1626	86.3
Less than one per week	57	5.3	36	8.6	19	9.2	14	14.0	8	8.8	134	7.1
Less than one a day	15	1.4	7	1.7	7	3.4	3	3.0	2	2.2	34	1.8
Every day	32	3.0	17	4.1	16	7.8	12	12.0	14	15.4	91	4.8
Total	1071	100.0	417	100.0	206	100.0	100	100.0	91	100.0	1885	100.0

Table 4.20: Lifetime and current smoking by parental monitoring of who students are with in the evenings

Students were asked if their parents know where they spend Saturday nights ('know always', 'know quite often', 'know sometimes', 'usually don't know'). Again, decreased parental monitoring of Saturday nights was associated with increased smoking. As seen in Table 4.21 and Figure 4.8, students whose parents did not know where they were on Saturday nights were more likely to have smoked 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetimes (29.7%, n=22) than students whose parents always know where they are on Saturday nights (4.2%, n=50). A similar pattern was observed for current smoking and these associations were statistically significant⁶⁴.

⁶⁴ Lifetime smoking by parental monitoring of where students spend Saturday nights: [χ^2 (9)= 201.966, p<.001,]. Current smoking by parental monitoring of where students spend Saturday nights: [χ^2 (9)= 156.886, p<.001]

Parental monitoring of Saturday nights										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Know Always		Quite Often		Sometimes		Usually Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	925	77.5	274	60.5	68	41.0	29	39.2	1296	68.7
1-2	108	9.1	69	15.2	22	13.3	9	12.2	208	11.0
3-39	110	9.2	78	17.2	48	28.9	14	18.9	250	13.3
40+	50	4.2	32	7.1	28	16.9	22	29.7	132	7.0
Total	1193	100.0	453	100.0	166	100.0	74	100.0	1886	100.0

Parental monitoring of Saturday nights										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Always		Quite Often		Sometimes		Usually Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1093	91.5	380	83.7	104	62.7	43	58.9	1620	85.9
Less than one per week	51	4.3	42	9.3	31	18.7	12	16.4	136	7.2
Less than one a day	14	1.2	9	2.0	8	4.8	4	5.5	35	1.9
Every day	36	3.0	23	5.1	23	13.9	14	19.2	96	5.1
Total	1194	100.0	454	100.0	166	100.0	73	100.0	1887	100.0

Table 4.21: Lifetime and current smoking by parental monitoring of where students spend their Saturday nights

Figure 4.8: Stacked bar chart of lifetime smoking by parental monitoring on Saturday night

Family Social Support

Help-seeking from informal sources and social support may have potential benefits in reducing the likelihood of poor psychosocial outcomes among adolescents (Heerde and Hemphill, 2018). Regarding family social support (Bjarnason,

1994), students were asked about how easily they could borrow money and get money as a gift from their mother and/or father. Around 3% of respondents did not answer these questions.

Parental Support: lend or give money

Students were asked if they can easily borrow money or get money as a gift from their mother and/or father. Results are presented in Table 4.22 and 4.23. There was a weak relationship between ability to borrow money from parents and lifetime smoking⁶⁵. However, parental support through lending money was not significantly associated with current smoking⁶⁶.

The majority of students who reported being able to almost always borrow from their parents had never smoked cigarettes in their lifetimes (70.5%, n=425). Of those who almost never borrow money from a parent, 14.1% (n=13) had smoked 40 times or more in their lifetime.

The ability to receive money as a gift from one or both parents was also not significantly associated with lifetime and current smoking⁶⁷.

Parental Support: Lend money												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	425	70.5	363	69.3	335	71.4	123	64.4	52	56.5	1298	69.1
1-2	60	10.0	60	11.5	42	9.0	30	15.7	14	15.2	206	11.0
3-39	77	12.8	71	13.5	69	14.7	19	9.9	13	14.1	249	13.3
40+	41	6.8	30	5.7	23	4.9	19	9.9	13	14.1	126	6.7
Total	603	100.0	524	100.0	469	100.0	191	100.0	92	100.0	1879	100.0

Parental Support: Lend money												
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	521	86.1	461	88.0	400	85.7	165	86.4	73	78.5	1620	86.2
Less than one per week	50	8.3	30	5.7	38	8.1	12	6.3	5	5.4	135	7.2
Less than one a day	6	1.0	9	1.7	10	2.1	4	2.1	5	5.4	34	1.8
Every day	28	4.6	24	4.6	19	4.1	10	5.2	10	10.8	91	4.8
Total	605	100.0	524	100.0	467	100.0	191	100.0	93	100.0	1880	100.0

Table 4.22: Lifetime and current smoking by whether students can lend money from a parent

⁶⁵ Lifetime smoking by ability to lend money: [χ^2 (12)= 27.206, p=.007].

⁶⁶ Current smoking by ability to lend money [χ^2 (12)= 21.273, p=.047]

⁶⁷ Lifetime smoking by ability to get money as a gift: [χ^2 (12)= 16.153, p=.184]. Current smoking by ability to get money as a gift [χ^2 (12)= 14.302, p=.282]

Parental Support: Give money												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	357	68.1	343	71.2	341	72.2	191	67.5	70	56.0	1302	69.0
1-2	54	10.3	48	10.0	51	10.8	33	11.7	22	17.6	208	11.0
3-39	74	14.1	62	12.9	54	11.4	38	13.4	22	17.6	208	11.0
40+	39	7.4	29	6.0	26	5.5	21	7.4	11	8.8	126	6.7
Total	524	100.0	482	100.0	472	100.0	283	100.0	125	100.0	1886	100.0
Parental Support: Give money												
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	Almost always		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Almost Never		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	448	85.2	421	87.0	419	89.0	241	85.2	99	79.8	1628	86.2
Less than one per week	39	7.4	33	6.8	32	6.8	20	7.1	12	9.7	136	7.2
Less than one a day	9	1.7	11	2.3	7	1.5	5	1.8	2	1.6	34	1.8
Every day	30	5.7	19	3.9	13	2.8	17	6.0	11	8.9	90	4.8
Total	526	100.0	484	100.0	471	100.0	283	100.0	124	100.0	1888	100.0

Table 4.23: Lifetime and current smoking by whether students can get money as a gift from parent

Satisfaction with relationship with parents

Students were asked to report their level of satisfaction regarding their relationships with their fathers and mothers, with responses ranging through ‘very satisfied’, ‘satisfied’, ‘neither nor’, ‘not so satisfied’, ‘not at all satisfied’ and ‘there is no such person’. No significant relationship was observed between satisfaction with relationship with mother and either lifetime or current smoking⁶⁸. However, generally students who seemed very satisfied with their relationship with their mother were likely to smoke fewer cigarettes than students who were ‘not so satisfied’ or ‘not at all satisfied’.

No significant relationship was observed for satisfaction with relationship with father and lifetime or current smoking⁶⁹.

⁶⁸ Lifetime smoking by satisfaction with relationship with mother: [$X^2(15) = 18.526, p = .236$]. Current smoking by satisfaction with relationship with mother [$X^2(15) = 11.081, p = .747$]

⁶⁹ Lifetime smoking by satisfaction with relationship with father: [$X^2(15) = 16.862, p = .327$]. Current smoking by satisfaction with relationship with father [$X^2(15) = 16.197, p = .369$]

Satisfaction with Relationship with Mother														
Lifetime smoking*(number of occasions)	Very satisfied		Satisfied		Neither nor		Not so satisfied		Not at all satisfied		There is no such person		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	681	70.4	427	66.1	71	66.4	60	67.4	26	65.0	12	60.0	1277	68.3
1-2	100	10.3	80	12.4	9	8.4	12	13.5	8	20.0	0	0.0	209	11.2
3-39	125	12.9	91	14.1	16	15.0	10	11.2	3	7.5	4	20.0	249	13.3
40+	62	6.4	48	7.4	11	10.3	7	7.9	3	7.5	4	20.0	135	7.2
Total	968	100.0	646	100.0	107	100.0	89	100.0	40	100.0	20	100.0	1870	100.0

Satisfaction with Relationship with Mother														
Current Smoking (number of cigarettes)	Very satisfied		Satisfied		Neither nor		Not so satisfied		Not at all satisfied		There is no such person		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	845	87.2	547	84.4	89	83.2	76	85.4	32	80.0	15	75.0	1604	85.6
Less than one a week	63	6.5	53	8.2	7	6.5	5	5.6	5	12.5	2	10.0	135	7.2
Less than 1 a day	13	1.3	13	2.0	4	3.7	2	2.2	1	2.5	1	5.0	34	1.8
Every day	48	5.0	35	5.4	7	6.5	6	6.7	2	5.0	2	10.0	100	5.3
Total	969	100.0	648	100.0	107	100.0	89	100.0	40	100.0	20	100.0	1873	100.0

Table 4.24: Lifetime and current smoking by satisfaction with relationship with mother

Satisfaction with Relationship with Father														
Lifetime smoking*(number of occasions)	Very satisfied		Satisfied		Neither nor		Not so satisfied		Not at all satisfied		There is no such person		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	554	71.4	406	67.7	101	63.9	98	61.3	61	67.8	53	67.1	1273	68.3
1-2	81	10.4	66	11.0	18	11.4	27	16.9	9	10.0	7	8.9	208	11.2
3-39	88	11.3	87	14.5	24	15.2	24	15.0	10	11.1	14	17.7	247	13.3
40+	53	6.8	41	6.8	15	9.5	11	6.9	10	11.1	5	6.3	135	7.2
Total	776	100.0	600	100.0	158	100.0	160	100.0	90	100.0	79	100.0	1863	100.0

Satisfaction with Relationship with Father														
Current Smoking (number of cigarettes)	Very satisfied		Satisfied		Neither nor		Not so satisfied		Not at all satisfied		There is no such person		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	679	87.4	520	86.5	128	81.0	130	81.3	74	82.2	67	83.8	1598	85.6
Less than one a week	47	6.0	43	7.2	15	9.5	18	11.3	6	6.7	6	7.5	135	7.2
Less than 1 a day	14	1.8	10	1.7	3	1.9	2	1.3	1	1.1	3	3.8	33	1.8
Every day	37	4.8	28	4.7	12	7.6	10	6.3	9	10.0	4	5.0	100	5.4
Total	777	100.0	601	100.0	158	100.0	160	100.0	90	100.0	80	100.0	1866	100.0

Table 4.25: Lifetime and current smoking by satisfaction with relationship with father

Overall, students reported high levels of satisfaction with their relationships with their parents, but level of satisfaction was not associated with lifetime or current smoking status.

Household members

Students were asked to indicate whether their household includes their father, stepfather, mother, stepmother, brother(s), sister(s), grandparent(s), other relatives(s) or non-relative(s), or whether they live alone. The majority (78.6%, n=1504) of respondents reported that two or more parents, including stepparents, are part of their household and 20.4% (n=391) reported living with only one parent. 19 students (1%) did not live with parents but with grandparent(s), other relative(s) and non-relative(s) (Table 4.26).

Household	N	%
Two or more parents	1504	78.6
One parent	391	20.4
Other	19	1.0
Total	1914	100.0

Table 4.26: Number and percentage of students by household type

Results presented in Table 4.27 and Figure 4.9 show that 69.3% (n=1040) of students from two-parent households, 66% (n=256) in one-parent households and 63.2% (n=12) of students from other household types had never smoked. While 6.7% (n=101) of students in two-parent households had smoked 40 or more cigarettes, 7.7% (n=30) of students in one-parent households had done so. Daily smoking was also much higher among students living in other household types (15.8%, n=3) compared to one-parent households (6.7%, n=26) and two-parent families (4.6%, n=69). No significant relationship was found between household type and lifetime or current smoking⁷⁰.

Household members								
Lifetime smoking*(number of occasions)	Two parents		One parent		Other		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1040	69.3	256	66.0	12	63.2	1308	68.6
1-2	159	10.6	49	12.6	2	10.5	210	11.0
3-39	200	13.4	53	13.7	2	10.5	255	13.4
40+	101	6.7	30	7.7	3	15.8	134	7.0
Total	1500	100.0	388	100.0	19	100.0	1907	100.4
Household members								
Current Smoking (number of cigarettes)	Two parents		One parent		Other		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	%	N
Not at all	1300	86.6	322	82.8	16	84.2	1638	85.8
Less than one a week	105	6.7	33	8.5	0	0.0	138	7.2
Less than 1 a day	28	1.9	8	2.7	0	0.0	36	1.9
Every day	69	4.6	26	6.7	3	15.8	98	5.3
Total	1502	100.0	389	100.0	19	100.0	1910	100.0

Table 4.27: Lifetime and current smoking by household membership

⁷⁰ Lifetime smoking by household type: [$X^2(6)=4.420$, $p=.620$; Cramer's $V=.034$]. Current smoking by household type: [$X^2(6)=10.160$, $p=.118$; Cramer's $V=.052$].

Table 4.9: Lifetime smoking by household type

Substance use of peers

Students were asked about their peers' substance use, namely whether their peers smoked cigarettes, drank alcohol, smoked cannabis, used inhalants, tranquilizers, or ecstasy. Responses were categorized into 'none', 'a few', 'some', 'most or all'.

Peer smoking

30% of students reported that none of their friend's smoke (n=559) and 42.4% (n=794) reported that a few of their friends smoke. 17.6% (n=30) reported that some, most (9.1%, n=170), or all (1.0%, n=18) of their friends' smoke.

No significant relationship was observed between lifetime and current smoking and respondents' peer-smoking⁷¹. However, results presented in Table 4.28 shows that a high proportion of students who reported that none of their friends smoked cigarettes had never smoked cigarettes themselves (72.4%, n=404) and were not current smokers (87.3%, n=488) compared to 64.1% (n=125) who reported that most or all of their friends smoke cigarettes but that they had not ever smoked cigarettes. Almost half of students who reported that most or all of their friend smoked cigarettes had themselves smoked cigarettes in their lifetimes (35.9%, n=63) and 18.5% (n=29) had smoked in the last 30 days.

⁷¹ Lifetime smoking by Peer smoking: [χ^2 (12)= 16.597, p=.165, Cramer's V=.055]. Current smoking by peer smoking: [χ^2 (12)= 9.994, p=.621]

Peer smoking										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	404	72.4	530	67.2	218	66.3	125	64.1	1277	68.5
1-2	52	9.3	88	11.2	42	12.8	25	9.9	207	11.1
3-39	68	12.2	119	15.1	37	11.2	22	16.4	246	13.2
40+	34	6.1	52	6.6	32	9.7	16	9.6	134	7.2
Total	558	100.0	789	100.0	329	100.0	188	100.0	1864	100.0

Peer smoking										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	488	87.3	678	85.6	274	83.5	159	81.5	1599	85.6
Less than one per week	37	6.6	56	7.1	26	7.9	15	11.9	134	7.2
Less than one a day	11	2.0	17	2.1	5	1.5	1	0.3	34	1.8
Every day	23	4.1	41	5.2	23	7.0	13	6.3	100	5.4
Total	559	100.0	792	100.0	328	100.0	188	100.0	1867	100.0

Table 4.28: Lifetime and current smoking by peer smoking

Figure 4.10: Lifetime smoking by how many friends smoke

Peer Alcohol Use

Students were also asked how many of their friends drink alcohol or get drunk. Only a minority had no friends who drink alcohol (12.0%, n=224) but fewer reported that all of their friends drink alcohol (8.5%, n=159). An even smaller minority

reported that all of their friends get drunk (6.4%, n=119). More students answered that they had a few friends who drank (27.4%, n=512) or most of their friends drank alcohol (35.1%, n=656) compared to some friends (17.1%, n=320).

Results presented in Table 4.29, 4.30 and Figure 4.11 show that 71.9% (n=161) whose friends did not drink at all had never smoked in their lifetime and 87.5% (n=196) were not current smokers. Students who reported that most or all of their friends drank alcohol had smoked more cigarettes in their lifetimes than had students whose friends had never drunk, although these results did not reach statistical significance⁷².

Similarly, students who reported that most or all of their friends get drunk smoked more cigarettes than students who said none of their friends get drunk. Again, there was no significant association between peer drunkenness and lifetime or current smoking⁷³.

Peer drinking												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most		All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	161	71.9	359	70.1	211	66.6	438	67.2	108	67.9	1277	68.5
1-2	21	9.4	56	10.9	40	12.6	68	10.4	22	13.8	207	11.1
3-39	29	12.9	67	13.1	46	14.5	85	13.0	19	11.9	246	13.2
40+	13	5.8	30	5.9	20	6.3	61	9.4	10	6.3	134	7.2
Total	224	100.0	512	100.0	317	100.0	652	100.0	159	100.0	1864	100.0
Peer drinking												
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most		All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	196	87.5	447	87.3	265	83.1	554	84.8	137	86.2	1599	85.6
Less than one per week	16	7.1	33	6.4	30	9.4	42	6.4	13	8.2	134	7.2
Less than one a day	2	0.9	8	1.6	12	3.8	10	1.5	2	1.3	34	1.8
Every day	10	4.5	24	4.7	12	3.8	47	7.2	7	4.4	100	5.4
Total	224	100.0	512	100.0	319	100.0	653	100.0	159	100.0	1867	100.0

Table 4.29: Lifetime and current smoking by peer drinking

⁷² Lifetime smoking by peer alcohol use: [χ^2 (12)= 10.789, p=.547]. Current smoking by peer smoking: [χ^2 (12)= 18.970, p=.089]

⁷³ Lifetime smoking by peer drunkenness: [χ^2 (12)= 12.943, p=.373]. Current smoking by peer drunkenness: [χ^2 (12)= 12.918, p=.375]

Peer drunkenness												
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most		All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	245	73.4	337	67.3	288	67.6	321	67.2	80	67.2	1271	68.4
1-2	26	7.8	59	11.8	49	11.5	57	11.9	17	14.3	208	11.2
3-39	44	13.2	74	14.8	57	13.4	56	11.7	15	12.6	246	13.2
40+	19	5.7	31	6.2	32	7.5	44	9.2	7	5.9	133	7.2
Total	334	100.0	501	100.0	426	100.0	478	100.0	119	100.0	1858	100.0

Peer drunkenness												
Current (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most		All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	295	88.3	428	85.3	360	84.3	410	85.6	101	84.9	1594	85.7
Less than one per week	22	6.6	38	7.6	37	8.7	25	5.2	12	10.1	134	7.2
Less than one a day	6	1.8	9	1.8	8	1.9	9	1.9	1	0.8	33	1.8
Every day	11	3.3	27	5.4	22	5.2	35	7.3	5	4.2	100	5.4
Total	334	100.0	502	100.0	427	100.0	479	100.0	119	100.0	1861	100.0

Table 4.30: Lifetime and current smoking by peer drunkenness

Figure 4.11: Lifetime smoking by how many friends get drunk

Peer cannabis Use

Students were asked how many of their friends use cannabis and responses are presented in Table 4.31. Half of the students responded that none of their friends use cannabis (50%, n=931) and over a quarter reported that a few of their friends did (31.0%, n=578). 12.0% (n=224) answered that some of their friends use cannabis, 5.7% (n=106) said most or all of their friends and 1.4% (n=26) students said all of their friends did.

There was a significant association between peer cannabis use and lifetime and current⁷⁴ smoking. Responses show that the majority of students who reported that none of their friends had used cannabis were non-smokers (71.2%, n=661). Out of those who said that most or all of their friends use cannabis, 9.8% (n=13) had smoked 40 cigarettes or more in their lifetime and 9.9% (n=13) smoked every day.

Peer cannabis use										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	661	71.2	378	65.7	152	68.2	79	59.8	1270	68.4
1-2	98	10.6	69	12.0	21	9.4	20	15.2	208	11.2
3-39	120	12.9	73	12.7	33	14.8	20	15.2	246	13.2
40+	49	5.3	55	9.6	17	7.6	13	9.8	134	7.2
Total	928	100.0	575	100.0	223	100.0	132	100.0	1858	100.0

Peer cannabis use										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	813	87.5	486	84.2	186	83.0	108	82.4	1593	85.6
Less than one per week	59	6.4	43	7.5	22	9.8	10	7.6	134	7.2
Less than one a day	20	2.2	10	1.7	4	1.8	0	0.0	34	1.8
Every day	37	4.0	38	6.6	12	5.4	13	9.9	100	5.4
Total	929	100.0	577	100.0	224	100.0	131	100.0	1861	100.0

Table 4.31: Lifetime and current smoking by peer cannabis use

⁷⁴ Lifetime smoking by peer cannabis use: [χ^2 (9)= 17.748, p=.038, Cramer's V=.056]. Current smoking by peer cannabis use: [χ^2 (9)= 16.935, p=.050, Cramer's v=.055]

Figure 4.12: Current smoking by peer cannabis use

Smoking and peer use of ecstasy

When students were asked how many of their friends take ecstasy, the majority of students (84.4%, n=1576) did not have any friends who use ecstasy. 11.9% (n=222) had a few friends who use ecstasy and 2.4% (n=44) had some friends who use ecstasy. 1.4% (n=25) reported that most or all of their friends use ecstasy.

Results presented in Table 4.32 show that 15.4% (n=4) of students who reported that most or all of their friends use ecstasy have smoked 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetimes and 11.5% (n=3) smoked every day, while less than 6.8% (n=106) of those whose friends did not use ecstasy have done so. Both lifetime and current smoking were not significantly associated with the number of friends who use ecstasy⁷⁵.

Peer use of ecstasy										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1087	69.3	142	63.9	30	68.2	16	61.5	1275	68.5
1-2	170	10.8	26	12.2	8	18.2	2	7.7	207	11.1
3-39	206	13.1	31	14.0	4	9.0	4	15.4	245	13.2
40+	106	6.8	22	9.9	2	4.6	4	15.4	134	7.2
Total	1569	100.0	222	100.0	44	100.0	26	100.0	1861	100.0
Peer use of ecstasy										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	&	N	%
None	1352	86.0	184	83.3	40	90.9	21	80.8	1597	85.7
Less than one per week	110	7.0	20	9.1	2	4.6	2	7.7	134	7.2
Less than one a day	28	1.8	5	2.2	0	0.0	0	0.0	33	1.8
Every day	83	5.2	12	5.4	2	4.5	3	11.5	100	5.3
Total	1573	100.0	221	100.0	44	100.0	26	100.0	1864	100.0

Table 4.32: Lifetime and current smoking by peer use of ecstasy

Smoking and Peer Use of Inhalants

Students were also asked how many of their friends use inhalants. Majority of students (85.1%, n=1592) responded that they had no friends who use inhalants, 10.7% (n=200) had a few friends who use inhalants, 2.7% (n=50) had some friends and only 1.6% (n=29) responded that most or all of their friends use inhalants.

⁷⁵ Lifetime smoking by peer use of ecstasy: [$\chi^2(9) = 9.874, p = .361, \text{Cramer's } V = .042$]. Current smoking by peer use of ecstasy: [$\chi^2(9) = 5.433, p = .795, \text{Cramer's } v = .031$]

Table 4.32 shows that 17.2% (n=5) who reported that most or all of their friends use inhalants have smoked 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetime and 13.8% (n=4) smoke every day. Of those students whose friends do not use inhalants, 68.8% (n=1090) have never used inhalants in their lifetime and 86.3% (n=1370) had not used inhalants in the last month. Again, no significant association was found between current and lifetime smoking and peer use of inhalants⁷⁶.

Peer use of inhalants										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1090	68.8	138	69.0	31	62.0	18	62.1	1277	68.5
1-2	179	11.3	19	9.5	7	14.0	3	10.3	208	11.2
3-39	206	13.0	26	13.0	10	20.0	3	10.3	245	13.1
40+	110	6.9	17	8.5	2	4.0	5	17.2	134	7.2
Total	1585	100.0	200	100.0	50	100.0	29	100.0	1864	100.0
Peer use of inhalants										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1370	86.3	166	83.0	42	84.0	22	75.9	1600	85.7
Less than one per week	110	6.9	17	8.5	5	10.0	2	6.9	134	7.2
Less than one a day	27	1.7	4	2.0	1	2.0	1	3.5	33	1.7
Every day	81	5.1	13	6.5	2	4.0	4	13.8	100	5.4
Total	1588	100.0	200	100.0	50	100.0	29	100.0	1867	100.0

Table 4.33: Lifetime and current smoking by peer use of inhalants

Smoking and Peer Use of Tranquilisers or Sedatives

Students were asked how many of their friends use tranquilizers or sedatives without a doctor's prescription. (Table 4.34) No significant association was observed between lifetime and current smoking by number of friends who use tranquilizers or sedatives⁷⁷. However, students who reported that most or all of their friends used tranquilizers or sedatives smoked more packs of cigarettes (14.8%, n=4) than students who had no friends who used tranquilizers or sedatives (6.6%, n=108). Similarly, students who reported that most or all of their friends used tranquilizers or sedatives were more likely to smoke every day (11.3%, n=3) compared to students whose friends did not.

⁷⁶ Lifetime smoking by use of inhalants: [χ^2 (9)= 8.794, p=.456, Cramer's V=.040]. Current smoking by peer use of inhalants: [χ^2 (9)= 7.048, p=.632, Cramer's V=.036]

⁷⁷ Lifetime smoking by use of tranquilizers or sedatives: [χ^2 (12)= 16.900, p=.153]. Current smoking by peer use of tranquilizers or sedatives: [χ^2 (12)= 9.994, p=.621]

Peer use of tranquilizers or sedatives										
Lifetime smoking (number of occasions)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1133	69.4	104	62.3	21	65.6	17	62.9	1275	68.6
1-2	176	10.8	22	13.2	7	21.9	2	7.7	207	11.1
3-39	216	13.2	23	13.8	1	3.1	4	14.6	244	13.1
40+	108	6.6	18	10.8	3	9.4	4	14.8	133	7.2
Total	1633	100.0	167	100.0	32	100.0	27	100.0	1859	100.0

Peer use of tranquilizers or sedatives										
Current smoking (number of cigarettes)	None		A few		Some		Most or All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	1413	86.4	134	80.2	28	84.8	22	81.3	1597	85.8
Less than one per week	112	6.9	17	10.2	2	6.1	2	7.4	133	7.1
Less than one a day	31	1.9	2	1.2	0	0.0	0	0.0	33	1.8
Every day	79	4.8	14	8.4	3	9.1	3	11.3	99	5.3
Total	1635	100.0	167	100.0	33	100.0	27	100.0	1862	100.0

Table 4.34: Lifetime and current smoking by peer tranquilizers or sedatives use

Figure 4.13: Current smoking by peer use of tranquilizers or sedatives

Summary

Socioeconomic status was strongly associated with smoking. Having parents with higher educational attainment was associated with a lower likelihood of smoking and the effect was similar for both parents. 42.5% of respondents whose fathers had completed primary school or less had ever smoked compared to 33.5% whose fathers had received or completed third-level education. A further 14.9% of respondents whose fathers had primary education only, reported smoking everyday compared to only 2.8% respondents whose fathers received a third-level education. Similarly, 40% of students whose mothers had completed primary school or less had ever smoked cigarettes compared to 28.2% of students whose mothers received a third-level education.

Respondents who perceived their family to be 'very much less well off' were most likely to smoke more than 40 cigarettes or more (25%) followed by respondents who perceived their family to be 'very much better off' than their peers (13.7%). Respondents who perceived their family to be 'better off' were the most likely to abstain from cigarettes (73.7). Similarly, respondents who perceived their family to be 'very much less well off' were more likely to smoke cigarettes every day (29.1%) compared to those who were 'better off' (3.55) and 'about the same' (3.8%).

Absence from school due to skipping class, illness or other reasons and having a lower academic grade were strongly associated with higher levels of smoking. 40% of students who had smoked more than 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetime had skipped school on 7 or more days and 34.5% smoked every day. 73.6% of students who had not skipped school in the last 30 days had never smoked a cigarette in their lifetime and 89.5% were not current smokers. Students who missed class on 7 or more days of the last 30 due to illness were also much more likely to smoke every day than those who did not miss any class (14.3% compared to 3.2%).

Academic attainment was also significantly related to smoking behaviour; students with low grades were much more likely to smoke every day (27.8% of students who reported average E or lower grades) compared to students who reported average grade scores of A or B (1.9%).

The students' relationships with their parents were also strongly related to smoking. 70.7% of students whose parents set rules for outside the home had never smoked and 86.2% had not smoked at all in the last 30 days. Students whose parents almost never set rules for outside the home were more likely to smoke 40 cigarettes or more in their lifetime (11.2%) and were more likely to smoke every day (8.8%) than students whose parents didn't set rules for outside the home. Similarly, 76% of students whose parents almost always know where they are on Saturday evenings had never smoked cigarettes in their lifetimes and 90% were not current smokers. Students whose parents almost never know where they are were more likely to smoke more than 40 cigarettes in their lifetimes (28.9%) and smoke every day (13.7%) than students whose parents almost always know where they are. Smoking was related to peer use of cannabis and other substances.

E-CIGARETTES AND WATER PIPES

Students were asked if they had ever used e-cigarettes (Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems, ENDS), when they first tried e-cigarettes, their reasons for using e-cigarettes, and their cigarette smoking habits at that time as well as their water pipe use.

Use of e-cigarettes

39% (n=758) of respondents reported ever using e-cigarettes including 15.5% (n=301) who responded that they had used an e-cigarette in the last 30 days. A further 13.6% (n=264) reported using e-cigarettes in the last 12 months, and 9.7% (n=189) answered that they had used e-cigarettes ‘more than 12 months ago’.

E-cigarette Use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes, last 30 days	185	19.6	117	11.7	301	15.5
Yes, last 12 months	128	13.6	136	13.6	264	13.6
Yes, more than 12 months ago	117	12.4	72	7.2	189	9.7
<i>Ever used</i>	430	45.6	325	32.5	754	39.0
Never	535	56.8	684	68.4	1219	62.7

Table 4.35: E-cigarette ever-use by gender

E-cigarette use in the last 30 days

When students were asked to consider how often they used e-cigarettes during the last 30 days, 81.9% (n=1592) reported that they had not used e-cigarettes at all in the previous 30 days, and 9.5% (n=184) reported that they had used e-cigarettes at least once per week in the last 30 days. 4% (n=78) of respondents said they had used e-cigarettes at least once per week and 4.6% (n=89) said they had used e-cigarettes almost every day in the last 30 days. There were significant differences in 30-day e-cigarette use between males and females, as more male students reported using e-cigarettes in the last 30 days (Table 4.36) than did female students⁷⁸.

30-day e-cigarette Use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	726	77.2	866	86.4	1592	81.9
Less than once per week	97	10.3	87	8.7	184	9.5
At least once per week	51	5.4	27	2.7	78	4.0
Almost everyday	67	7.1	22	2.2	89	4.6
Total	941	100.0	1002	100.0	1943	100.0

Table 4.36: E-cigarette use during the last 30 days by gender

First use of e-cigarettes

Students were asked at what age they used their first e-cigarette (Table 4.37). Of those students who had used an e-cigarette (37.6%, n=729), more than half reported that they were 14-15 years old (67%, n=489) and 20.3% (n=148) were aged 13. Male students tended to commence e-cigarette use at a younger age (mean=13.6 years, SD=1.4) than female students (mean=14.1 years, SD=.88)⁷⁹. The mean age when students first used e-cigarettes was around 0.2 years older than the mean

⁷⁸ 30-day cigarette use by gender: $\chi^2(3) = 41.118, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .146$

⁷⁹ Age of first e-cigarette use by gender: $t(727) = -5.448, p < .001$

age of initiation for smoking⁸⁰.

Age at first e-cigarette	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
9 years old or less	15	3.6	0	0.0	15	2.1
10 years old	3	0.7	1	0.3	4	0.5
11 years old	7	1.7	0	0.0	7	1.0
12 years old	37	8.9	13	2.1	50	6.8
13 years old	98	23.7	50	15.9	148	20.3
14 years old	135	32.6	140	44.4	275	37.7
15 years old	111	26.8	103	32.7	214	29.4
16 years old or older	8	1.9	8	2.5	16	2.2
Total	414	100.0	315	100.0	729	100.0

Table 4.37: Age at which students first used e-cigarettes

Figure 4.14: Age of initiation for e-cigarettes and tobacco

E-cigarette use on a daily basis

Results presented in Table 4.38 show that 41.8% (n=87) of respondents who reported that they use e-cigarette on a daily basis started doing so at 15 years old and 28.4% (n=59) started using e-cigarette daily aged 14 years. 11.1% (n=23) reported starting to use e-cigarettes every day at 13 years old. 153 of the 208 e-cigarette daily users were male and 55 were females, and they started using e-cigarettes on a daily basis at a similar age⁸¹. The mean age for male students was 15.1 years (SD=1.65) and for female students was 15.2 years (SD=1.22)

⁸⁰ E-cigarettes: mean=13.8, n=729, SD=1.23, SE=.05. Tobacco: mean=13.7, n=635, SD=1.66, SE=.06

⁸¹ Age of starting to use e-cigarettes on a daily basis by gender: [t(206)= -.505, p=.614]

Age began daily e-cigarette use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
12 years old or less	17	11.1	5	9.1	22	10.6
13 years old	18	11.7	5	9.1	23	11.1
14 years old	42	27.5	17	30.9	59	28.4
15 years old	60	39.2	27	49.1	87	41.8
16 years old or older	16	10.5	1	1.5	17	8.2
Total	153	100.0	55	100.0	208	100.0

Table 4.38: Age at which students began using e-cigarettes daily

Figure 4.15: Age of initiation for e-cigarettes and daily e-cigarette use

Figure 4.15 shows the ages at which students first used an e-cigarette and began using e-cigarettes on a daily basis. While the most frequent age for first using e-cigarette is 14 years, the most frequent age for daily e-cigarette use is 15 years which indicates a time lag between first using e-cigarettes and starting to use e-cigarettes daily.

E-cigarettes and tobacco

Lifetime and current tobacco smoking and use of e-cigarettes was examined. Overall, 39% of students (n=754) reported ever using an e-cigarette. Around 89.6% of respondents reported that they had never used e-cigarettes and never smoked a cigarette in their lifetime (n=1091). 10.4% (n=126) of students who had never used e-cigarettes had smoked tobacco at least once in their lifetime. While 14.4% (n=279) of all respondents had smoked tobacco in the last 30 days, more than half of students who had used e-cigarettes in the previous month had smoked tobacco (54%, n=154).

Of the students who used e-cigarettes between one and 12 months ago, 10.8% (n=27) had smoked in the previous month but not every week and 29.8% (n=74) had smoked between 3-39 cigarettes.

E-cigarette use										
Lifetime Tobacco Use* (*number of occasions)	Never Used		Used more than 12 months ago		Used in the last 12 months		Used in the last 30 days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1091	89.6	81	46.0	96	38.7	55	19.2	1323	68.7
1-2	75	6.2	46	26.1	52	21.0	38	13.3	211	10.9
3-39	38	3.1	32	18.2	74	29.8	115	40.2	259	13.4
40+	13	1.1	17	9.7	26	10.5	78	27.3	134	7.0
Total	1217	100.0	176	100.0	248	100.0	286	100.0	1927	100.0

E-cigarette use										
Current Tobacco Use (*number of occasions)	Never Used		Used more than 12 months ago		Used in the last 12 months		Used in the last 30 days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	1177	96.6	145	81.9	203	81.5	131	46.0	1661	85.6
Less than one per week	30	2.5	18	10.2	27	10.8	64	22.5	141	7.3
Less than 1 per day	4	0.3	3	1.7	3	1.2	25	8.8	37	1.9
Every day	8	0.7	11	6.2	16	6.4	65	22.8	101	5.2
Total	1219	100.0	177	100.0	249	100.0	285	100.0	1940	100.0

Table 4.39: Lifetime and current smoking by e-cigarettes

Relationship with tobacco when first tried e-cigarette

Students were asked about their relationship with tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes. The majority of respondents reported that they had never smoked at the time they first used e-cigarette (66.7%, n=461) and another 24.3% (n=168) reported that they had tried tobacco but smoked occasionally.

Figure 4.16: Relationship with tobacco when first used an e-cigarette

Respondents' relationship with tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes was correlated with their lifetime use of e-cigarettes. Responses presented in Table 4.40 show that students who smoked tobacco regularly were more likely to continue using e-cigarettes.

Of students who had used e-cigarettes in the last year, 77.8% (n=166) reported that they had never used tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes and only 4.55% (n=10) were regular smokers. 50.7% (n=141) of respondents who had used e-cigarettes in the last 30 days had never used tobacco, while 14% (39) were regular tobacco users

Use of e-cigarettes by relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette								
Use of e-cigarettes	I had never used tobacco		I had occasionally used tobacco		I was regularly using tobacco		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Used more than 12 months ago ⁸²	122	79.2	22	14.3	10	6.5	154	100.0
Used in the last 12 months ⁸³	166	77.8	46	20.7	10	4.5	222	100.0
Used in the last 30 days ⁸⁴	141	50.7	98	35.3	39	14.0	278	100.0
Total	467	100.0	168	100.0	62	100.0	9.0	100.0

Table 4.40: Use of e-cigarettes by relationship with tobacco when first used an e-cigarette

Students' lifetime and current tobacco smoking habits were correlated with students' relationship with tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes (Table 4.41). There were significant associations between lifetime and current tobacco smoking⁸⁵ and relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette. 52.1% (n=240) of respondents reported having smoked tobacco in their lifetimes but had not smoked at the time of their first e-cigarette. 61 students (98.4%) who had smoked tobacco in their lifetime reported smoking tobacco regularly when they first tried e-cigarettes. 16.3% (n=75) of students reported that they had never used tobacco at the time of their first e-cigarettes but currently smoked tobacco at the time of the survey.

Lifetime smoking by relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette								
Lifetime tobacco smoking	I had never used tobacco		I smoked tobacco occasionally		I smoked tobacco regularly		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	220	47.8	7	4.2	1	1.6	228	33.2
1-2	109	23.7	12	7.3	2	3.2	123	17.9
3-39	112	24.3	88	53.3	13	21.0	213	31.0
40+	19	4.1	58	35.2	46	74.2	123	17.9
Total	460	100.0	165	100.0	62	100.0	687	100.0

⁸² More than 12 months e-cig. use and relationship with Tobacco when first tried e-cig.: [$X^2(3)=14.254$, $p=.001$, Cramer's $V=.144$]

⁸³ Last 12 months e-cig. use and relationship with Tobacco when first tried e-cig.: [$X^2(3)=12.060$, $p=.002$, Cramer's $V=.132$]

⁸⁴ 30 day e-cig. use and relationship with Tobacco when first tried e-cig.: [$X^2(3)=54.334$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.281$]

⁸⁵ Lifetime smoking by relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette: [$X^2(6)=337.478$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.496$]. Current smoking by relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette: [$X^2(3)=383.667$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.528$].

Current smoking by relationship with tobacco when first tried an e-cigarette								
Current tobacco smoking	I had never used tobacco		I smoked tobacco occasionally		I smoked tobacco regularly		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	385	83.7	65	39.2	6	9.7	456	66.3
Less than one per week	52	11.3	52	31.3	5	8.1	109	15.8
Less than 1 per day	14	3.0	18	10.8	1	1.6	33	4.8
Everyday	9	2.0	31	18.7	50	80.6	90	13.1
Total	460	100.0	166	100.0	62	100.0	688	100.0

Table 4.41: Lifetime and current tobacco smoking by relationship with tobacco when first used an e-cigarette

Reason for use of e-cigarettes

Students were asked why they first tried e-cigarettes and possible answers offered were: ‘in order to stop smoking cigarettes’, ‘out of curiosity’, ‘because my friends offered an e-cigarette to me’, ‘none of the above reasons’. 475 students who had used e-cigarettes responded and students could select multiple responses⁸⁶.

The most common reason for trying e-cigarettes was ‘out of curiosity’, with 66.3% of e-cigarette users selecting this answer (n=315) and the next most frequent answer was ‘because friends offered an e-cigarette to me’ (28.8%, n=137), 8.6% (n=41) said ‘none of the above reasons’ and 3.4% (n=16) reported using e-cigarettes to stop smoking tobacco. Out of 16 students (3.4%) who reported using e-cigarettes to stop smoking tobacco, 12 of them reported smoking 40 or more cigarettes in their lifetime.

Reason for trying e-cigarettes	Yes		No		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
To stop smoking cigarettes	16	3.4	459	96.6	475	100.0
Out of curiosity	315	66.3	160	33.7	475	100.0
Because friends offered it	137	28.8	338	71.2	475	100.0
None of the above reasons	41	8.6	434	91.4	475	100.0

Table 4.42: Reasons for trying e-cigarettes

⁸⁶ Students who selected ‘I have never tried e-cigarettes were excluded’.

Figure 4.17: Reasons for trying e-cigarettes

Perceived risk of e-cigarette use

Students were asked how much they thought people risk harming themselves if they tried e-cigarettes once or twice (Table 4.40). Almost half (46.3%, n=893) of respondents believed that there was no risk in using e-cigarettes once or twice, and 37.2% (n=718) believed that there was a slight risk. Only 4.2% of students believed that there was a great risk in trying e-cigarettes once or twice. There were significant gender differences in perceived risk of e-cigarette use⁸⁷. More male students (51.1%, n=477) than female students (41.8%, n=416) perceived that there was no risk in trying e-cigarettes once or twice, while more female students (4.5%, n=45) perceived that there was great risk than did male students (3.9%, n=36).

Perceived risk of trying e-cigarettes once or twice	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	477	51.1	416	41.8	893	46.3
Slight risk	312	33.4	406	40.8	718	37.2
Moderate risk	60	6.4	90	9.5	150	7.8
Great risk	36	3.9	45	4.5	81	4.2
Don't know	49	5.3	38	3.8	87	4.5
Total	934	100.0	995	100.0	1929	100.0

Table 4.43: Perceived risk of trying e-cigarettes once or twice

⁸⁷ Trying e-cigarettes once or twice: [$\chi^2(4)=22.958$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.109$]

Factors related to e-cigarette use

Socioeconomic status: parental education & perceived relative wealth

Around 68.6% of respondents whose fathers had third-level education had never used e-cigarettes. Students whose fathers received only primary education were the most likely to have used e-cigarettes in the previous 30 days (30.6%, n=15) and those whose fathers received third-level education were the least likely (12.7%, n=114).

Similarly, those whose mothers had completed their education⁸⁸ at or before the end of primary schooling were the most likely to have used e-cigarettes in the previous 30 days (28.5%, n=6) compared to students whose mothers had third-level education (13.7%, n=156). Generally, parental education seemed to have a protective factor against e-cigarette use

Father's Education										
Lifetime e-cigarette use (number of cigarettes)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	25	5.1	392	56.0	615	68.6	156	64.2	1188	62.9
Used more than 12 months ago	3	6.1	80	11.4	70	7.8	32	13.2	185	9.8
Used in the last 12 months	8	16.3	110	15.7	109	12.2	29	11.9	256	13.6
Used in the last 30 days	15	30.6	133	19.0	114	12.7	31	12.8	293	15.2
Mother's Education										
Lifetime e-cigarette use (number of cigarettes)	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't Know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	N	%	N	%	N
None	11	52.4	305	54.2	762	67.3	109	64.8	1187	63.0
Used more than 12 months ago	2	9.5	75	13.3	88	7.7	20	11.9	185	9.8
Used in the last 12 months	2	9.5	91	16.1	144	12.7	17	10.1	254	13.4
Used in the last 30 days	6	28.5	104	18.4	156	13.7	26	15.4	292	15.5

Table 4.44: Lifetime e-cigarette use by father's and mother's education

As with parental education, respondents who considered their family to be 'very much less well off' (18.8%, n=6) and 'less well off' (17.3%, n=25) were the most likely to have experimented with e-cigarette use at least once a week, or every day (Table 4.45, Figure 4.18).

⁸⁸ Due to low responses in some categories, 'Some secondary school' and 'completed secondary school' was recoded as 'secondary', 'some college or university' and 'completed college or university' was recoded as 'third level'

Perceived relative wealth												
Lifetime e-cigarette use*(number of occasions)	Very (much) better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		(Very) much less well off		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	186	60.7	380	65.6	524	64.3	77	52.7	14	43.7	1181	62.9
Used more than 12 months ago	29	9.5	52	8.9	86	10.5	12	8.2	6	18.7	185	9.8
Used in the last 12 months	44	14.4	83	14.3	96	11.8	26	17.8	6	18.7	255	13.6
Used in the last 30 days	51	16.7	72	12.4	120	14.7	38	26.0	7	21.8	288	15.3
Perceived relative wealth ⁸⁹												
Current e-cigarette use (number of cigarettes)	Very much better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		Very much less well off		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	243	79.2	496	85.5	678	83.4	104	71.7	21	65.6	1542	82.2
Less than once per week	35	11.4	41	7.1	80	9.8	16	11.0	5	15.6	177	9.4
At least once a week	12	3.9	24	4.1	26	3.2	12	8.3	2	6.3	76	4.1
Every day	17	5.5	19	3.3	29	3.6	13	9.0	4	12.5	82	4.3
Total	307	100.0	580	100.0	813	100.0	145	100.0	32	100.0	1877	100.0

Table 4.45: Lifetime and current e-cigarette use by perceived relative wealth

Figure 4.18: Current e-cigarette use by perceived relative wealth

A strong association was observed between respondents reported average grades and current e-cigarette use⁹⁰. 86.8% (n=743) of students who scored A and B had never smoked e-cigarettes compared to 61.1% (n=22) who scored E or lower. Only 2% (n=17) of students who scored A or B used e-cigarettes every day.

⁸⁹ Current e-cigarette use by perceived relative wealth: [$\chi^2 (12)= 34.667, p=.001$. Cramer's V= .007].

⁹⁰ Current e-cigarette use by average grade: [$\chi^2 (9)=54.941, p<.001$. Cramer's V= .099]

Average Grade										
Current e-cigarette use (frequency of e-cigarettes use)	A and B (70 - 100%)		Mostly C (51- 69%)		Mostly (40 to 50%)		E or lower (39% or less)		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	743	86.8	607	80.9	155	71.8	22	61.1	1527	82.2
Less than once per week	68	7.9	75	10.0	27	12.5	7	19.4	177	9.5
At least once a week	28	3.3	25	3.3	16	7.4	5	13.9	74	4.0
Every day	17	2.0	43	5.8	18	8.3	2	5.6	80	4.3
Total	856	100.0	750	100.0	216	100.0	36	100.0	1858	100.0

Table 4.46: Current e-cigarette use by average grades reported

WATER PIPES

Regarding water pipe use, 93.2% of respondents reported that they had never used a water pipe to smoke tobacco (n=1803). Of those who reported using a water pipe, 41 (2.1%) said they had used it in the last 12 months and 41 (2.1%) said they had used a water pipe more than 12 months previously. 291 (15.5%) reported using water pipes in the previous 30 days. Of the 291 students who used water pipes in the previous 30 days, 18 (54.5%) of them smoked more than 40 cigarettes in their lifetime including 16 students (48.5%) who smoke every day. Of the students who had never used a water pipe, 72.3% (n=1300) had never smoked a cigarette and 11.1% (n=200) had smoked once or twice (Table 4.39, Figure 4.19).

Figure 4.15: Use of water pipes

Water pipe use										
Lifetime smoking	Never used		Used more than 12 months ago		Used in the last 12 months		Used in the last 30 days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	1300	72.3	5	12.2	11	19.3	2	6.1	1318	68.3
1-2	200	11.1	4	9.8	6	10.5	2	6.1	212	11.0
3-39	211	11.7	14	34.1	25	43.9	11	33.3	261	13.5
40+	87	4.8	18	43.9	15	26.3	18	54.5	138	7.2
Total	1798	100.0	41	100.0	57	100.0	33	100.0	1929	100.0

Water pipe use										
Current smoking	Never used		Used more than 12 months ago		Used in the last 12 months		Used in the last 30 days		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not at all	1598	88.8	19	46.3	28	49.1	7	21.1	1652	85.6
Less than one per week	112	6.2	7	17.1	14	24.6	7	21.2	140	7.3
Less than 1 per day	25	1.4	5	12.2	4	7.0	3	9.1	37	1.9
Everyday	65	3.6	10	24.4	11	19.3	16	48.5	102	5.3
Total	1800	100.0	41	100.0	57	100.0	33	100.0	1931	100.0

Table 4.47: Lifetime and current smoking by use of water pipes

Figure 4.19: Lifetime smoking (number of occasions) by water pipe use

Summary

39% of respondents reported ever using e-cigarettes and 15.4% reported doing so in the last 30 days. This is higher than tobacco smoking, as 31.6% ever smoked and as 14.4% of students reported smoking tobacco in the last 30 days. More than half of students who reported using e-cigarettes had done so when they were 14-15 years old (67%). The mean age when students first used e-cigarettes was around 0.2 years older than the mean age of initiation for smoking. 42% of respondents started using e-cigarettes on a daily basis at 15 years old.

Smoking tobacco and using e-cigarettes were very strongly related; 52.1% of e-cigarette users reported having smoked

tobacco in their lifetimes but had not smoked at the time of their first e-cigarette. 98.4% of students who had smoked tobacco in their lifetime reported smoking tobacco regularly when they first tried e-cigarettes. 16.3% of students reported that they 'had never used' tobacco at the time they used their first e-cigarettes but were now current tobacco smokers.

Regarding students' relationship with tobacco when they first tried e-cigarettes, 66.2% of respondents answered that they had never smoked tobacco at the time they first tried e-cigarettes. 24.3% had smoked occasionally, and 9% had smoked regularly. The majority of e-cigarette users started using them 'out of curiosity' (66.3%) while 28.8% reported that it was because their friends offered it. Only 3.4% reported using e-cigarettes to stop smoking tobacco

Almost half (46.3%) of respondents believed that there was no risk in using e-cigarettes once or twice, and 37.2% believed that there was a slight risk. Only 4.2% of students believed that there was a great risk in trying e-cigarettes once or twice. More male students (51.1%) than female students (41.8%) perceived that there was no risk in trying e-cigarettes once or twice, while more female students (4.5%) perceived that there was great risk than did male students (3.9%).

Generally, parental education seemed to have a protective factor against e-cigarette use. Around 68.6% of respondents whose fathers had third-level education had never used e-cigarettes. Students whose fathers received only primary education were the most likely to have used e-cigarettes in the previous 30 days (30.6%) and those whose fathers received third-level education were the least likely (12.7%).

Similarly, those whose mothers had completed their education at or before the end of primary schooling were the most likely to have used e-cigarettes in the previous 30 days (28.5%) compared to students whose mothers had third-level education (13.7%).

Similarly, those who considered their family to be 'very much less well off' (18.8%, n=6) and 'less well off' (17.3%, n=25) were the most likely to have experimented with e-cigarette use at least once a week, or every day.

93.2% of respondents reported that they had never used a water pipe to smoke tobacco. Of those who reported using a water pipe, 2.1% said they had used it in the last 12 months and 15.5% reported using water pipes in the previous 30 days.

CANNABIS

19% had ever tried cannabis

16%

Had used cannabis in the last 12 months

9%

Had used cannabis in the last 30 days

24.8% vs 15%

More boys than girls **have ever tried** cannabis

12% vs 7%

More boys than girls **have used** cannabis in **the last 30 days**

53% vs 37%

More girls than boys **perceived** a great risk **from using cannabis regularly**

24% vs 18%

More girls than boys **perceived** a great risk **from using cannabis occasionally**

More boys (22%) than girls (13%) **have tried unsuccessfully to stop**

79% of cannabis users first used it aged 14 or 15 years

42%

perceived obtaining cannabis as fairly or very easy

6%

Have had memory problems when smoking

73% Students had used cannabis with tobacco and **33%** had done so very often

46%

Have used cannabis before midday

- 31% Have a few friends who use cannabis
- 12% Have some friends who use cannabis
- 6% Have most friends who used cannabis
- 1% only have friends who use cannabis

5. CANNABIS USE

In ESPAD 2019, students were asked a number of questions related to their cannabis use over their lifetime, the last 12 months, and the last 30 days, their age of first cannabis use, perceived access to cannabis, perceived risk of cannabis use, opportunity to try cannabis without trying it, mixed cannabis with tobacco, as well as type of cannabis used in the previous 12 months. Socioeconomic status, school attendance and attainment, relationship with parents and parenting style, and peer substance use were examined to see if these were related to cannabis use in this cohort. The results on cannabis use as well as factors related to cannabis use are presented in this chapter

Cannabis Use

Lifetime

Respondents were asked on how many occasions in their lifetime they had used cannabis. As presented in Table 5.1, the majority of students (80.9%, n=1656) answered that they had never used cannabis in their lifetime. Among those who had used cannabis in their lifetime (19.1%, n=370), 8.1% (n=156) had tried cannabis once or twice and 4.1% (n=80) had tried it on more than 20 occasions.

There were significant differences in lifetime cannabis use between male and female respondents⁹¹ as more male (23.8%, n=223) than female respondents (14.7%, n=147) had ever tried cannabis. More male students had also tried cannabis 20 or more times (5.7%, n=53) than had female students (2.7%, n=27).

Lifetime cannabis use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	714	76.2	851	85.3	1565	80.9
<i>Ever used cannabis</i>	223	23.8	147	14.7	370	19.1
Once or twice	83	8.9	73	7.3	156	8.1
3 to 5 times	42	4.5	23	2.3	65	3.3
6 to 9 times	20	2.1	11	1.1	31	1.5
10 to 19 times	25	2.7	13	1.3	38	2.0
20 times or more	53	5.7	27	2.7	80	4.1
Total	937	100.0	998	100.0	1935	100.0

Table 5.1: Lifetime cannabis use by gender

The last 12 months

As can be seen in Table 5.2, 15.8% (n=303) of students have used cannabis in the last 12 months and 3.1% (n=60) of students reported that they had used cannabis 20 times or more in the last 12 months. Again, there were significant differences between male and females in the number of times they had used cannabis in the last 12 months⁹² as more male students (20%, n=186) had used cannabis in the last 12 months than had female students (11.8%, n=117). There were also differences in the intensity of their cannabis use as more male students than female students reported using cannabis more frequently.

⁹¹ Lifetime cannabis use: [$\chi^2(5)=31.148$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.126$]

⁹² 12 months cannabis use: [$\chi^2(5)=27.865$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.121$]

Cannabis use in the last 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	743	80.0	873	88.2	1616	84.2
<i>Ever</i>	<i>186</i>	<i>20.0</i>	<i>117</i>	<i>11.8</i>	<i>303</i>	<i>15.8</i>
Once or twice	74	8.0	57	5.8	131	6.8
3 to 5 times	39	4.2	16	1.6	55	2.9
6 to 9 times	23	2.5	12	1.2	35	1.8
10 to 19 times	14	1.5	8	0.8	22	1.1
20 times or more	36	3.8	24	2.4	60	3.1
Total	929	100.0	990	100.0	1919	100.0

Table 5.2: Cannabis use in the last 12 months by gender

The last 30 days

Overall, 9% (173) had used cannabis in the last 30 days compared to 91% (n=1744) who had not had cannabis in the last 30 days. 4.4% (n=85) reported using cannabis once or twice in the last 30 days and only 1.3% (n=24) reported using cannabis 20 times or more in the last 30 days. Significantly more male (11.52%, n=107) than female students (6.7%, n=66) reported using cannabis in the last 30 days⁹³.

Cannabis use in the last 30 days	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	822	88.5	922	93.3	1744	91.0
<i>30 days use</i>	<i>107</i>	<i>11.5</i>	<i>66</i>	<i>6.7</i>	<i>173</i>	<i>9.0</i>
Once or twice	52	5.6	33	3.3	85	4.4
3 to 5 times	15	1.6	21	2.1	36	1.9
6 to 9 times	18	1.9	1	0.1	19	1.0
10 to 19 times	6	0.6	3	0.3	9	0.5
20 to 39 times	16	1.7	8	0.8	24	1.3
Total	929	100.0	988	100.0	1917	100.0

Table 5.3: Cannabis use in the last 30 days by gender

Age of first cannabis use

Respondents were asked at what age they first tried cannabis and responses were recoded into '12 years or younger', '13 years old', '14 years old', '15 years old', '16 years or older'. The majority of students who used cannabis first tried it at 15 years (49.3%, n=187). and mean age of initiation was 15.2 years old (SD=1.43). Female students tried cannabis at an older age (mean=15.3 years, SE=.11) than male students (mean=15.1 years, SE=.10). There were no significant differences in the age at which male and female respondents first tried cannabis⁹⁴.

⁹³ Cannabis use-30 days: { $X^2(5)=28.069$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.121$ }

⁹⁴ Age of first cannabis use by gender: [$t(377)=-1.694$, $p=.091$]

Age of first cannabis use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	716	76.0	847	84.7	1563	80.5
12 years or younger	14	6.1	6	3.9	20	5.3
13 years old	28	12.4	15	9.8	43	11.4
14 years old	71	31.4	43	28.1	114	30.1
15 years old	107	47.4	80	52.3	187	49.3
16 years or older	6	2.7	9	5.9	15	3.9
Total	226	100.0	152	100.0	379	100.0

Table 5.4: Age of first cannabis use by gender

Figure 5.1 Age at first cannabis use by gender

Perceived access to cannabis

Students were asked how difficult they thought it would be to get cannabis if they wanted it. Almost half responded that it would be either ‘fairly easy’ or ‘very easy’ to get cannabis if they wanted it (42.4%, n=822) and only 17.2% (n=333) thought that it would be ‘impossible’. There were significant differences in perceived access to cannabis by gender⁹⁵ as more male students perceived that it would be ‘very easy’ (19.8%, n=186) than did female students (11.3%, n=113) and 16.4% (n=164) of female students believed that it would be ‘very difficult’ to obtain cannabis, compared to 13.5% (n=127) of male students who thought that it would.

⁹⁵ Access to cannabis: $[X^2(5)=34.915, p=0.000, \text{Cramer's } V=.134]$

Perceived access to cannabis	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Impossible	162	17.3	171	17.1	333	17.2
Very difficult	127	13.5	164	16.4	291	15.0
Fairly difficult	114	12.1	159	15.9	273	14.1
Fairly easy	259	27.6	264	26.4	523	27.0
Very easy	186	19.8	113	11.3	299	15.4
Don't know	91	9.7	129	12.9	220	11.3
Total	939	100.0	1000	100.0	1939	100.0

Table 5.5: Perceived access to cannabis by gender

Students were asked if they had ever had the possibility to try cannabis without trying it. 38% (n=734) responded affirmatively and 62% (n=1200) said no. There were significant gender differences in the number of times respondents had the opportunity to use cannabis without using it⁹⁶ as more female students (66.7%, n=664) reported they had never had such an opportunity than did male students (57.1%, n=536). More male students (16.8%, n=158) than female students (11.3%, n=112) reported that they had had such an opportunity 3 or more times.

Opportunities to use cannabis without use	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	536	57.1	664	66.7	1200	62.0
Once or twice	245	26.1	219	22.0	464	24.0
3 times or more	158	16.8	112	11.3	270	14.0
Total	939	100.0	995	100.0	1934	100.0

Table 5.6: Number of times possible to use cannabis without using by gender

Students were also asked if they had ever used cannabis mixed with tobacco (Table 5.7). Over a quarter of respondents (33.2%, n=123) who have used cannabis responded that they have used it with tobacco 'fairly' or 'very often', 25.2% (n=93) responded that they have rarely done so. There were no significant differences in respondents' use of cannabis mixed with tobacco by gender⁹⁷.

Cannabis mixed with tobacco	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	56	25.1	45	30.6	101	27.3
Rarely	62	27.8	31	21.1	93	25.2
From time to time	32	14.4	21	14.3	53	14.3
Fairly or very often	73	32.7	50	34.0	123	33.2
Total	223	100.0	147	100.0	370	100.0

Table 5.7: Cannabis mixed with tobacco

Perceived risk of cannabis

Students were asked a number of questions related to the perceived risks of cannabis use (physically or in other ways), in trying it once or twice, smoking cannabis occasionally, or smoking cannabis regularly. Overall, 31.9% (n=615) believed that

⁹⁶ Cannabis refusal skills: $[X^2(2)=21.344, p<.001, \text{Cramer's } V=.105]$

⁹⁷ Cannabis mixed with tobacco: $[X^2(3)=2.614, p=.455, \text{Cramer's } V=.084]$

there was no risk in trying cannabis once or twice; 35.2% (n=677) believed that there was a slight risk; and 10.2% (n=196) of students believed that there was a great risk. There were significant differences between male and female students⁹⁸ in perceived risk of trying cannabis once or twice.

Female respondents considered trying cannabis once or twice more risky, with 11% (n=109) saying there is a great risk in trying cannabis once or twice, compared to 9.3% (n=87) of male students.

Perceived risk of trying cannabis once or twice	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	367	39.4	248	25.0	615	31.9
Slight risk	291	31.2	386	38.9	677	35.2
Moderate risk	131	14.1	196	19.7	327	17.0
Great risk	87	9.3	109	11.0	196	10.2
Don't know	56	6.0	54	5.4	110	5.7
Total	932	100.0	993	100.0	1925	100.0

Table 5.8: Perceived risk of trying cannabis once or twice by gender

Students were asked how much people risked harming themselves if they smoked cannabis occasionally (Table 5.9) and 21.2% (n=407) answered that they perceived a great risk, 33.1% (n=636) responded 'moderate risk', and 15.3% (n=294) answered that they perceived no risk.

As with trying cannabis once or twice, there were significant differences in perceived risk of smoking cannabis occasionally⁹⁹ as more male students (21.2%, n=197) than female students (9.8%, n=97) perceived no risk from smoking cannabis occasionally. More female (24.1%, n=239) than male students (18%, n=168) perceived a great risk.

Perceived risk of smoking cannabis occasionally	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	197	21.2	97	9.8	294	15.3
Slight risk	245	26.3	225	22.7	470	24.4
Moderate risk	262	28.1	374	37.7	636	33.1
Great risk	168	18.0	239	24.1	407	21.2
Don't know	59	6.3	57	5.7	116	6.0
Total	931	100.0	992	100.0	1923	100.0

Table 5.9: Perceived risk of smoking cannabis occasionally by gender

Similarly, there were significant gender differences in perceived risk of smoking cannabis regularly¹⁰⁰ as more male students (15.2%, n=141) than female students (4.3%, n=43) perceived no risk in smoking cannabis regularly (Table 5.10). More female (54.3%, n=538) than male students (36.6%, n=340) perceived a great risk from smoking cannabis regularly.

⁹⁸ Trying cannabis once or twice: [$X^2(4)=49.900$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.161$]

⁹⁹ Smoking cannabis occasionally: [$X^2(4)=65.139$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.184$]

¹⁰⁰ Smoking cannabis regularly: [$X^2(4)=103.563$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.232$]

Perceived risk of trying cannabis regularly	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
No risk	141	15.2	43	4.3	184	9.6
Slight risk	149	16.0	103	10.4	252	13.1
Moderate risk	241	25.9	244	24.6	485	25.3
Great risk	340	36.6	538	54.3	878	45.7
Don't know	59	6.3	62	6.3	121	6.3
Total	930	100.0	990	100.0	1920	100.0

Table 5.10: Perceived risk of smoking cannabis regularly by gender

Students were asked if they had used certain types of cannabis in the last 12 months; ‘Cannabis resin’, ‘weed/skunk’, ‘cannabis oil’. Responses were recoded into ‘Yes’ or ‘No’ to examine the most common type of cannabis used by students. The results are shown in Table 5.11.

Results show that most students had used weed/skunk (17.3%, n=335), followed by those who answered that they had used cannabis resin (5.7%, n=111). Only 4.7% (n=90) responded they had used cannabis oil in the previous 12 months. There were significant differences in the use of cannabis resin¹⁰¹ and weed/skunk¹⁰² between male and female students as more male students (8.3%, n=77; 21.1%, n=198) than female students (3.4%, n=34; 13.7%, n=137) reported using more cannabis resin and weed/skunk respectively.

Types of cannabis used	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Cannabis resin	77	8.3	34	3.4	111	5.7
Weed/skunk	198	21.1	137	13.7	335	17.3
Cannabis Oil	52	2.6	38	3.8	90	4.7

Table 5.11: Type of cannabis used in the last 12 months by gender

Students were asked about their cannabis-related experiences in the last 12 months. Responses in this category were recoded into ‘Yes’ or ‘No’ to examine differences by gender, and results are presented in Table 5.12. Almost half of respondents who had used cannabis during the last 12 months (45.5%, n=135) had done so before midday and one-third (31.4%, n=93) had smoked cannabis alone. 37.3% (n=110) had had memory problems when smoking and almost a quarter (22.5%, n=67) have had problems (argument, fight, accident, bad result at school, etc.) because of cannabis use. Females (46%, n=57) were more likely than males (40%, n=53) to have had memory problems when using cannabis¹⁰³. Males (22%, n=38) were, however, more likely to have tried unsuccessfully to stop than females were (13.1%, n=16)¹⁰⁴.

¹⁰¹ Cannabis resin: [$X^2(1)=21.022$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.105$]

¹⁰² Weed/skunk: [$X^2(1)=18.401$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.097$]

¹⁰³ Had memory problems when smoking: [$X^2(1)=6.892$, $p=.009$, Cramer's $V=.153$]

¹⁰⁴ Tried unsuccessfully to stop: [$X^2(1)=3.748$, $p=.053$, Cramer's $V=.113$]

Cannabis-related experiences in the last 12 months	Male		Female		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Smoked cannabis before midday	85	49.1	50	40.3	135	45.5
Smoked cannabis alone	60	34.9	33	26.6	93	31.4
Had memory problems when smoking	53	40.0	57	46.0	110	37.3
Friends or family advising stopping or reducing	31	17.9	22	17.7	53	17.9
Tried unsuccessfully to stop	38	22.0	16	13.1	54	18.3
Problems because of cannabis use	40	23.0	27	21.8	67	22.5

Table 5.12: Cannabis-related experience in the last 12 months

Summary

Overall, only 19.1% of respondents had tried cannabis, with more males (23.8%) than females (14.7%) having done so. 15.8% of students had used cannabis in the last 12 months and 9% had used cannabis in the last 30 days.

Males generally tried cannabis at a younger age than females did. 6% of males and 4% of females tried cannabis at 12 years or younger. Most students first tried cannabis at 15 years (49%) and 30% first tried it at 14 years old.

Almost half of students (42.4%) perceived obtaining cannabis as either ‘fairly easy’ or ‘very easy’ and male students believed it would be easier to access cannabis than female students did.

Regarding perceived risk of cannabis use, females generally perceived more risk in using cannabis than males: 11% of females compared to 9.3% of males perceived a great risk in using cannabis once or twice; 24.1% of females compared to 18% of males perceived a great risk in using cannabis occasionally; and 54.3% of females compared to 36.6% of males perceived a great risk from smoking cannabis regularly.

Students were asked if they had ever had the possibility to try cannabis without trying it. 26% of males and 22% of females reported this happening once or twice and 14% reported this happening three times or more.

Students were also asked if they had ever used cannabis mixed with tobacco. Over a quarter of respondents (33.2%) who have used cannabis responded that they have used it with tobacco ‘fairly’ or ‘very often’, 25.2% responded that they have rarely done so.

Students were asked if they had used certain types of cannabis in the last 12 months. Most students (17.3%) had used weed/skunk followed by those who answered that they used cannabis resin (5.7%). Only 4.7% (n=90) responded they had used cannabis oil in the last 12 months.

Students were asked about their cannabis related experiences in the last 12 months. Almost half of respondents who had used cannabis during the last 12 months (45.5%) had done so before midday and more than one-third 37.3% had had memory problems when smoking. Females (46%) were more likely than males (40%) to have had memory problems when smoking. Males (22%) were however more likely to have tried unsuccessfully to stop than females were (13.1%).

Factors related to cannabis use

Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status was measured through the highest education level of each respondent's father and mother and perceived wealth of the respondent's family compared to other families in Ireland.

Significant associations were observed between father's education and current cannabis use¹⁰⁵ (Table 5.13, Figure 5.2). Those whose fathers received primary education only were the group with the highest proportion of students who were current cannabis users (26.1%, n=12) and this number fell to 6.9% (n=51) when fathers had completed college or university. Around 90% of those whose father had a secondary or third-level education were not current cannabis users.

Current cannabis use by father's education	Primary school		Some secondary		Completed secondary school		Some college or university		College or university		Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Current Users	12	26.1	40	11.4	27	7.9	15	10.1	51	6.9	15	7.3	163	8.7
Not current users	34	73.9	312	88.6	315	92.1	134	89.9	688	93.1	191	92.7	1703	91.2
Total	46	100.0	352	100.0	342	100.0	149	100.0	739	100.0	206	100.0	1866	100.0

Table 5.13: Current cannabis use by father's education

Figure 5.2: Current cannabis use by father's education

A significant association was found between mother's educational level and a student's current cannabis use¹⁰⁶. 15% (n=3 of 20) of respondents whose mother had primary school education only were current cannabis users compared to 6.6% (n=63) of respondents whose mothers had completed college or university.

Those whose mothers had completed college or university were in the group with the highest proportion of students who had

¹⁰⁵ Current cannabis use by father's education: [χ^2 (6)= 24.738, $p < .001$, Cramer's $V = .115$].

¹⁰⁶ Current cannabis use by mothers education: [χ^2 (6)= 19.319, $p = .004$, Cramer's $V = .102$].

not used cannabis in the last 30 days (Table 5.14, Figure 5.3).

Current cannabis use by mother's education	Primary school		Some secondary		Completed secondary school		Some college or university		College or university		Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	17	85.0	160	85.6	327	88.1	162	91.0	886	93.4	137	93.2	1707	91.2
Current users	3	15.0	27	14.4	44	11.9	16	9.0	63	6.6	10	6.8	164	8.8
Total	20	100.0	187	100.0	371	100.0	178	100.0	949	100.0	147	100.0	1871	100.0

Table 5.14: Current cannabis use by mother's education

Figure 5.3: Current cannabis use by mother's education

Similarly, perceived wealth was significantly associated with current cannabis use¹⁰⁷. Students who perceived their families to be much less well-off were the most likely to be current cannabis users (23.3%, n=7) compared to students who perceived themselves to be about the same (6.7%, n=54) or better off (7%, n=40) than other families in Ireland. (Table 5.15, Figure 5.4).

Current cannabis use by perceived wealth	Very much better off		Much better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		Much less well off		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current users	80	86.0	184	89.3	534	93.0	754	93.3	121	84.0	23	79.7	1696	91.4
Current users	13	14.0	22	10.7	40	7.0	54	6.7	23	16.0	7	23.3	159	8.6
Total	93	100.0	206	100.0	574	100.0	808	100.0	144	100.0	30	100.0	1855	100.0

Table 5.15: Current cannabis use by perceived wealth

¹⁰⁷ Current cannabis use by perceived wealth: [χ^2 (6)= 24.738, p<.001, Cramer's V=.115].

Figure 5:4: Current cannabis use by perceived wealth

School

Absences

Students were asked to report the number of days they had missed class in the last 30 days either due to illness, because they skipped school, or for other reasons.

There was a significant association between lifetime cannabis use and students' absences because of illness¹⁰⁸. Students who were never absent from class because of illness were the least likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (14.6%, n=122), closely followed by students who missed one day (19.8%, n=69). Students who missed 5 or more days of class due to illness were more likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (27.1%, n=38). Current cannabis use was also significantly associated with absence because of illness¹⁰⁹. 13.1% (n=18) of students who had missed 5 days or more of class were current cannabis users compared to 6.2% (n=52) of students who had never missed class because of illness.

Table 5.16, and Figures 5.5 and 5.6 show lifetime and current cannabis use in relation to the number of days of school respondents had been absent from school because of illness in the past 30 days.

¹⁰⁸ Lifetime cannabis use by absence due to illness: [χ^2 (4)= 28.355, p<.001, Cramer's V=.126].

¹⁰⁹ Current cannabis use by absence due to illness: [χ^2 (4)= 15.114, p=.004, Cramer's V=.093].

Absences because of illness												
Lifetime cannabis use	None		1 day		2 days		3 to 4 days		5 days or more		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have not used cannabis	716	85.4	280	80.2	195	74.7	140	74.5	102	72.9	1433	80.7
Have used cannabis	122	14.6	69	19.8	66	25.3	48	25.5	38	27.1	342	19.3
Total	838	100.0	349	100.0	261	100.0	188	100.0	140	100.0	1776	100.0

Absences because of illness												
Current cannabis use	None		1 day		2 days		3 to 4 days		5 days or more		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	781	93.8	307	88.5	228	88.7	169	90.9	119	86.9	1604	91.1
Current users	52	6.2	40	11.5	29	11.3	17	9.1	18	13.1	156	8.9
Total	833	100.0	347	100.0	257	100.0	186	100.0	137	100.0	1770	100.0

Table 5.16: Lifetime and current cannabis use by absences because of illness

Figure 5.5 Lifetime cannabis use by absence due to illness.

Figure 5.6 Current cannabis use by absence due to illness

Similarly, skipping school was significantly associated with lifetime¹¹⁰ and current cannabis use¹¹¹. Students who skipped 5 days or more were the most likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (50%, n=25) and in the last 30 days 34.8% (n=16). Students who had not skipped school in the last month were the least likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (15.1%, n=197) or to be current cannabis users (7%, n=91)

Table 5.17, Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8 show lifetime and current cannabis use in relation to the number of days of school respondents had skipped school.

¹¹⁰ Lifetime cannabis use by skipping school: $[X^2 (3)= 90.198, p<.001, \text{Cramer's } V=.235]$.

¹¹¹ Current cannabis use by skipping school: $[X^2 (3)= 65.865, p<.001, \text{Cramer's } V=.202]$.

Skipping school										
Lifetime cannabis use	None		1 day		3 to 4 days		5 days or more		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have not used cannabis	1104	84.9	154	65.8	30	60.0	25	50.0	1313	80.3
Have used cannabis	197	15.1	80	34.2	20	40.0	25	50.0	322	19.7
Total	1301	100.0	234	100.0	50	100.0	50	100.0	1635	100.0

Skipping school										
Current cannabis use	None		1 day		3 to 4 days		5 days or more		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	1207	93.0	190	82.6	39	79.6	30	65.2	1466	90.3
Current users	91	7.0	40	17.4	10	20.4	16	34.8	157	9.7
Total	1298	100.0	230	100.0	49	100.0	46	100.0	1623	100.0

Table 5.17: Lifetime and current cannabis use by skipping school

Figure 5.7 Lifetime cannabis use by skipping school. Figure 5.8 Current cannabis use by skipping school

Academic attainment was also related to cannabis use with a strong association being found between average grades reported and current and lifetime cannabis use¹¹². Table 5.18 and Figures 5.9 and 5.10 show that those with lower grades were more likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime and in the last 30 days.

19.4% (n=7 out of 36) of students who scored an E or lower had ever used cannabis and 11.1% (n=4 out of 36) were current cannabis users. However, only 14.4% (n=123) of students who scored A or B had ever used cannabis and only 5.9% (n=50) were current cannabis users.

¹¹² Lifetime cannabis use by average grade: [χ^2 (3)= 26.825, p<.001, Cramer's V=.120]. Current cannabis use by skipping school: [χ^2 (3)= 19.275, p<.001, Cramer's V=.103].

Average grade										
Lifetime cannabis use	A and B		C		D		E or lower		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have not used cannabis	731	85.6	595	79.6	152	71.0	29	80.6	1507	81.4
Have used cannabis	123	14.4	153	20.5	62	29.0	7	19.4	345	18.6
Total	854	100.0	748	100.0	214	100.0	36	100.0	1852	100.0

Average grade										
Current cannabis use	A and B		C		D		E or lower		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	800	94.1	664	89.7	180	85.7	32	88.9	1676	91.3
Current users	50	5.9	76	10.3	30	14.3	4	11.1	160	8.7
Total	85	100.0	740	100.0	210	100.0	36	100.0	1836	100.0

Table 5.18: Lifetime and current cannabis use by average grade

Figure 5.9: Lifetime cannabis use by average grade

Figure 5.10: Current cannabis use by average grade

Parenting

Parental monitoring on Saturday nights

Students were asked several questions regarding their relationship with their parents including whether their parents knew where they spend their Saturday nights. Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8 show the likelihood of having tried cannabis correlated by parental monitoring on a Saturday night.

A strong relationship was observed between parental monitoring of Saturday nights and student’s lifetime or current cannabis use¹¹³, with parents knowing where students were, being a protective factor against both. Results presented in Table 5.19 show that more than half of students (50.7%, n=37) whose parents usually don’t know where they are on Saturday nights have tried cannabis in their lifetimes compared to only 11.5% (n=137) who responded that their parents always know where they are on Saturday nights.

Similarly, students who answered that their parents usually don’t know where they are on Saturday nights were more likely to be current cannabis users (38.9%, n=28) than were students whose parents always know where they are (4.6%, n=54).

¹¹³ Lifetime cannabis use by parental monitoring of Saturday nights: [χ^2 (3)= 162.127, p<.001, Cramer’s V=.294]. Current cannabis use by parental monitoring of Saturday nights: [χ^2 (3)= 134.368, p<.001, Cramer’s V=.269].

Parental monitoring of Saturday nights										
Lifetime cannabis use	Know always		Know quite often		Know sometimes		Usually don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have not used cannabis	1055	88.5	345	76.5	93	56.7	36	49.3	1529	81.3
Have used cannabis	137	11.5	106	23.5	71	43.3	37	50.7	351	18.7
Total	1192	100.0	451	100.0	164	100.0	73	100.0	1800	100.0

Parental monitoring of Saturday nights										
Current cannabis use	Know always		Know quite often		Know sometimes		Usually don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	1130	95.4	399	89.1	128	80.1	44	61.1	1701	91.3
Current users	54	4.6	49	10.9	31	19.5	28	38.9	162	8.7
Total	1184	100.0	448	100.0	159	100.0	71	100.0	1863	100.0

Table 5.19: Lifetime and current cannabis use by parental monitoring of Saturday nights

Figure 5.11 Lifetime cannabis use by parental monitoring.

Figure 5.12 Current cannabis use by parental monitoring

Household

Students were asked to indicate whether their household includes their father, step-father, mother, step-mother, brother(s), sister(s), grandparent(s), other relatives(s) or non-relative(s), or whether they live alone. Students whose households included two or more parents, one parent or other people were examined and there was no significant association between lifetime and current cannabis use and household-type¹¹⁴.

Students living in one-parent homes were most likely to have tried cannabis (22.55, n=88) compared to students living with

¹¹⁴ Lifetime cannabis use and household type: [χ^2 (2)=5.149, p=.076, Cramer's V=.052]. Current cannabis use by household type: [χ^2 (2)= 2.830, p=.234, Cramer's V=.039]

two parents (17.8%, n=266). 10.9% (n=42) of students who lived with one parent were current cannabis users, followed by those in two parent homes (8.3%, n=123) but these differences were not statistically significant. Those living in “other” types of household were the most likely to have used cannabis in their lifetime (26.35%, n=5 of 19).

Lifetime cannabis use and household type	Two or more parents		One parent		Other	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Has not tried cannabis	1227	82.2	303	77.5	14	73.7
Has tried cannabis	266	17.8	88	22.5	5	26.3
Total	1493	100.0	391	100.0	19	100.0

Table 5.20: Lifetime cannabis use and household type

Current cannabis use and household type	Two or more parents		One parent		Other	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not a current cannabis user	1358	91.7	344	89.1	18	94.7
Current cannabis user	123	8.3	42	10.9	1	5.3
Total	1481	100.0	386	100.0	19	100.0

Table 5.21: Current cannabis use and household type

Peer Substance Use

Peer cannabis use

Students were asked how many of their friends they would estimate smoke cannabis. Of 1,865 respondents, half of the respondents (50%, n=931) said none of their friends use cannabis, 31% (n=578) said a few of their friends use cannabis, 12% (n=224) said some of their friends use cannabis, 5.7% (n=106) said most of their friends did and only 1.4% (n=26) said all their friends used cannabis.

Peer cannabis use was not significantly associated with lifetime cannabis¹¹⁵ use although figures in Table 5.20 show that students who reported that some of their friends use cannabis were most likely to have tried it (23.1%, n=51) compared to students who reported that none of their friends tried it (16.8%, n=156).

Similarly, no significant association was found between current cannabis use and peer cannabis use¹¹⁶.

¹¹⁵ Lifetime cannabis use by peer cannabis use: $[X^2 (3) = 6.665, p = .083, \text{Cramer's } V = .060]$

¹¹⁶ Current cannabis use by peer cannabis use: $[X^2 (3) = 2.666, p = .446, \text{Cramer's } V = .038]$

Peer cannabis use								
Lifetime cannabis use by peer use	None		A few		Some		Most or All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Have not used cannabis	772	83.2	458	79.8	170	76.9	102	77.9
Have used cannabis	156	16.8	116	20.2	51	23.1	29	22.1
Total	982	100.0	574	100.0	221	100.0	131	100.0

Peer cannabis use								
Current cannabis use by peer use	None		A few		Some		Most or All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Not current Users	842	92.0	517	90.7	197	89.1	116	89.2
Current users	73	8.0	53	9.3	24	10.9	14	10.8
Total	928	100.0	574	100.0	221	100.0	131	100.0

Table 5.20: Lifetime and current cannabis use by peer use

Figure 5.13 Lifetime cannabis use by peer use of cannabis

Figure 5.14 Current cannabis use by peer use of cannabis

Summary

Socioeconomic status was measured through the highest education level of the respondent's fathers and mothers and perceived wealth of respondents.

Significant associations were observed between father's education and current cannabis use. Students whose fathers received primary education only were the group with the highest proportion of students who were current cannabis users (26.1%) and this number fell to 6.9% when fathers had completed college or university. Similarly, 15% (n=3 of 30) of respondents whose mother had primary school education were current cannabis users compared to 6.6% (n=63) of respondents whose mothers had completed college or university.

Students who perceived their families to be less well-off were the most likely to be current cannabis users (23.3%) compared to students who perceived themselves to be about the same (6.7%) or better off (7%) than other families.

School attendance and academic attainment were also significantly associated with lifetime and current cannabis use. Students who were never absent from class due to illness were the least likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (14.6%). Students who missed 5 or more days of class due to illness were more likely to have tried cannabis in their lifetime (27.1%) and 13.1% of these students were current cannabis users compared to 6.2% of students who had never missed class. Similarly, about half of students (50%) who had skipped class on 5 or more days in the last 30 days had used cannabis in their lifetime and 34.8% were current cannabis users. 15.1% who had not skipped class at all had tried cannabis in their lifetimes and 7% were current cannabis users. 19.4% of students who scored an E or lower had ever used cannabis and 11.1% were current cannabis users. However, only 14.4% of students who scored A or B had ever used cannabis and only 5.9% (n=50) were current cannabis users.

Parental monitoring was also associated with cannabis use. More than half of students (50.7%) whose parents usually don't know where they are on Saturday nights have tried cannabis in their lifetimes compared to only 11.5% whose parents always know where they are on Saturday nights. Similarly, those whose parents usually don't know where they are on Saturday nights were more likely to be current cannabis users (n=38.9%,) than were students whose parents always know where they are (4.6%).

DRUG USE

ESPAD
The European School Survey Project
On Alcohol and Other Drugs

Inhalants

Painkillers

Alcohol with pills

Cocaine

Ecstasy

Illicit drug use during lifetime

Substance use by gender

Ecstasy

Cocaine

LSD

Magic mushrooms

Anabolic steroids

Crack

Inhalants

Painkillers

Meth

Age of initiation

14.7 years

Tranquilizers

14.9 years

Ecstasy

14.6 years

Drinking alcohol

14.1 years

Amphetamines

14.0 years

Inhalants

14.7 years

Smoking cigarettes

15.0 years

Cocaine

15.0 years

Alcohol with pills Using e-cigarettes

14.8 years

Using e-cigarettes

15.0 years

Cannabis

15.5 years

Getting drunk

Perceived Access:

Over 51%

perceived difficult access to

Amphetamine, Meth,
tranquilizers, Ecstasy,
Cocaine and Crack

Over 19%

perceived easy access to

cocaine and ecstasy

Perceived Risk:

Over 22%

perceived great risk
from trying ecstasy
and amphetamines

Over 65%

perceived great risk from
trying amphetamines
or ecstasy regularly

6. USE OF OTHER SUBSTANCES

Adolescent substance use and other forms of risk behaviour have proved to be a rapidly changing phenomenon, requiring close monitoring and frequent assessment. Since the inception of ESPAD in 1995, many changes have taken place in the European drug market as well as in youth social, economic and cultural environment. These changes are reflected in temporal changes in the patterns of use of “traditional” substances, legal or illegal, as well as in the emergence of the use of “new” non-controlled substances or different forms of risk behaviour.

ESPAD is committed to provide the best available evidence to support the development of informed policies and actions targeting adolescents to meet the challenges that lie ahead. The 2019 ESPAD survey included items on a range of substances including inhalants, tranquilizers and ecstasy. These questioned concerned lifetime use, use in the past 12 months, the age of the respondents at their first use, perceived ease of access and the perceived risk of trying and using a drug regularly. There was also an item on the use of new substances and the form of these substances, if used.

These substances were examined in relation to factors that might influence students’ behavior including fathers’ education, perceived relative wealth, skipping school, average grade, parental monitoring and peer substance use.

Substance use

Prevalence

Students were asked several questions regarding their use of sixteen substances. These substances included inhalants (glue, aerosol and paint), ecstasy, tranquilizers, cocaine, amphetamines, LSD or some other hallucinogens, ‘magic mushrooms’, anabolic steroids, crack, methamphetamines, heroin, GHB, drugs by injection with a needle (like heroin, cocaine, amphetamine). Students were also asked about their use of alcohol with pills and painkillers to get high.

These questions included lifetime use, use in the past 12 months, age of respondents at first use, perceived ease or difficulty of access, and perceived risk of using these substances.

Students’ responses regarding substance use were also examined in relation to socioeconomic factors that may influence their use such as parental education and perceived wealth, as well as absences from school, average grade, parental monitoring, and peer substance use. Students were also asked about a dummy drug Sprack among the real drugs; 19 (1%) of students reported using the drug and were excluded from this section of the analysis.

The overall prevalence of drug use was low and results are presented in Table 6.1. The drug most frequently used by students was inhalants (10.3%, n=200) followed by the use of painkillers to get high (5.4%, n=105). The next most commonly used drugs were alcohol with pills (4.2%, n=81) followed by cocaine (3.3%, n=63) and ecstasy (2.9%, n=56). The least commonly used drug was heroin (1.2%, n=23) and GHB (1.1%, n=21). Significant differences were observed between male and female students in their lifetime use of ten substances (ecstasy, amphetamines, LSD, anabolic steroids, GHB, cocaine, magic mushrooms, crack, injections and methamphetamines), and no significant gender differences were found in the use of the other substances. More male students (3.8%, n=36) had ever used ecstasy than had female students (2%, n=20)¹¹⁷ and more male students (3.6%, n=34) had ever used LSD than had female students (1.9%, n=19). Use of anabolic steroids (2.7%, n=25)

¹¹⁷ See table 6.1 for chi-square test results

and GHB (1.6%, n=15) was also more common among male students than among female students (1.2%, n=12; 0.6%, n=6 respectively). However, more female students reported using alcohol with pills (4.3%, n=43) and painkillers to get high (6.0%, n=60) than did male students (4.0%, n=38; 4.8%, n=45 respectively) although these differences did not reach statistical significance.

Substance ever used in lifetime	Male		Female		All		Total	Chi-Square Test
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	
Inhalants	105	11.2	95	9.5	200	10.3	1938	$X^2(1) = 1.426, p = .232$
Alcohol with pills	38	4.0	43	4.3	81	4.2	1939	$X^2(1) = .078, p = .781$
Painkillers to get high	45	4.8	60	6.0	105	5.4	1934	$X^2(1) = 1.364, p = .243$ Cramer's V = .027
Ecstasy*	36	3.8	20	2.0	56	2.9	1940	$X^2(1) = 5.749, p = .016$ Cramer's V = .0544
Tranquilizers	27	2.9	24	2.4	51	2.6	1937	$X^2(1) = .428, p = .513$
Cocaine*	43	4.6	20	2.0	63	3.3	1931	$X^2(1) = 10.149, p = .001$
Amphetamines*	27	2.9	13	1.3	40	2.1	1931	$X^2(1) = 5.856, p = .016$ Cramer's V = .055
LSD*	34	3.6	19	1.9	53	2.8	1927	$X^2(1) = 5.366, p = .053$
Magic Mushrooms*	34	3.7	17	1.7	51	2.7	1924	$X^2(1) = 7.008, p = .008$ Cramer's V = .060
Anabolic Steroids*	25	2.7	12	1.2	37	1.9	1935	$X^2(1) = 5.535, p = .019$ Cramer's V = .053
Crack*	23	2.5	12	1.2	35	1.8	1931	$X^2(1) = 4.191, p = .041$
Methamphetamines*	25	2.7	7	0.7	32	1.7	1930	$X^2(1) = 11.354, p = .001$
Injection*	18	1.9	6	0.6	24	1.2	1923	$X^2(1) = 6.906, p = .009$
Heroin	15	1.6	8	0.8	23	1.2	1931	$X^2(1) = 2.597, p = .107$
GHB*	15	1.6	6	0.6	21	1.1	1926	$X^2(1) = 4.512, p = .034$
<i>Sprack</i>	14	1.5	5	0.5	19	1.0	1925	$X^2(1) = 4.906, p = .027$

Table 6.1: Students who reported substance use in lifetime by gender and Chi-square results (*p<.05).

Figure 6.1: Lifetime substance use by gender

Students were also asked if they had used any of these substances in the past 12 months and their responses are presented in Table 6.2. Inhalants were the most used (5.4%, n=105) during the previous 12 months and the least commonly used was methamphetamines (1.5%, n=28). More male students (3.5%, n=33) reported using ecstasy than did female students (1.8%, n=18)*, and although relatively little used, methamphetamines were far more likely to be used by male students than by female students**.

Substance ever used in the past 12 months	Male		Female		All		Total	Chi-Square Test
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Inhalants	52	5.6	53	5.3	105	5.4	1934	$X^2(1) = .056, p = .812$
Ecstasy	33	3.5	18	1.8	51	2.6	1939	$X^2(1) = 5.522, p = .019$ Cramer's V = .053*
Cocaine	34	2.6	20	2.0	54	2.8	1931	$X^2(1) = 4.637, p = .031$
Amphetamines	24	2.6	10	1.0	34	1.8	1930	$X^2(1) = 6.730, p = .009$
Crack	21	2.2	10	1.0	31	1.6	1930	$X^2(1) = 4.621, p = .032$
Methamphetamines	22	2.3	6	0.6	28	1.5	1930	$X^2(1) = 10.252, p = .001^{**}$
Heroin	23	2.5	12	1.2	35	1.8	1931	$X^2(1) = 4.192, p = .041$

Table 6.2: Students who reported substance use in the past 12 months by gender and Chi-square results.

Age of Initiation

Respondents were asked at what age they started using six substances: inhalants, alcohol with pills, ecstasy, tranquilisers or sedatives without a prescription, cocaine or crack, and amphetamines or methamphetamines. Responses presented in Table 6.3 show that the majority of the respondents who used one of these substances first tried the substance when they were 14 years or older. Of the 152 students who provided the age when they first used inhalants, 83 were aged 14 years or older and 35 were 11 years or younger. Similarly, out of 84 students who had used alcohol with pills, 64 were 14 years or older and

only 7 were below 12 years. 21 out of 36 students who reported using amphetamines were 14 years or older, 8 were 12 or 13 years, and 7 were below 12 years.

Substance	11 or younger		12 or 13		14 or older		Total used		Total responded
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants	35	23.0	34	22.4	83	54.6	152	100.0	1949
Alcohol with pills	7	8.3	13	15.5	64	76.2	84	100.0	1949
Ecstasy	6	10.3	11	19	41	70.7	58	100.0	1949
Tranquilizers	5	9.8	9	17.7	37	72.7	51	100.0	1949
Cocaine or crack	6	9.1	8	12.1	52	78.8	66	100.0	1949
Amphetamines or Meth	7	19.4	8	22.2	21	58.3	36	100.0	1949

Table 6.3: Age of first use of six substances

The mean age of initiation and standard error for these substances as well as e-cigarette use, daily smoking, drinking alcohol and getting drunk, are shown in Table 6.4 and Figure 6.2. Mean age of initiation of drinking alcohol, smoking, daily smoking, e-cigarette use, and use of cannabis, tranquilisers, alcohol with pills, ecstasy and cocaine is approximately 15 years old, with use of inhalants and amphetamines beginning at a slightly younger age. The age of initiation of inhalants was the youngest reported by respondents at 14 years.

Substance	Mean	Standard Error
Drink alcohol	14.6	0.05
Get drunk	15.5	0.04
Smoking	14.7	0.06
Daily smoking	14.9	0.14
E-cigs	14.8	0.04
Cannabis	15.3	0.06
Inhalants	14.0	0.16
Tranquilizers	14.8	0.26
Alcohol with pills	15.0	0.18
Ecstasy	14.9	0.23
Cocaine/Crack	15.0	0.21
Amphetamines/Meth.	14.1	0.37

Table 6.4: Mean age of initiation and standard error for using various substances

Figure 6.2: Mean age of initiation of use of alcohol, drunkenness, smoking, e-cigarette use, cannabis and six other substances

Perceived Access

Students were asked how difficult they thought it would be to get 6 substances (amphetamines, meth, tranquilizers, ecstasy, cocaine and crack) and responses are presented in Table 6.5. About one in three students answered that it would be impossible to get these substances. 36% (n=694) responded that it would be impossible to get meth and 35.9% (n=681) said it would be impossible to get amphetamines. The substances with the highest proportion of students who answered ‘very easy’ were cocaine (7.2%, n=139) followed by ecstasy (6%, n=115), and ecstasy and cocaine also had the lowest numbers of students reporting that they thought it would be impossible to get (30.1%, n=586; 30.5%, n=590 respectively).

Perceived Access	Impossible		Very difficult		Fairly difficult		Fairly easy		Very easy		Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Amphetamine	681	35.9	427	22.1	240	12.4	136	7.0	51	2.6	396	20.5	1928	100.0
Meth	694	36.0	435	22.6	236	12.2	122	6.3	47	2.4	394	20.4	1927	100.0
Tranquilizers	644	33.4	431	22.4	281	14.6	166	8.6	68	3.5	337	17.5	1927	100.0
Ecstasy	586	30.1	404	21.0	287	14.9	259	13.4	115	6.0	276	14.3	1927	100.0
Cocaine	590	30.5	397	20.4	279	14.3	283	14.5	139	7.2	247	12.8	1935	100.0
Crack	655	33.9	418	21.6	271	14.0	193	10.0	99	5.1	296	15.3	1932	100.0

Table 6.5: Perceived access of six substances

Figure 6.4: Perceived access to six substances

Perceived Risk

Students were asked how much people risk harming themselves (physically or in other ways) by trying ecstasy and amphetamines and taking these substances regularly. Almost half of students believed that there was great risk from trying ecstasy (22%, n=422), while 9.5% (n=183) reported that there was no risk from trying ecstasy. 63.7% (1222) of respondents thought that there was great risk in trying ecstasy regularly, 19% (n=364) thought there was moderate risk and 4% (n=77) believed that there was no risk. Almost a third of respondents believed that there was a great risk from trying amphetamines (30.2%, n=588), and almost 30% answered moderate risk (28.1%, n=548). Around 6.8% (n=131) perceived that there was no risk from trying amphetamines. Similarly, 61.7% (n=1179) of respondents perceived that there was great risk from trying amphetamines regularly, while 3.8% (n=73) of respondents perceived no risk. 16.4% (314) responded ‘don’t know’ to perceived risk in trying amphetamines regularly. Regular use was perceived, therefore, as carrying much greater risk than trying a substance.

Perceived Risk of Substance	No risk		Slight risk		Moderate risk		Great risk		Don't know		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Try ecstasy	183	9.5	546	28.5	601	31.3	422	22.0	167	8.7	1919	100.0
Ecstasy regularly	77	4.0	86	4.5	364	19.0	1222	63.7	170	8.9	1919	100.0
Try amphetamines	131	6.8	344	28.6	548	28.1	588	30.2	305	15.9	1919	100.0
Amphetamines regularly	73	3.8	72	3.8	273	14.3	1179	61.7	314	16.4	1919	100.0

Table 6.6: Perceived risk of substance use.

Figure 6.5: Perceived risk of using ecstasy and amphetamine

New Substances (Legal High)

New psychoactive substances (NPS) were defined as ‘substances that imitate the effects of illicit drugs such as cannabis or ecstasy and are sometimes called “legal highs”, “ethnobotanicals” or “research chemicals” and can come in different forms (herbal mixtures, powders, crystals or tablets)’. Students were asked if they had ever used new substances that imitate the effects of illicit drugs (such as cannabis or ecstasy) as well as the type of substance that they used. 4.7% (n=91) responded that they had used these substances and 92.7% (1797) reported that they had not. Significant differences were observed for lifetime use by gender¹¹⁸ as more male students reported ever using legal highs (6.6%, n=62) than did female students (2.9%, n=29).

Ever used legal highs	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	62	6.6	29	2.9	91	4.7
No	846	90.3	951	95.0	1797	92.7
Don't know	29	3.1	21	2.1	50	2.6
Total	937	100.0	1001	100.0	1938	100.0

Table 6.7: Legal high use by gender

Students were also asked about the appearance/form of the new substances that they had used in the previous 12 months and that they could select all that apply. The most common type of legal high used was herbal smoking mixtures (5.8%, n=111), closely followed by powder/tablet form of legal highs which was used by 3.9% (n=75) of students. 3.6% (n=69) of students said that they had used a liquid form of legal highs and 3.9% (n=75) said that they used legal highs in a form other than herbal, powder/table, or liquid. There were significant differences in the type of legal high used by gender (see Table 6.8). Male students (8.3%, n=77) reported significantly higher use of herbal smoking mixtures than did female students (3.4%, n=34).

¹¹⁸Legal use high by gender: [χ^2 (3)= 21.109, $p < .001$, Cramer's $V = .104$]

Type of legal high used	Male		Female		All		Chi-Square Test
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Herbal smoking mixtures	77	8.3	34	3.4	111	5.8	$X^2(1) = 20.803, p < .001$
Powder/tablet form	52	5.6	23	2.3	75	3.9	$X^2(1) = 13.736, p < .001$
Liquid form	52	5.6	17	1.7	69	3.6	$X^2(1) = 20.882, p < .001$
Other form	56	6.0	19	1.9	75	3.9	$X^2(1) = 21.613, p < .001$ Cramer's $V = .106$

Table 6.8: Form of legal high by gender

Students were asked about the number of times they had used synthetic cannabinoids in their life with the response categories '0', '1-2', '3 or more'. Prevalence of any use of synthetic cannabinoids was based on intake on at least one occasion and responses were recoded into 'yes' or 'no' to examine gender differences. Noticeable gender differences were found for synthetic cannabinoid use and results presented in Table 6.9¹¹⁹. More male students (2.5%, n=23) than female students (1%, n=10) reported using synthetic cannabinoids in their lifetime.

Lifetime use of synthetic cannabinoids	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	23	2.5	10	1.0	33	1.7
No	913	97.5	987	99.0	1990	98.3
Total	936	100.0	997	100.0	1933	100.0

Table 6.9: Lifetime use of synthetic cannabinoids by gender

Similarly, students were asked about the number of times they had used synthetic cathinone in their lifetime and results are presented in Table 6.8. No significant gender differences¹²⁰ were found for synthetic cathinone use although males (2.7%, n=25) had a slightly higher prevalence of use than females (2.3%, n=23) had for synthetic cathinone.

Lifetime use of synthetic cathinone	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Yes	25	2.7	23	2.3	48	2.5
No	908	97.3	975	97.7	1883	97.5
Total	933	100.0	998	100.0	1931	100.0

Table 6.10: Lifetime use of synthetic cathinone by gender

Energy Drinks

Lifetime consumption of energy drinks (excluding sports drinks)

Students were asked on how many occasions in their lifetimes they had consumed energy drinks (e.g. red bull/monster energy) in their lifetime. Responses presented in Table 6.11 show that only 27% (n=489) of students had never used energy drinks in their lifetime. While 73% (n=1324) had used energy drinks in their lifetime. Among this category of students, majority responded that they had used energy drinks more than 40 times in their lifetime (18.1%, n=327). There were no

¹¹⁹ Lifetime synthetic cannabinoid use: [$X^2(1) = 6.084, p = .014, \text{Cramer's } V = .561$]

¹²⁰ Lifetime synthetic cathinone use: [$X^2(1) = .280, p = .597$]

significant gender differences in lifetime consumption of energy drinks among students¹²¹.

Lifetime consumption of energy drinks* *number of occasions	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	233	26.4	256	27.5	489	27.0
Once or Twice	138	15.6	136	14.6	274	15.1
3 to 5 times	99	11.2	101	10.8	200	11.0
6 to 9 times	70	8.0	74	7.9	144	7.9
10 to 19 times	100	11.4	95	10.2	196	10.8
20 to 39 times	89	10.1	94	10.1	183	10.1
40 times or more	152	17.3	176	18.9	327	18.1
Total	881	100.0	932	100.0	1813	100.0

Table 6.11: Lifetime energy drinks consumption

The last 12 months

Students were asked about their consumption of energy drinks during the last 12 months (Table 6.12). 60.9% (n=1092) responded that they had consumed energy drinks in the last 12 months with 7.2% (n=130) reporting that they had consumed energy drinks over 40 times. There were significant gender differences in consumption of energy drinks in the last 12 months¹²². More male students (61.1%, n=532) than female students (60.7%, n=560) reported consuming energy drinks in the last 12 months.

Use of energy drinks in the last 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	339	38.9	363	39.3	702	39.1
Once or twice	157	18.0	140	15.1	297	16.6
3 to 5 times	90	10.3	95	10.3	185	10.3
6 to 9 times	82	9.4	85	9.2	167	9.3
10 to 19 times	83	9.5	103	11.2	186	10.4
20 to 39 times	61	7.0	66	7.2	127	7.1
40 times or more	59	6.8	71	7.7	130	7.2
Total	871	100.0	923	100.0	1794	100.0

Table 6.12: Energy drinks consumption on the last 12 months

The last 30 days

As can be seen in Table 6.13, only 40.1% (n=721) reported that they had consumed energy drinks in the last 30 days compared to 59.9% (n=1079) who had not had energy drinks in the last 30 days. Again, more male students 44.4% (n=384) than female students (40.1%, n=337) reported consuming energy drinks in the last 30 days¹²³

¹²¹ Lifetime use of energy drinks [$\chi^2(6)=1.815$, $p=.934$, Cramer's $V=.032$]

¹²² Use of energy drinks, last 12 months: [$\chi^2(6)=29.952$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.129$]

¹²³ Use of energy drinks, last 30 days: [$\chi^2(6)=31.961$, $p<.001$, Cramer's $V=.133$]

Use of energy drinks in the last 30 days	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	480	55.6	599	64.0	1079	59.9
Once or twice	137	15.9	162	17.3	299	16.6
3 to 5 times	88	10.2	74	7.9	162	9.0
6 to 9 times	66	7.6	45	4.8	111	6.2
10 to 19 times	46	5.3	34	3.6	80	4.4
20 to 39 times	22	2.5	16	1.7	38	2.1
40 times or more	25	2.9	6	0.6	31	1.7
Total	864	100.0	936	100.0	1800	100.0

Table 6.13: Energy drinks consumption on the last 30 days

Summary

Students were asked several questions regarding their use of sixteen substances including a ‘dummy’ drug, Sprack. The overall prevalence of drug use was low. Inhalants were by far the most commonly used substance at 10.3%, followed by the use of painkillers to get high at 5.4%. The next most commonly used drugs were alcohol with pills (4.2%) followed by cocaine (3.3%) and Ecstasy (2.9%). The least commonly used drug was heroin (1.2%) and GHB (1.1%). There were significant differences between male and female students in their lifetime use of ten substances (ecstasy, amphetamines, LSD, anabolic steroids, GHB, cocaine, magic mushrooms, crack, injections and methamphetamines) and no significant differences were found in the use of the other substances.

Most respondents who used inhalants, alcohol with pills, ecstasy, tranquilizers or sedatives without a prescription, cocaine or crack and amphetamines or methamphetamines first tried the substance when they were 14 years or older. Mean age of initiation of drinking alcohol, smoking, daily smoking, using e-cigarettes, cannabis, tranquilizers, alcohol with pills, ecstasy and cocaine is approximately 15 years old, with using inhalants and amphetamines beginning at a slightly younger age. The age of initiation of inhalants was the youngest at 14 years.

Almost half of students perceived that it would be impossible to get each of six substances, ranging from 36% for methamphetamines and 35.9% for amphetamines. 7.2% and 6% of respondents responded that it would be ‘very easy’ to obtain cocaine and ecstasy respectively. Cocaine had the lowest number of students who thought it would be impossible to get (30.1%).

Almost half of students perceived a great risk from trying ecstasy (22%) and amphetamines (30.2%) compared to students who perceived no risk in trying ecstasy (9.5%) and amphetamines (6.8%) Similarly, more than half of students perceived a great risk from trying ecstasy (63.7%) and amphetamines (61.7%) regularly compared to students who believed there was no risk in trying ecstasy (4%) and amphetamines (3.8%) regularly.

Only 4.7% of students had used legal highs and more male students (6.6%) than female students (2.9%) had used legal highs. The most common type of legal high used was herbal smoking mixtures (5.8%) closely followed by powder/tablet form of legal highs (3.9%).

Factors related to substance use

Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status was measured via respondents' parental educational level and perceived wealth of the family compared to the families of respondents' peers.

Significant associations were found between father's education¹²⁴ and the use of heroin (see Table 6.14) with 16.1% of students (3 of 21) whose father received primary level education or less having ever used heroin, compared to 1.1% of those whose father received some third-level education (n=10). This pattern, although weaker, was also found when examining use of inhalants, alcohol with pills, cocaine and was somewhat evident concerning crack and painkiller use, although the relationship with these substances was not significant. Respondents whose fathers had reached a higher level of education were less likely to have used heroin, inhalants, painkillers to get high, and alcohol with pills.

Substance ever used in lifetime	Primary or less		Secondary		Third level		Don't know		Total		Chi-Square Test
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants	8	16.7	80	11.4	81	9.0	19	7.9	188	9.9	X ² (3) =6.109, p=.106, Cramer's V=.057
Ecstasy	3	6.1	25	3.6	20	2.2	4	1.7	52	2.8	X ² (3) =5.781, p=.123 Cramer's V= .055
Alcohol with pills	5	10.2	33	4.7	34	3.7	8	3.3	80	4.2	X ² (3) =5.616, p=.132, Cramer's V=.054
Painkillers to get high	4	8.1	41	5.9	45	5.0	11	4.6	101	5.7	X ² (3) =1.562, p=.668, Cramer's V=.028
Tranquilizers	2	4.1	19	2.7	25	2.8	5	2.1	51	2.7	X ² (3) =.744, p=.863, Cramer's V=.019
Cocaine	3	6.1	28	4.0	23	2.6	7	2.9	61	3.3	X ² (3) =3.947, p=.267, Cramer's V=.045
Amphetamines	2	4.1	16	2.3	17	1.9	4	1.7	39	2.1	X ² (3) =1.455, p=.069, Cramer's V= .028
Crack	3	6.1	11	1.6	14	1.6	5	2.1	33	1.8	X ² (3) =5.875, p=.118, Cramer's V=.055
Methamphetamines	2	4.1	14	2.0	9	1.0	6	2.5	31	1.7	X ² (3) =5.663, p=.129, Cramer's V=.055
Heroin	3	6.1	6	0.9	10	1.1	2	0.8	21	1.1	X ² (3) =11.708, p=.008 Cramer's V=.078

Table 6.14: Lifetime use of substances by Fathers education (*p<.05)

Perceived wealth

Students were also asked about their perceived wealth of their family (Table 6.15, Figure 6.6). Perceived wealth was significantly associated with use of inhalants, ecstasy, and painkillers. The strongest association was observed between perceived wealth and lifetime ecstasy use. Those who answered '(very) much less well off' were the most likely to report

¹²⁴ A weaker association was found between these substances and mothers education; Inhalants [X² (6)=14.156, p=.030, Cramer's V=.087], Ecstasy [X² (6)=4.892, p=.558], alcohol with pills [X² (6)=8.888, p=.180], painkillers [X² (6)=17.961, p=.006, Cramer's V=.098], tranquilizers [X² (6)=5.999 p=.423] Cocaine [X² (6)=8.337, p=.214], Amphetamines [X² (6)=10.090, p=.121], crack [X² (6)=19.534 ,p=.003, Cramer's V=.102], Meth [X² (6)=24.275, p<.001, Cramer's V=.114], Heroin [X² (6)=20.801, p=.002, Cramer's V=.105]

using ecstasy (9.7%, n=3), followed by those who answered, ‘very much better off’ (9.4%, n=9). Those who perceived themselves to be ‘better off’ (1.25%, n=7) and ‘about the same’ (2.2%, n=18) had the lowest prevalence of lifetime ecstasy use. A similar pattern was observed for lifetime use of painkillers in order to get high Around 10% (n=3) of those who were ‘(very) much less well off’ and 7.4% (n=7) of those who were ‘very much better off’ had used painkillers in their lifetime. Only 3.3% (n=19) of those who were ‘better off’ had used painkillers in their lifetime.

Substance ever used in lifetime	Very much better off		Much better off		Better off		About the same		Less well off		(Very) much less well off		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants*	9	9.5	19	9.0	60	10.4	80	9.3	15	10.3	6	29.0	192	10.2	X ² (5)=12.514, p=.028. Cramer's V=.082
Ecstasy*	9	9.4	7	3.3	7	1.2	18	2.2	8	5.5	3	9.7	52	2.8	X ² (5)=31.425, p<.001 Cramer's V=.129
Alcohol with pills	6	6.3	11	5.2	14	2.4	39	4.8	8	5.5	2	6.5	80	4.3	X ² (5)=7.740, p=.171. Cramer's V=.064
Painkillers*	7	7.4	12	5.7	19	3.3	44	5.4	15	10.3	3	10.0	100	5.3	X ² (5)=14.010, p=.016. Cramer's V=.086
Tranquilizers	3	3.2	8	3.8	12	2.1	19	2.3	7	4.8	2	6.5	51	2.7	X ² (5)=6.373, p=.272. Cramer's V=.058

Table 6.15: Lifetime use of substances by perceived wealth (*p<.05)

Figure 6.6: Use of inhalants, ecstasy and painkillers by perceived relative wealth

School

Skipping school

School attendance and academic attainment were examined with regard to lifetime substance use. Students were asked the number of days they had skipped class in the last 30 days. Skipping school was strongly associated with lifetime use of inhalants, ecstasy, alcohol with pills, painkillers, and tranquilizer use (see Table 6.16). Students who had skipped more than

three days of class (17.4%, n=17) and 1-2 days (19.7%, n=46) in the past 30 days had ever used inhalants while only 8.4% (n=110) of students who had not skipped any days in the past 30 days had used inhalants. Similarly, 20% (n=20) of students who had skipped class on three or more days had used alcohol with pills compared with only 2.6% (n=34) of those who had not skipped class in the past 30 days. Students who had skipped class on three or more days were more likely to have used ecstasy, painkillers and tranquilizers in their lifetime than were students who had not skipped any class.

Substance ever used in lifetime	None		1-2 days		3+ days		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants	110	8.4	46	19.7	17	17.4	173	10.6	$X^2(2)=31.420, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.139$
Ecstasy	23	1.8	14	5.0	13	13.0	50	3.1	$X^2(2)=47.485, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.170$
Alcohol with pills	34	2.6	17	7.3	20	20.0	71	4.3	$X^2(2)=73.337, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.212$
Painkillers	49	3.8	26	11.1	19	19.2	94	5.8	$X^2(2)=54.773, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.183$
Tranquilizers	27	2.1	13	5.7	8	8.1	48	2.9	$X^2(2)=18.228, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.106$

Table 6.16 Lifetime use of substances by skipping school in the last 30 days

Figure 6.7: Substance use by skipping school

Absence due to illness

Absence due to illness was also significantly associated with lifetime use of inhalants, ecstasy, alcohol with pills, painkillers and tranquilizers (Table 6.17).

Students who missed school on 3 or more days in the last month due to illness (13.1%, n=43) and 1-2 days (13.7%, n=84) were the most likely to have ever tried inhalants and students who had not missed any time in school due to illness were the least likely (7.2%, n=60). Similarly, students who missed three or more days of school in the last month due to illness were the most likely to have used alcohol with pills in the last 30 days (9.2%, n=30). Students who had not missed any day due to illness were the least likely to have used alcohol with pills. Similar results were observed for lifetime use of ecstasy, painkillers and tranquilizers

Substance ever used in lifetime	None		1-2 days		3+ days		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants*	60	7.2	84	13.7	43	13.1	187	10.5	$X^2(2)=19.114, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.104$
Ecstasy*	14	1.8	26	4.2	10	3.1	50	2.8	$X^2(2)=8.673, p=.013$. Cramer's $V=.070$
Alcohol with pills*	16	1.9	42	6.9	17	5.2	75	4.2	$X^2(2)=22.404, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.112$
Painkillers *	26	3.1	43	7.0	30	9.2	99	5.6	$X^2(2)=20.354, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.107$
Tranquilizers*	10	1.2	29	4.7	11	3.4	50	2.8	$X^2(2)=16.700, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.097$

Table 6.17: Lifetime use of substances by absence due to illness in the last 30 days

Average grade

Students were asked about their average grade at the end of the previous term. Again, school grade was significantly associated with lifetime use of inhalants, ecstasy, alcohol with pills, and painkillers in order to get high. No significant association was observed for average grade and lifetime use of tranquilizers (Table 6.18). 16.7% (n=6) of students who said that mostly E or lower best described their average grade had used ecstasy in their lifetime. However, only 1.2% of students who said that mostly A or B described their average grade had ever used ecstasy. Similarly, students who reported attaining a lower grade were more likely to report having used inhalants, painkillers, alcohol with pills, and tranquilizers.

Substance ever used in lifetime	A-B		C		D		E or lower		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Inhalants	75	8.8	78	10.4	33	15.4	4	11.8	190	10.2	$X^2(3)=8.250, p=.041$. Cramer's $V=.067$
Ecstasy	10	1.2	27	3.6	8	3.7	6	16.7	51	2.7	$X^2(3)=36.866, p<.001$. Cramer's $V=.141$
Alcohol with pills	25	2.9	34	4.5	11	5.1	4	11.1	74	4.0	$X^2(3)=8.601, p=.035$. Cramer's $V=.068$
Painkillers	32	3.7	41	5.5	20	9.4	4	11.1	97	5.2	$X^2(3)=13.844, p=.003$. Cramer's $V=.086$
Tranquilizers	16	1.9	24	3.2	7	3.3	2	5.7	49	2.6	$X^2(3)=4.4, p=.226$. Cramer's $V=.048$

Table 6.18: Lifetime use of substances by average school grade

Figure 6.8: Substance use by average grade ($p < .05$)

Parental Monitoring

Students were asked if their parents know where they spend Saturday nights ('know always', 'know quite often', 'know sometimes', 'usually don't know'). Significant association was observed between parental monitoring of Saturday nights and lifetime use of cocaine, amphetamines, ecstasy, tranquilizers, inhalants, alcohol with pills, and painkillers (see Table 6.19).

While 17.8% ($n=13$) of students whose parents 'usually don't know' where they are on Saturday nights have used cocaine in their lifetime, only 1.2% ($n=14$) of students whose parents 'always know' where they are have done so. 10.9% ($n=8$) of students who answered, 'usually don't know' have used amphetamines, compared to 1.1% ($n=13$) of students who answered 'always'.

Similarly, 23% ($n=17$) of those whose parents 'usually don't know' where they spend Saturday nights reported using painkillers while 2.4% ($n=29$) of those whose parents 'always know' where they are have done so. Similar results were observed for lifetime use of ecstasy, tranquilizers, and alcohol with pills.

Parental monitoring of Saturday nights											
Substance used in lifetime	Know always		Know quite often		Know sometimes		Usually don't know		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Cocaine*	14	1.2	16	3.5	16	9.8	13	17.8	59	3.1	$X^2(3) = 90.383$, $p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .219$
Amphetamines*	13	1.1	6	1.3	10	6.1	8	10.9	37	1.9	$X^2(3) = 50.661$, $p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .164$
Ecstasy*	14	1.2	12	2.6	15	9.1	11	14.9	52	2.8	$X^2(3) = 76.330$, $p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .201$
Tranquilizers*	18	1.5	11	2.4	13	7.9	8	10.8	50	2.7	$X^2(3) = 42.660$, $p < .001$. Cramer's $V = .150$

Inhalants*	71	6.0	73	16.2	35	21.2	14	19.2	193	10.3	X ² (3)= 68.842, p<.001. Cramer's V=.191
Alcohol with pills*	19	1.6	26	5.7	20	12.1	13	17.6	78	4.1	X ² (3)=82.651, p<.001. Cramer's V=.209
Painkillers*	29	2.4	34	7.5	19	11.5	17	23.3	99	5.3	X ² (3)=84.419, p<.001. Cramer's V=.212
Total	1185	100.0	448	100.0	160	100.0	66	100.0	1885	100.0	

Table 6.19: Lifetime substance use by parental monitoring of Saturday nights

Figure 6.9: Substance use by parental monitoring of Saturday nights

Household members

Students were asked to report who lived in their household with them and their answers were simplified to provide three categories of responsible adult; two or more parents (including stepparents), one parent, or other people (including siblings, grandparents, relatives, non-relatives). Household composition was examined in relation to substance use and a significant relationship between household composition and lifetime use of alcohol with pills and painkillers was found (see Table 6.20). 17.7% (n=3 of 17) of students who did not live with any parents had used alcohol with pills in their lifetime while only 3.3% of those who lived with two parents had done so (n=49). Again, 17.7% (n=3 of 17) of students who did not live with any parents had used painkillers to get high while only 4.6% (n=67) of those who lived with two parents had done so.

A similar pattern was seen for use of other substances but there were only 17 students who did not live with either parent, few students have used these substances and the Chi-square tests did not reach significance.

Substance used in lifetime	Two parents		One parent		Other people		Total		Chi-Square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Cocaine	35	2.4	10	2.6	1	6.3	46	2.5	$X^2(2)=1.044, p=.593$. Cramer's V=.024
Amphetamines	18	1.2	5	1.3	0	0.0	23	1.2	$X^2(2)=.234, p=.890$. Cramer's V=.011
Ecstasy	30	2.0	9	2.4	0	0.0	39	2.1	$X^2(2)=.525, p=.769$. Cramer's V=.017
Tranquilizers	28	1.9	9	2.4	1	5.9	38	2.0	$X^2(2)=1.610, p=.447$. Cramer's V=.029
Inhalants	142	9.6	37	9.4	3	17.7	182	9.7	$X^2(2)=1.229, p=.541$. Cramer's V=.026
Alcohol with pills*	49	3.3	13	3.4	3	17.7	65	3.5	$X^2(2)=10.317, p=.006$. Cramer's V=.074
Painkillers*	67	4.6	20	5.3	3	17.7	90	4.8	$X^2(2)=6.514, p=.039$. Cramer's V=.212
Total	1478	100.0	381	100.0	17	100.0	1876	100.0	

Table 6.20: Lifetime substance use by household composition

Figure 6.10: Substance use by household composition

Substance use of peers

Students were asked how many of their friends use inhalants, tranquilizers and ecstasy and the response categories were 'none', 'a few', 'some', 'most' or 'all'. The majority of students did not have any friends who used inhalants, tranquilizers and ecstasy (between 84.4% and 87.8%), and a very small minority reported that all of their friends used these substances (see Table 6.21). A noteworthy minority reported that a few (between 167 and 222) or some (between 33 and 50) of their friends use inhalants, tranquilizers and ecstasy. More students had friends who used inhalants than the other two substances.

Substance ever used in lifetime	None		A few		Some		Most		All		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Inhalants	1592	85.1	200	10.7	50	2.7	15	0.8	14	0.8	1871	100.0
Ecstasy	1576	84.4	222	11.9	44	2.4	13	0.7	13	0.7	1868	100.0
Tranquilizers	1639	87.8	167	9.0	33	1.8	14	0.8	13	0.7	1866	100.0

Table 6.21: Peer use of inhalants, ecstasy and tranquilizers

Figure 6.11: Peer use of inhalants, ecstasy and tranquilizers

Peer use of inhalants, ecstasy and tranquilizers was examined in relation to lifetime substance use. Due to low responses in some categories, peer use was simplified into three categories for analysis- ‘none’, ‘a few’ or ‘some, most or all’ and there were moderately strong associations between peer use of ecstasy, inhalants and tranquilizers and respondents’ use of inhalants (see Table 6.22).

The strongest significant relationship was between peer use of ecstasy and use of inhalants. 18.8% (n=13) of students who reported some, most or all of their friends take ecstasy have ever used inhalants, while 9.1% (n=20) of those with a few friends who take ecstasy have used inhalants and 9.8% (n=154) students who do not have any friends who take ecstasy have used inhalants.

Peer use of inhalants was also related to respondents’ use of tranquilizers, inhalants and alcohol with pills (Table 6.17). 18% (n=14) of students who reported that some, most or all of their friends use inhalants have used inhalants themselves and 11.6% (n=23) of those who have a few friends who use inhalants have ever used inhalants. 9.5% (n=150) of students whose friends do not use inhalants have used inhalants themselves. Similar results were observed for peer use of inhalants and respondents’ use of tranquilizers, and alcohol with pills.

Peer use of tranquilizers was strongly related to respondents’ use of ecstasy. 8.5% (n=5) of those who reported some, most or all of their friends use tranquilizers have used ecstasy (see Table 6.22), while 2.5% (n=40) of those who have no friends using tranquilizers have used ecstasy.

Peer use of ecstasy									
Substance used in lifetime	None		A few		Some, most or all		Total		Chi-square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Ecstasy	43	2.7	4	1.8	5	7.3	52	2.8	X ² (2)= 5.843, p=.054 Cramer's V=.056
Tranquilizers	36	2.4	5	2.3	2	2.9	45	2.4	X ² (2)=.090, p=.956. Cramer's V=.007
Inhalants*	154	9.8	20	9.1	13	18.8	187	10.1	X ² (2)= 6.242, p=.044. Cramer's V=.058
Alcohol with pills	60	3.0	11	5.0	4	5.8	75	4.0	X ² (2)= 1.224, p=.542. Cramer's V=.026
Painkillers	84	5.4	13	5.9	3	4.4	100	5.4	X ² (2)= .267, p=.875. Cramer's V=.012
Total	1545	84.4	218	11.9	67	3.7	1830	100.9	X ² (2)= 1.044, p=.593. Cramer's V=.024
Peer use of inhalants									
Substance used in lifetime	None		A few		Some, most or all		Total		Chi-square
	N	%	N	N	%	%	N	%	
Ecstasy	40	2.5	7	3.5	5	6.4	52	2.8	X ² (2)= 4.583, p=.101 Cramer's V=.050
Tranquilizers*	33	2.1	10	5.0	3	3.9	46	2.5	X ² (2)=6.700, p=.030 Cramer's V=.061
Inhalants*	150	9.5	23	11.6	14	18.0	187	10.0	X ² (2)= 6.506, p=.044. Cramer's V=.058
Alcohol with pills*	56	3.5	14	7.0	5	6.4	75	4.0	X ² (2)= 6.736, p=.039. Cramer's V=.059
Painkillers	82	5.2	14	7.0	4	5.2	100	5.4	X ² (2)=1.201, p=.549. Cramer's V=.025
Total	1561	85.2	196	10.7	76	4.2	1883	100.0	
Peer use of tranquilizers									
Substance used in lifetime	None		A few		Some, most or all		Total		Chi-square
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Ecstasy*	40	2.5	6	3.6	5	8.5	51	2.7	X ² (2)= 8.270, p=.016 Cramer's V=.067
Tranquilizers	36	2.2	7	4.2	2	3.4	45	2.4	X ² (2)=2.818, p=.244. Cramer's V=.039
Inhalants	115	9.5	23	13.8	9	15.3	187	10.1	X ² (2)= 4.886, p=.091. Cramer's V=.051
Alcohol with pills	64	3.9	6	3.6	4	6.8	74	4.0	X ² (2)= 1.291, p=.524. Cramer's V=.026
Painkillers	89	5.5	7	4.3	3	5.1	99	5.3	X ² (2)= .424, p=.809. Cramer's V=.015
Total	1608	87.9	164	9.0	57	3.1	1829	100.0	

Table 6.22: Peer use of ecstasy, inhalants and tranquilizers by lifetime substance use

Summary

Father's education was associated with lifetime use of alcohol with pills, painkillers to get high, tranquilizers, cocaine and amphetamines. The strongest relationship was observed between father's education and lifetime use of tranquilizers; 4.1% of students whose father received primary level education only had used tranquilizers, but 2.8% of students whose father received some third-level education had used tranquilizers.

Perceived wealth was significantly associated with lifetime use of inhalants, ecstasy and painkillers. The strongest association was observed between perceived wealth and lifetime ecstasy use. Those who answered '(very) much less well off' (9.7%) and '(very) much better off' (9.4%). Those who perceived themselves to be 'better off' (1.25%) and 'about the same' (2.2%) had the lowest prevalence of lifetime ecstasy use.

Skipping school was strongly associated with lifetime inhalants, ecstasy, alcohol with pills, painkillers and tranquilizer use. Students who skipped more than three days of class (17.4%) and 1-2 days (19.7%) had ever used inhalants while only 8.4% of students who had not skipped any day in the past 30 days had used inhalants. Similarly, 20% of students who skipped class on three or more days had used alcohol with pills compared with only 2.6% of those who had not skipped class in the past 30 days. Students who had skipped class on three or more days were more likely to have used ecstasy, painkillers, and tranquilizers in their lifetime than had students who had not skipped any class. School grade was also significantly associated with lifetime use of inhalants, ecstasy, alcohol with pills, and painkillers. 16.7% of students whose average grade score was an E or lower had used ecstasy in their lifetime. However, only around 1.2% of students whose average grade score was an A or B had ever used ecstasy. Similarly, students who attained a lower grade were more likely to have used inhalants, painkillers, alcohol with pills, and tranquilizers.

Students were asked if their parents know where they spend Saturday nights and significant associations were observed between parental monitoring of Saturday nights and lifetime use of cocaine, amphetamines, ecstasy, tranquilizers, inhalants, alcohol with pills and painkillers. 17.8% of students whose parents 'sometimes or usually don't know' where they spend Saturday nights have used cocaine, but 1.2% of students who answered 'always' have used cocaine. Similarly, compared to 17.6% of students who responded that their parents usually don't know where they are on Saturday nights and had used alcohol with pills, only 1.6% of students whose parents always know where they are had used cocaine. Similar results were observed for lifetime use of amphetamines, ecstasy, inhalants and painkillers. In general, higher levels of parental monitoring were associated with lower substance use.

When substance use was examined in relation to household members, few significant differences were found. Lifetime use of alcohol with pills and painkillers were significantly associated with household type; 3.3% of those who live with two parents had used alcohol with pills and 17.7% students who did not live with any parents had done so. Similarly, 17.7% of students who did not live with any parents had used painkillers to get high while only 4.6% of those who lived with two parents had done so. While a higher proportion of students who were not living with either parent had used inhalants, cocaine and ecstasy, significant differences were not found.

Peer substance use was very strongly related to students' own substance use. The vast majority of students did not have any friends who used inhalants, ecstasy or tranquilizers (85%, 84%, 88%). Only a few students who reported some, most or all of their friends take ecstasy have ever used inhalants (18.85%), while 9.1% of those with a few friends who take ecstasy have used inhalants and 10% students who do not have any friends who take ecstasy have done so themselves. Peer use of ecstasy was also related to respondents' use of painkillers, alcohol with pills, inhalants and tranquilizers. Similarly, peer use of inhalants was moderately related to respondents' use of tranquilizers, inhalants, and alcohol with pills, and peer use of

tranquilizers was related to use of ecstasy.

INTERNET GAMING AND GAMBLING

ESPAD
The European School Survey Project
On Alcohol and Other Drugs

37% spent 2-3 hours on social media on a typical school day

39% spent 6+ hours on social media on a typical non-school day

(98% vs 95%)

More females than males spent more hours on social media on a typical school day

44% spent some time playing games on a school day,

56% spent some time playing games on a typical non-school day

Strongly or partly agreed that they spend too much time gaming

Agreed that their parents say they spend too much time gaming.

Agreed that their parents say that they spend too much time on social media

Strongly or partly agreed that they spend too much time on social media.

16% have ever gambled

(23% vs 7%)

More males than females have ever gambled

12% gambled monthly or less and 2% gambled 2+ times a month

Betting on sports or animals (horses, dogs, etc.) was the most common gambling activity (15%).

7. INTERNET, GAMING AND GAMBLING

ESPAD 2019 included a number of items related to internet use and online activity as well as gambling, both online and in traditional settings. This chapter discusses the main results regarding time spent on the internet, different uses of the internet and perceived problems of internet use before discussing the results regarding frequency of gambling and gambling activities both online and in traditional settings.

Internet use

Students were asked how many hours they had spent on social media communicating with others on the internet in the last 30 days on a school day and on a non-school day (weekend, holidays). Only 3.6% (n=69) of respondents did not use the internet on a typical school day in the last 30 days (Table 7.1). The highest proportion (36.6%, n=705) responded that they spent 2 to 3 hours, closely followed by 22.6% (n=435) who answered that they spent 4-5 hours. There were significant differences in internet use on a typical school day between male and female students¹²⁵. Female respondents spent more time on social media on a school day (98%, n=978) than did male students (94.7%, n= 877). Male students (19.3%, n=179) were more likely than female students (13.4%, n=134) to spend about 1 hour or more on the internet on a school day. Female students (16.6%, n=166) were more likely to spend 6 hours or more on the internet than were male students (14.2%, n=131).

Hours spent on internet - school day	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	49	5.3	20	2.0	69	3.6
Half an hour	65	7.0	40	4.0	105	5.5
About 1 hour	179	19.3	134	13.4	313	16.3
2 to 3 hours	337	36.4	368	36.9	705	36.6
4 to 5 hours	165	17.8	270	27.1	435	22.6
6 hours or more	131	14.2	166	16.6	297	15.4
Total	926	100.0	998	100.0	1924	100.0

Table 7.1: Hours spent on the internet during a typical weekday by gender

97.3% (n=1856) of students spent some time on social media on a non-school day in the last 30 days (Table 7.2). More than one third of respondents (39.1%, n=746) spent 6 hours or more on social media. Significant gender differences were also observed for non-school day internet use¹²⁶ with females (98.5%, n=977) spending more time on the internet on a typical non-school day than did male students (96.1%, n=879). Male students (22.8%, n=209) were more likely to spend 2-3 hours on the internet than were female students (17.3%, n=172), whereas female students (44.3%, n=439) were more likely than male students (33.6%, n=307) to spend 6 hours or more on the internet on a non-school day.

¹²⁵ School day use: [χ^2 (5)= 52.823, p<.001, Cramer's V=.166]

¹²⁶ Non-school day use: [χ^2 (5)= 55.921, p<.001. Cramer's V=.171]

Hours spent on internet - non-school day	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	36	3.9	15	1.5	51	2.7
Half an hour	41	4.5	13	1.3	54	2.8
About 1 hour	65	7.1	44	4.4	109	5.7
2 to 3 hours	209	22.8	172	17.3	381	20.0
4 to 5 hours	257	28.1	309	31.1	566	29.7
6 hours or more	307	33.6	439	44.3	746	39.1
Total	915	100.0	992	100.0	1907	100.0

Table 7.2: Hours spent on the internet during a typical weekend by gender

Students were asked how many hours they spent playing games with other people using a computer, tablet, console, smartphone or other electronic device during the last 30 days on a school day and a non-school day.

Almost half of respondents (44.1%, n=845) had spent some time playing games on a school day in the last 30 days and most students (13.4%, n=256) spent about an hour. There were significant differences between male and female students on hours spent playing games on a typical school day¹²⁷ with males spending more time playing games overall (66%, n=609; females-23.7%, n= 236). The highest number of male respondents spent about 1 hour playing games on a school day (30.5%, n=189).

Hours spent playing games -school day	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	314	34.0	758	76.3	1072	55.9
Half an hour	101	10.9	115	11.6	216	11.3
About 1 hour	189	30.5	67	6.7	256	13.4
2 to 3 hours	191	20.7	24	2.4	215	11.2
4 to 5 hours	67	7.3	17	1.7	84	4.4
6 hours or more	61	6.6	13	1.3	74	3.9
Total	923	100.0	994	100.0	1917	100.0

Table 7.3: Hours spent playing games during a typical school day by gender

More than half of respondents (55.5%, n=1060) spent some time playing games on a typical non-school day in the last 30 days. There were significant gender differences in hours spent playing games on a non-school day¹²⁸. More male students (84%, n=770) than female students (29.2%, n=290) spent time playing games on a typical non-school day. Again, male respondents (30.5%, n=280) were more likely to spend 2 to 3 hours playing games on a non-school day than female students (5.9%, n=59).

¹²⁷ Playing games-school day: [$X^2(5) = 431.519, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .474$]

¹²⁸ Playing games non-school day: [$X^2(5) = 723.914, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .616$]

Hours spent playing games, non-school day	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	147	16.0	704	70.8	851	44.5
Half an hour	63	6.9	108	10.9	171	8.9
About 1 hour	99	10.8	71	7.1	170	8.9
2 to 3 hours	280	30.5	59	5.9	339	17.7
4 to 5 hours	139	15.2	25	2.5	164	8.5
6 hours or more	189	20.6	27	2.7	216	11.3
Total	917	100.0	994	100.0	1911	100.0

Table 7.4: Hours spent playing games during a typical non-school day by gender

Students were asked how many days they spent playing games with other people using a computer, tablet console, smartphone or other electronic device during the last 7 days (Table 7.5). Overall, 44.1% (n=842) spent time playing games with other people in the past 7 days. There were significant differences between male and female respondents¹²⁹. Male students (71.8%, n=661) spent much more time playing games with other people than did female students (18.2%, n=181). More male students responded to spending 4 or more days (37.1%, n=342; female-5.2%, n=52) playing games with other people.

Days spent playing games with other people	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
None	259	28.2	811	81.8	1070	55.9
1 day	104	11.3	69	7.0	173	9.1
2-3 days	215	23.4	60	6.0	275	14.4
4 or more days	342	37.1	52	5.2	394	20.6
Total	920	100.0	992	100.0	1912	100.0

Table 7.5: Days spent playing games with others by gender

Perceived problems with internet use

Students were asked how much they agreed with statements about problems associated with internet use with regards to social media communication and gaming. The three statements were ‘I think I spend way too much time’, ‘I get in a bad mood when I cannot spend time’, ‘my parents say that I spend way too much time’ on either social media or gaming (strongly agree, partly agree, neither nor, partly disagree, strongly disagree). Results are presented in Table 7.6.

Most students responded that they either strongly agree (26.3%, n=506) or partly agree (37.4%, n=720) that they spend too much time on social media. More students answered that they strongly disagree (33%, n=631) that they get in a bad mood when they cannot spend time on social media. 31.1% (n=599) strongly agreed and 25.4% (n=486) partly agreed that their parents say that they spend too much time on social media.

Regarding gaming, 47.5% (n=909) strongly disagreed that they spend too much time gaming. 56.6% (n=1011) strongly disagreed that they get in a bad mood when they cannot spend time on games and 50.5% (n=965) strongly disagreed that they parents say they spend too much time gaming.

¹²⁹ Days spent playing games with other people: $[X^2(3) = 590.793, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .556]$

Perceived problems-social media	Strongly agree		Partly agree		Neither nor		Partly disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Spend too much time	506	26.3	720	37.4	296	15.4	222	11.5	179	9.3	1923	100.0
Bad mood when unable to	193	10.1	438	22.9	308	16.1	344	18.0	631	33.0	1914	100.0
Parents say spend too much time	599	31.1	486	25.4	315	16.5	200	10.5	310	16.2	1910	100.0
Perceived problems-gaming	Strongly agree		Partly agree		Neither nor		Partly disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	%	N
Spend too much time	138	7.2	244	12.8	359	18.8	263	13.7	909	47.5	1913	100.0
Bad mood when unable to	96	5.0	170	8.9	334	17.6	226	11.9	1011	56.6	1903	100.0
Parents say spend too much time	210	11.0	237	12.4	316	16.2	180	9.4	965	50.5	1905	100.0

Table 7.6: Perceived problems with internet use for social media and gaming

Gambling

The method used to compute the gambling prevalence in this report is different from the one used in the 2015 report. In 2015, a direct question ‘How often (if ever) did you gamble money in the last 12 months?’ was used to compute the gambling prevalence. However, in 2019 3 items of the adopted version of the Consumption Screen for Problem Gambling (CSPG) (Rockloff, 2011) assessing the intensity of gambling, was used to examine the proportion of gamblers displaying excessive gambling behaviour. The three questions measure: (a) gambling frequency: ‘How often (if ever) have you gambled money in the last 12 months?’ (‘I have not gambled for money’, ‘monthly or less’, ‘2–4 times a month’, ‘2 or more times a week’), (b) time spent on gambling: ‘How much time did you spend gambling on a typical day in which you gambled in the last 12 months?’ (‘I have not gambled for money’, ‘less than 30 min’, ‘between 30 min and 1 hour’, ‘between 1 and 2 hours’, ‘between 2 and 3 hours’, ‘3 hours or more’); and (c) gambling intensity: ‘How often did you spend more than 2 hours gambling (on a single occasion) in the last 12 months?’ (‘I have not gambled for money’, ‘never’, ‘less than monthly’, ‘monthly’, ‘weekly’ and daily’. This means that a direct comparison between the results of 2019 and those of 2015 cannot be made.

Responses presented in Table 7.7 show that 84.3% (n=1607) had never gambled at all in the past 12 months. Of those who had gambled, 12.3% (n=235) had gambled monthly or less. There were significant gender differences in gambling in the last 12 months¹³⁰. Male students (23.4%, n=215) were more likely to have gambled in the last 12 months than female students (8.6%, n=85).

¹³⁰ Gambling: [$\chi^2(3) = 90.141, p < .001, \text{Cramer's } V = .217$]

Gambling in the past 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	702	76.6	905	91.4	1607	84.3
Monthly or less	157	17.1	78	7.9	235	12.3
2 to 4 times a month	36	3.9	6	0.6	42	2.2
2 or more times a week	22	2.4	1	0.1	23	1.2
Total	917	100.0	990	100.0	1907	100.0

Table 7.7: Gambling in the past 12 months by gender

Regarding how much time students spend gambling for money on a typical day in the last 12 months, of students who had gambled, 10.6%, (n=201) responded that they spent less than 30 minutes. There were significant gender differences in time spent on gambling¹³¹

Time spent on gambling on a typical day in the last 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	717	78.3	903	91.2	1620	85.0
Less than 30 minutes	129	14.1	72	7.3	201	10.6
Between 30 minutes and 1 hour	37	4.0	7	0.7	44	2.3
Between 1 and 2 hours	12	1.3	4	0.4	16	0.8
2 hours or more	21	2.3	4	0.4	25	1.3
Total	916	100.0	990	100.0	1906	100.0

Table 7.8: Time spent on gambling on a typical day in the last 12 months by gender

Regarding time spent on gambling, of students who had gambled for more than 2 hours, 22.3% (n=85) had gambled less than monthly and 4.2% (n=16) had gambled monthly for money for more than two hours. Again, significant gender differences were observed for gambling more than 2 hours in the last 12 months¹³².

Gambling more than 2 hours (on a single occasion) in the last 12 months	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Never	162	65.6	106	78.5	268	70.2
Less than monthly	59	23.9	26	19.3	85	22.3
Monthly	13	5.3	3	2.2	16	4.2
Weekly	7	2.8	0	0.0	7	1.8
Daily	6	2.4	0	0.0	6	1.6
Total	247	100.0	135	100.0	382	100.0

Table 7.9: Gambling more than 2 hours (on a single occasion) in the last 12 months by gender

Students were asked how often they had used the internet to gamble for money if they had gambled in the last 12 months. 15.9% (n=295) answered that they never used the internet to gamble for money. Of those who had, 3% (n=56) answered that they seldom use the internet. Significant gender differences were also observed for use of the internet to gamble for money¹³³.

¹³¹ Time spent on gambling: [χ^2 (5)= 70.768, $p < .001$, Cramer's $V = .193$]

¹³² Gambling more than 2 hours: [χ^2 (4)= 11.953, $p = .018$, Cramer's $V = .177$]

¹³³ Use of Internet to gamble for money: [χ^2 (5)= 12.498, $p = .029$, Cramer's $V = .082$]

Use of Internet to gamble for money	Male		Female		All	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
I have not gambled for money	636	71.7	803	83.7	1439	77.9
I never use the internet to gamble for money	162	18.3	133	13.9	295	15.9
Seldom	41	4.6	15	1.6	56	3.0
Sometimes	20	2.3	6	0.5	26	1.4
Mostly	10	1.1	2	0.2	12	0.7
Always	18	2.0	1	0.1	19	1.0
Total	892	100.0	955	100.0	1847	100.0

Students were asked what type of games they played when they gambled for money in the last 12 months. Responses were recoded into ‘Yes’ and ‘No’ to examine the most popular types of games played. Overall, betting on sports or animals (horses, dogs, etc.) was the most common gambling activity (14.5%, n=261). The least popular form of gambling was slot machines (8.4%, n=153).

Gambling	No		Yes		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Slot machines	1651	91.5	153	8.4	1804	100.0
Cards or dice	1651	90.6	168	9.4	1783	100.0
Lotteries	1569	88.1	212	11.9	1781	100.0
Betting	1542	85.5	261	14.5	1803	100.0

Table 7.10: Gambling for money in the last 12 months by types of games played

Figure 7.2: Gambling activities by types of games played

The Lie/Bet Questionnaire (Johnson, Hamer and Nora, 1998), a two-question screening tool was adopted to assess the proportion of gamblers with a possible problematic gambling behaviour. Two questions were asked ‘Have you ever lied to family and friends about how much money you have spent on gambling?’ and ‘Have you ever felt that you need to gamble

for more money?’ both with response categories ‘yes’ and ‘no’. Results presented in Table 7.11 show that 26.3% (n=78) of students who had gambled in the last 12 months (n=300) felt the need to bet more and more money and 12.2% (n=36) have had to lie to the people important to them about how much they gambled. There were no significant gender differences¹³⁴.

Gambling	No		Yes		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Ever felt the need to bet more and more money?	218	73.7	78	26.3	296	100.0
Ever lied to the people important to you about how much you gambled?	260	87.8	36	12.2	296	100.0

Table 7.11: Gaming behaviors

Summary

Female students spent more hours on social media on a typical school day (98%) than male students (94.7%) with females more likely to spend 6 hours (16.6%) or more on the internet than males were (14.2%). Again, female students (98.5%) responded to spending more time on the internet on a typical non-school day than did male students (96.1%) with females more likely to spend 6 hours or more (44.3%) than did male students (33.6%) on social media on a typical school day. Male students (22.8%) however were more likely to spend 2-3 hours on social media than female students were (17.3%)

Almost half of respondents (44.1%) had spent some time playing games on a school day in the last 30 days and 13.4% students spent about an hour. Again, more than half of respondents (55.5%) spent some time playing games on a typical non-school day in the last 30 days, with males (84%) spending more time playing games on a typical non-school day than females (29.2%). A further 44.1% spent time playing games with other people in the past 7 days.

63.7% of students strongly or partly agreed that they spend too much time on social media. 10% strongly agreed that they get in a bad mood when they cannot spend time on social media. 56.5% agreed that their parents say that they spend too much time on social media. Regarding gaming, 47.5% strongly disagreed that they spend too much time gaming. 56.6% strongly disagreed that they get in a bad mood when they cannot spend time on games and 50.5% strongly disagreed that their parents say they spend too much time gaming.

The majority of students (84.3%) have never gambled in the past 12 months. Of those who had gambled, 12.3% had gambled monthly or less. Male students (23.4%) were more likely to have gambled in the last 12 months than female students (8.6%) and 10.6% of students had spent less than 30 minutes gambling for money on a typical day in the last 12 months. Overall, betting on sports or animals (horses, dogs, etc.) was the most common gambling activity (14.5%). The least popular form of gambling was slot machines (8.4%).

¹³⁴ Need to bet more money [$\chi^2(1)=.166$, $p=.683$]; Lied about gambling [$\chi^2(1)=1.721$, $p=.190$]

8. SUBSTANCE USE IN IRELAND TO DATE

The ESPAD project contributes considerably to our knowledge of the use of tobacco, alcohol and other substances among Irish 15-16 year olds. As well as the ability to examine the influence of psychosocial and environmental factors on substance use behaviours, substance use can be measured and compared over time. The introduction to this report showed that use of cannabis, inhalants, tranquilisers and other substances have declined in Ireland by over 50% since 1995, with a reduction in regular smoking of 49% and in 30-day alcohol consumption by over a quarter.

But between 2015 and 2019 there were some increases in alcohol and tobacco use and a marked increase in e-cigarette usage.

Alcohol Use

In Ireland, alcohol use in the past 30 days increased by 14% between 2015 and 2019 although there has been a 41% reduction in the past twenty-five years. Almost half of the sample reported drinking alcohol in the previous 30 days in Ireland in 2019.

Although there was a slight increase in alcohol use in the last four years, there has been a large reduction in drinking among 15-16 year olds since 1995 which suggest that the 2013 Healthy Ireland Framework' target of reducing alcohol consumption among people aged 15 or older to 9.2 liters of alcohol per year may be met by 2025. There was a 16% reduction in 30-day alcohol use from both 1995 and a 2% reduction in 2019 for the ESPAD average

Figure 8.1: Alcohol use in the past 30 days since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Heavy episodic drinking

Heavy episodic drinking in Ireland was particularly high in 1995 at 47% but fell by 30% by 2015 although there was an increase by 18% between 2015 and 2019. The ESPAD average, however, declined by 62% between 2015 and 2019.

Figure 8.2: Heavy episodic drinking in the past 30 days since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Current smoking

In Ireland, smoking among these 15-16 year olds was greatly reduced to 14% in 2019. This represents a reduction of over two-thirds (66%) since 1995, the second largest decline of any of these seven indicators in both Ireland and the ESPAD 20 average. However, there was a slight increase in 30-day cigarette smoking between 2015 and 2019 from 13% in 2015 to 14% in 2019 which was due to an increase in male smoking. In ESPAD 20 average, there was a decline by 5% between 2015 and 2019.

Figure 8.3: 30-day cigarette use since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime use of cannabis

Cannabis use in Ireland showed a one percentage point increase from 19% in 2015 to 20% in 2019 and a drop in almost half (46%) since 1995. Cannabis use in ESPAD 20 stayed the same between 2015 and 2019 although there has been a 45% increase since 1995.

Figure 8.4: Lifetime use of cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime Inhalant Use

There was no change in prevalence of lifetime inhalant use in Ireland and ESPAD 20. For Ireland, it has stayed at 10% since 2015. This represents a 55% reduction since 1995.

Figure 8.5: Lifetime use of inhalants since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Lifetime use of tranquilizers without prescription

There was no change in prevalence of tranquilizer use in Ireland. In Ireland, the use of tranquilizers without prescription has stayed at 3% since 2015 in Ireland, this represents a 57% reduction since 1995. There was also no change in ESPAD 20 average, with a reduction of 25% since 1995.

Figure 8.6: Lifetime use of tranquilizers since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Use of Illicit Drugs other than Cannabis

In Ireland, there was a decrease in use of illicit drugs other than cannabis by 29%, decreasing from 7% in 2015 to 5% in 2019. There was a 69% reduction in in use of illicit drugs since 1995, the largest reduction of all seven indicators in Ireland. The ESPAD 20 started at 3% in 1995, however, rising to 5% in 2015 until 2019, where returned to the 1995 level of 3%.

Figure 8.7: Lifetime use of illicit drugs other than cannabis since 1995 by gender in Ireland and ESPAD 20

Conclusion

Across Europe, there has been reductions in use of alcohol, heavy episodic drinking and smoking. There has been no change in use of cannabis, tranquilisers without doctors prescription, and use of other illicit substances.

In the past twenty-five years in Ireland, there have been major reductions in drinking, smoking and the use of many substances. The largest reduction was in the use of other illicit drugs which fell by 69% and the prevalence of smoking which fell 66% since 1995. Drinking alcohol and heavy episodic binge drinking also fell, and a substantial rate, with a 30% reduction in binge drinking and a 41% decrease in alcohol use.

However, there has been an increase in the use of these substances in the last four years. Alcohol use has increased by 14%, heavy episodic drinking has increased by 18%, smoking in the last 30 days has also increased by 8% to 14% and cannabis use has increased by 5% since 2015.

Since 1995, the use of tranquilisers has fallen by over half, although there has been no reduction in Ireland since 2015. Similarly, the use of inhalants has also fallen since 1999 and there has been no change since 2015. The use of other illicit drugs has also fallen both since 1995 by 69% and since 2015 by 29%.

Also, worth noting is the marked 50% increase in the last 30 day use of e-cigarettes from 10% in 2015 to 15% in 2019. This suggests that the popularity of e-cigarettes is on the rise among young people in Ireland.

These results call for continued targeted high-intensity tobacco, alcohol and drug use control campaigns and legislation.

Ireland					
Percentage change in substance use	1995	2015	2019	% change 1995-2019	% change 2015-2019
Alcohol Use (last 30 days)	69%	36%	41%	-41	14%
Heavy episodic drinking (last 30 days)	47%	28%	33%	-30%	18%
Smoking (last 30 days)	41%	13%	14%	-66%	8%
e-cigarette (last 30 days)	-	10%	15%	-	50%
Cannabis	37%	19%	20%	-46%	5%
Inhalants (<i>from 1999</i>)	22%	10%	10%	-55%	0%
Tranquilizers	7%	3%	3%	-57%	0%
Other illicit substances	16%	7%	5%	-69%	-29%
ESPAD 20					
Percentage change in substance use	1995	2015	2019	% change 1995-2019	% change 2015-2019
Alcohol Use (last 30 days)	56%	48%	47%	-16%	-2%
Heavy episodic drinking (last 30 days)	35%	35%	13%	-62%	-62%
Smoking (last 30 days)	32%	21%	20%	-38%	-5%
Cannabis	11%	16%	16%	45%	0%
Inhalants (<i>from 1999</i>)	8%	7%	7%	-13%	0%
Tranquilizers	8%	6%	6%	-25%	0%
Other illicit substances	3%	5%	3%	67%	0%

Table 8.1: Lifetime substance use for Ireland in 1995, 2015 and 2019 and percentage change since 1995 and 2015.

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Appendix 1: Data Collection Materials

TOBACCOFREE

RESEARCH INSTITUTE

November 27th 2018

Dear Principal

I am writing to ask for your assistance in carrying out a most important European-wide survey on drugs including Tobacco and Alcohol use among teenagers. We are hoping to carry out the survey in **Spring 2019** but need to know in advance what schools are willing to participate.

The European School Survey on Alcohol and Drugs (ESPAD) is a collaborative effort of independent research teams in more than forty European countries and the largest cross-national research project on adolescent substance use in the world. The overall aim with the project is to repeatedly collect comparable data on substance use among 15–16 year old students in as many European countries as possible. The ESPAD has been conducted in Irish secondary schools every four years for the past twenty years. It is a valuable, cornerstone research project and it is essential that Ireland continues to be involved. The TobaccoFree Research Institute Ireland has been awarded the competitive tender by the Department of Health to administer the ESPAD survey in Ireland for this cycle.

A random sample of secondary schools was generated for this study and your school has been selected for participation. I am aware that an exercise such as this can be an intrusion into the already busy life of the school. The study has been designed, however, to minimize additional work for you and your staff.

I am asking for your help in **assigning a cooperating teacher** who could serve as a liaison and oversee research administration in your school. In the past, this has often been the designated Social, Personal, and Health teacher, though the decision is, of course, yours.

The details of the research are outlined in the attached Information Sheet. For now, I ask that you complete and return the attached postcard to our office. My Colleagues and I will then liaise with the designated teacher directly.

While I cannot offer financial compensation for participation, I would happily volunteer my time to visit your school and speak with your staff and/or students about our research in this field.

Yours sincerely,

Professor Luke Clancy Director General

TobaccoFree Research Institute Ireland

D.I.T. Focas Building 8 Camden Row, Dublin 8.

TEL 353 15388372 Mobile 00 353 (0) 868364337 EMAIL lclancy@tri.ie www.tri.ie

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Ms Valerie Duncan, Mr. Ivor Fitzpatrick (Chair), Prof. Pat Goodman
Registered in Ireland, 10 Upper Mount Street, Dublin 2. Co Reg No 351908

PARENT / GUARDIAN INFORMATION SHEET

What is this study about?

The European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) survey takes place every 4 years in more than 35 European countries during the same time period and is based on a common set of questions and methodology. This series of studies began in 1995 following an initiative by the Swedish Council for Information on Alcohol and Other Drugs (CAN) to connect with researchers in other European countries, including Ireland, with a view to conducting a common survey on the usage of tobacco, alcohol and illegal drugs in the school-going population.

Why is this study important?

The most important goal of the ESPAD survey is to monitor trends in alcohol and other drug use among 15-16 year-olds and to compare trends between countries and groups of countries. This information is essential in planning future prevention initiatives. The rationale for school surveys is that students make up the age groups when onset of use is most likely to occur. In addition, school populations are more accessible than other groups.

Why was my child's school selected?

The study aims to gather information from young people aged between 15 and 16yrs who are currently in secondary education. Secondary schools across the country were randomly selected and invited to participate in the project.

What does participation involve?

If you and your child choose to get involved, your child will be asked to complete a short questionnaire during class time.

Does my child have to participate?

Absolutely not. Participation is 100% voluntary. No one will be included in any stage of the research unless they have given consent. Participants can revoke consent at any stage of the process.

Confidentiality

All information that is gathered in this study remains 100% confidential. Your child's information will be stored in a secure computer that is only used by members of the research team. No one will have access to the information gathered in this study aside from the researchers and it will only be used for research purposes. There will be no identifiable information stored in the computer at any stage during this research.

Who is conducting this study?

The Tobacco Free Research Institute Ireland (TFRI) is administering the survey on behalf of the Department of Health and the European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD).

We'd like to thank you in advance for your participation and support. It is through research that we are able to learn about young people's perception of tobacco products and work towards improving the overall health of young people in Ireland through tobacco prevention. Without parents' time and consent, studies like this would be unable to proceed.

Parental Non-Consent Form

I have read the information sheet on the ESPAD European Survey and I do not want my child to complete this survey.

School Name:

Child's Name:

Parent or Guardian's Name:

Parent or Guardian's Signature:

Date:

ESPAD INFORMATION SHEET

What is this study about?

The European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD) survey takes place every 4 years in 44 European countries and is based on a common set of questions and methodology. This series of studies began in 1995 to connect with researchers in other European countries, including Ireland, with a view to conducting a common survey on the usage of tobacco, alcohol and illegal drugs in the school-going population.

Why is this study important?

The most important goal of the ESPAD survey is to monitor trends in alcohol and other drug use among 15- 16 year olds and to compare trends between countries. This information is essential in planning future prevention initiatives across Europe. This year, 2019, will mark the 24th anniversary of the first data collection wave.

Why was my school selected?

Secondary schools across the country were randomly selected and invited to participate in the project. Your school was one that was randomly generated for participation.

What does participation involve?

If your school chooses to get involved, we will ask you to appoint a 'cooperating teacher' who will liaise with us and oversee the administration in your school. If your school has transition year, we would hope to survey 3rd and 4th (transition) year, otherwise, we would hope to survey 3rd and 5th year. We will contact the 'cooperating teacher' and arrange a date and time for survey administration. We will mail all surveys, information sheets, and instructions to the cooperating teacher with a stamped envelope included. After students complete the surveys, we ask that you return completed surveys to the prepaid envelope and return them to us.

What about consent and confidentiality?

Participation, both at the school level and the individual level, is 100% voluntary. We will obtain written consent from all students before the survey. Parents will receive information sheets and an 'opt-out' form if they want their child not to be involved. All students will receive an unmarked envelope with their survey and once the survey is completed, they will seal the survey before returning to the administering teacher. We will collect no identifying information from any student and all information gathered is 100% confidential.

Who is conducting this study?

The Tobacco Free Research Institute Ireland (TFRI) is overseeing the administration of the survey on behalf of the Department of Health and the European Schools Project for Alcohol and Other Drugs (ESPAD).

If you have any questions or concerns, please feel free to contact a member of the research team: Ms. Sheila Keogan (skeogan@tri.ie, 0876887678) or Dr. Ermelinda Brzychcyk (ermelinda@tri.ie, 0851516775). We'll be happy to discuss the project with you and/or your cooperating teacher in more detail. We'd like to thank you in advance for your consideration and support. It is through research that we are able to learn about young people's attitudes and behaviours in countries throughout Europe.

Dear Principal

I am writing to you about an important European-wide study that will be conducted in secondary schools in the coming months.

The European School Survey on Alcohol and Drugs (ESPAD) is a collaborative effort of independent research teams in more than forty European countries and the largest cross-national research project on adolescent substance use in the world. The overall aim with the project is to repeatedly collect comparable data on substance use among **15-16** year old students in as many European countries as possible.

The ESPAD has been conducted in Irish secondary schools every four years for the past twenty-four years. It is a valuable, cornerstone research project and one that we are eager to remain involved in. This year, the TobaccoFree Research Institute has been awarded the competitive tender to administer the European-wide project here in Ireland.

Data collection is set to begin in the coming weeks and your school has been randomly selected by the researchers for participation in this study.

I am aware that an exercise such as this can be an intrusion into the already busy life of the school. The study has been designed, however, to minimize additional work on the part of the school.

Given the importance of the information collected, to the future health and education of the students' and the input that this study will have on Government planning and legislative interventions, I hope that you will be able to support this most worthwhile exercise. It is unquestionably one of the most important studies to be conducted on substance use among European teenagers.

I would like to thank you, in anticipation, for your co-operation in this research.

Yours sincerely,

Dilly O'Brien
Tobacco and Alcohol Control Unit

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The European School Survey Project on
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www.espad.org

Appendix 2: Questionnaire used for ESPAD Ireland 2019

Questionnaire on substance use

Read this first please!

This questionnaire is part of an international study on substance use among European students. It will be answered by more than 100,000 students in over 35 countries. The study is called ESPAD.

This is a totally anonymous questionnaire. You should not state your name or any other information which identifies you. You should place your completed questionnaire in the enclosed envelope and seal it yourself. Your teacher will collect the envelopes after completion.

Your class has been randomly selected to take part in this study. In Ireland the survey is carried out by the TobaccoFree Research Institute. It is voluntary to take part. If there is any question you find objectionable for any reason, just leave it blank. It is important that you answer as thoughtfully and frankly as possible. The results will not be presented by single classes and remember your answers are totally anonymous.

If you do not find an answer that fits exactly, indicate the one that comes closest. Please, mark the appropriate answer to each question by making an "X" in the box. If you have a question, please raise your hand and your teacher will assist you.

Thank you in advance for your participation! Please begin.

TobaccoFree Research Institute Ireland
Focas Research Institute,
DIT Kevin Street,
Dublin 8
Email: skeogan@tri.ie
ermelinda@tri.ie
Website: www.tri.ie

The first questions ask for some background information about yourself and the kinds of things you might do

C01 What is your sex?

- 1 Male
 2 Female

C02 When were you born?

Year

Month

(Mark 01 for January, 02 for February ...
 ... 12 for December)

C03 How often (if at all) do you do each of the following?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	A few times a year	Once or twice a month	At least once a week	Almost every day
(a) Play computer games.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) Actively participate in sports, athletics or exercising	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) Read books for enjoyment (do not count schoolbooks)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) Go out in the evening (to a disco, cafe, party etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) Other hobbies (play an instrument, sing, draw, write)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) Go around with friends to shopping centres, streets, parks, etc, just for fun	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(g) Use the Internet for leisure activities (chats, music, games, social networks, videos etc).....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(h) Play on slot machines (the kind in which you may win money).....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

C04 During the LAST 30 DAYS on how many days have you missed one or more lessons?

Mark one box for each line.

	None	1 day	2 days	3-4 days	5-6 days	7 days or more
(a) Because of illness	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) Because you skipped or 'cut'.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) For other reasons	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

The following questions are about tobacco smoking (cigarettes, which include rolled cigarettes and EXCLUDE e-cigarettes)

C05 How difficult do you think it would be for you to get cigarettes (excluding e-cigarettes) if you wanted?

- 1 Impossible
 2 Very difficult
 3 Fairly difficult
 4 Fairly easy
 5 Very easy
 6 Don't know

C06 On how many occasions (if any) during your lifetime have you smoked cigarettes (excluding e-cigarettes)?

Number of occasions

0 <input type="checkbox"/>	1-2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3-5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6-9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10-19 <input type="checkbox"/>	20-39 <input type="checkbox"/>	40 or more <input type="checkbox"/>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C07 How often have you smoked cigarettes (excluding e-cigarettes) during the LAST 30 DAYS?

- 1 Not at all
- 2 Less than 1 cigarette per week
- 3 Less than 1 cigarette per day
- 4 1-5 cigarettes per day
- 5 6-10 cigarettes per day
- 6 11-20 cigarettes per day
- 7 More than 20 cigarettes per day

C08 When (if ever) did you FIRST do each of the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	9 years old or less	10 years old	11 years old	12 years old	13 years old	14 years old	15 years old	16 years or older
(a) Smoke your first cigarette (excluding e-cigarettes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Smoke cigarettes on a daily basis (excluding e-cigarettes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

The next questions are about nicotine products: water pipe (shisha), e-cigarettes, moist snuff (snus) and heat-not-burn tobacco

C09 Have you ever used e-cigarettes? Mark all that apply.

- 1 No
- 2 Yes, more than 12 months ago
- 3 Yes, in the last 12 months
- 4 Yes, in the last 30 days

C10 How often have you smoked e-cigarettes during the LAST 30 DAYS?

- 1 Not at all
- 2 Less than once per week
- 3 At least once a week
- 4 Almost every day

C11 When (if ever) did you FIRST do each of the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	9 years old or less	10 years old	11 years old	12 years old	13 years old	14 years old	15 years old	16 years or older
(a) Use your first e-cigarette	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Use e-cigarettes on a daily basis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

C12 When you first tried e-cigarettes (if ever), what was your relationship with tobacco?

- 1 I have never tried e-cigarettes
- 2 I had never used tobacco
- 3 I had occasionally used tobacco
- 4 I was regularly using tobacco

OC01 Why did you try e-cigarettes for the first time?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 I have never tried e-cigarettes
- 2 To stop smoking cigarettes
- 3 Out of curiosity
- 4 Because my friends offered an e-cigarette to me
- 5 None of the above reasons

OC02 The first times you used e-cigarettes what did your e-cigarette contain?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 I have never tried e-cigarettes
- 2 Nicotine
- 3 Flavouring
- 4 Don't know

C13 Have you ever used water pipe, moist snuff (snus), 'heat-not-burn' tobacco?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	Yes, but more than 12 months ago	Yes, in the last 12 months	Yes, in the last 30 days
(a) Water pipe (shisha).....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Moist snuff (snus)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) 'Heat-not-burn' tobacco	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4

The next questions are about alcoholic beverages – including beer, cider, premixed drinks, wine and spirits

C14 How difficult do you think it would be for you to get each of the following, if you wanted?

Mark one box for each line.

	Impossible	Very difficult	Fairly difficult	Fairly easy	Very easy	Don't know
(a) Beer.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) Cider	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) Premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(d) Wine	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(e) Spirits	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

C15 On how many occasions (if any) have you had any alcoholic beverage to drink?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) In your lifetime	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) During the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C16 Think back over the LAST 30 DAYS. On how many occasions (if any) have you had any of the following to drink?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) Beer.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) Cider	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) Premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(d) Wine.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(e) Spirits	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

The following questions are about the last day you drank alcohol

C17 When was the last day you drank alcohol?

- 1 I never drink alcohol
- 2 1-7 days ago
- 3 8-14 days ago
- 4 15-30 days ago
- 5 1 month - 1 year ago
- 6 More than 1 year ago

C18 Think of the LAST DAY that you drank any alcohol. Which of the following beverages did you drink on that day?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 I never drink alcohol
- 2 Beer
- 3 Cider
- 4 Premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops)
- 5 Wine
- 6 Spirits

C18a If you drank beer that last day you drank any alcohol, how much did you drink?

- 1 I never drink beer
- 2 I did not drink beer on the last day that I drank alcohol
- 3 <50 cl
- 4 50–100 cl
- 5 101–200 cl
- 6 >200 cl

C18d If you drank wine that last day you drank any alcohol, how much did you drink?

- 1 I never drink wine
- 2 I did not drink wine on the last day that I drank alcohol
- 3 <20 cl
- 4 20–40 cl
- 5 41–74 cl
- 6 >74 cl

OC18b If you drank cider that last day you drank any alcohol, how much did you drink?

- 1 I never drink cider
- 2 I did not drink cider on the last day that I drank alcohol
- 3 <50 cl
- 4 50–100 cl
- 5 101–200 cl
- 6 >200 cl

C18e If you drank spirits that last day you drank any alcohol, how much did you drink?

- 1 I never drink spirits
- 2 I did not drink spirits on the last day that I drank alcohol
- 3 <8 cl
- 4 8–15 cl
- 5 16–24 cl
- 6 >24 cl

OC18c If you drank premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops) that last day you drank any alcohol, how much did you drink?

- 1 I never drink alcopops
- 2 I did not drink alcopops on the last day that I drank alcohol
- 3 <50 cl
- 4 50–100 cl
- 5 101–200 cl
- 6 >200 cl

C18f Please indicate on this scale from 1 to 10 how drunk you would say you were that last day you drank alcohol. (If you felt no effect at all you should mark “1”.)

I never drink alcohol

The next question is about alcohol consumption during the last 30 days

C19 Think back again over the LAST 30 DAYS. How many times (if any) have you had five or more drinks on one occasion?

"A `drink` is defined as 1 glass/bottle/can of beer (33 cl), 1 glass of wine (ca 15 cl), 1 glass of spirits (ca 4 cl), 1 glass/bottle of cider (33 cl), 1 glass/bottle of premixed drinks (spritz, alcopops etc. (33 cl).

- 1 None
- 2 1
- 3 2
- 4 3-5
- 5 6-9
- 6 10 or more times

The next questions are also about alcohol

C20 On how many occasions (if any) have you been intoxicated from drinking alcoholic beverages, for example staggered when walking, not being able to speak properly, throwing up or not remembering what happened?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) In your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) During the last 12 months.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C21 When (if ever) did you FIRST do each of the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	9 years old or less	10 years old	11 years old	12 years old	13 years old	14 years old	15 years old	16 years or older
(a) Drink alcohol (at least one glass).....	<input type="checkbox"/>								
(b) Get drunk on alcohol.....	<input type="checkbox"/>								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

C22 In the LAST 12 MONTHS, how often did you drink ...

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Mostly	Always
(a) because it helps you enjoy a party?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) because it helps you when you feel depressed or nervous?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) to cheer up when you're in a bad mood?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) because you like the feeling?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) to get high?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) because it makes social gatherings more fun?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(g) to fit in with a group you like?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(h) because it improves parties and celebrations?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(i) to forget about your problems?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(j) because it's fun?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(k) to be liked?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(l) so you won't feel left out?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

Tranquillisers and sedatives, like benzos and tablets are sometimes prescribed by doctors to help people to calm down, get to sleep or to relax. Pharmacies are not supposed to sell them without a prescription.

C23 Have you ever taken tranquillisers or sedatives because a doctor told you to take them?

- 1 No, never
- 2 Yes, but for less than 3 weeks
- 3 Yes, for 3 weeks or more

The next questions ask about cannabis (marijuana or hashish)

C24 How difficult do you think it would be for you to get cannabis if you wanted?

- 1 Impossible
- 2 Very difficult
- 3 Fairly difficult
- 4 Fairly easy
- 5 Very easy
- 6 Don't know

C25 On how many occasions (if any) have you used cannabis?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) In your lifetime	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) During the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C26 When (if ever) did you FIRST try cannabis?

- 1 Never
- 2 9 years old or less
- 3 10 years old
- 4 11 years old
- 5 12 years old
- 6 13 years old
- 7 14 years old
- 8 15 years old
- 9 16 years or older

OC03 Have you ever had the possibility to try cannabis without trying it?

- 1 No
- 2 Once or twice
- 3 3 times or more

OC04 Have you ever used cannabis mixed with tobacco?

- 1 Never
- 2 Rarely
- 3 From time to time
- 4 Fairly often
- 5 Very often

OC05 During the last 12 MONTHS, did you use the following type(s) of cannabis?

	Never	Rarely	From time to time	Fairly often	Very often
(a) Cannabis resin.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) Weed/skunk.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) Cannabis oil.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

C27 Have you used cannabis during the LAST 12 MONTHS?

- 1 No
- 2 Yes → **Has the following happened to you during the LAST 12 MONTHS?**
Mark one box for each line.

	Never	Rarely	From time to time	Fairly often	Very often
(a) Have you smoked cannabis before midday?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) Have you smoked cannabis when you were alone?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) Have you had memory problems when you smoked cannabis?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) Have friends or members of your family told you that you ought to reduce or stop your cannabis use?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) Have you tried to reduce or stop your cannabis use without succeeding?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) Have you had problems because of your use of cannabis (argument, fight, accident, bad result at school, etc)?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

C28 How difficult do you think it would be for you to get each of the following, if you wanted?

Mark one box for each line.

	Impossible	Very difficult	Fairly difficult	Fairly easy	Very easy	Don't know
(a) Amphetamines	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) Methamphetamines.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) Tranquillisers or sedatives without a doctor's prescription	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(d) Ecstasy.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(e) Cocaine.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(f) Crack	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

C29 On how many occasions (if any) have you ever used...?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions		
	0	1-2	3 or more
(a) Ecstasy in your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Ecstasy during the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) Amphetamines in your lifetime	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(d) Amphetamines during the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(e) Methamphetamines in your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(f) Methamphetamines during the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(g) Cocaine in your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(h) Cocaine during the last 12 months.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(i) Crack in your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(j) Crack during the last 12 months.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(k) Heroin in your lifetime	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(l) Heroin during the last 12 months.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3

C30 On how many occasions (if any) have you used inhalants [glue, aerosol, paint] to get high?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasion		
	0	1-2	3 or more
(a) In your lifetime	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) During the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3

C31 On how many occasions in your lifetime (if any) have you used any of the following drugs?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions		
	0	1-2	3 or more
(a) LSD or some other hallucinogens	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) "Magic mushrooms".....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) GHB.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(d) Sprack.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(e) Drugs by injection with a needle (like heroin, cocaine, amphetamine).....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3

C32 On how many occasions in your lifetime (if any) have you used any of the following drugs?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions		
	0	1-2	3 or more
(a) Tranquillisers or sedatives (without a doctor's prescription).....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Anabolic steroids.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) Alcohol together with pills (medicaments) in order to get high.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(d) Painkillers in order to get high.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3

OC06 When (if ever) did you FIRST do each of the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	Never	9 years old or less	10 years old	11 years old	12 years old	13 years old	14 years old	15 years old	16 years or older
a) Try tranquillisers or sedatives (without a doctor's prescription)	<input type="checkbox"/>								
b) Try amphetamines or methamphetamines.....	<input type="checkbox"/>								
c) Try cocaine or crack	<input type="checkbox"/>								
d) Try ecstasy	<input type="checkbox"/>								
e) Try inhalants (glue, aerosol, paint) in order to get high	<input type="checkbox"/>								
f) Try alcohol together with pills (medicaments) in order to get high.....	<input type="checkbox"/>								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9

The next questions ask about new substances

C33 New substances that imitate the effects of illicit drugs [such as cannabis or ecstasy] may now be sometimes available. They are sometimes called ['legal highs', 'ethno botanicals', 'research chemicals'] and can come in different forms, for example – herbal mixtures, powders, crystals or tablets.

Have you used such substances...

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions			
	0	1-2	3 or more	Don't know/ Not sure
(a) In your lifetime?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) During the last 12 months?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4

C34 If you have used such new substances in the LAST 12 MONTHS, what was the appearance/form of the new substance/s?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 I have not used such substances in the last 12 months
- 2 Herbal smoking mixtures with drug-like effects
- 3 Powders, crystals or tablets with drug-like effects
- 4 Liquids with drug-like effects
- 5 Other

OC07 On how many occasions in your lifetime (if any) have you used any of the following substances?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions		
	0	1-2	3 or more
(a) Synthetic cannabinoids.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Synthetic cathinone[Snow blow/ Bath salts/ Bloom]	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3

C35 How much do you think PEOPLE RISK harming themselves (physically or in other ways), if they ...

Mark one box for each line.

	No risk	Slight risk	Moderate risk	Great risk	Don't know
(a) smoke cigarettes occasionally?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) smoke one or more packs of cigarettes per day?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) try e-cigs once or twice?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) have one or two drinks nearly every day?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) have four or five drinks nearly every day?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) have five or more drinks in one occasion nearly each weekend?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

C36 Again how much do you think PEOPLE RISK harming themselves (physically or in other ways), if they ... Mark one box for each line.

	No risk	Slight risk	Moderate risk	Great risk	Don't know
(a) try cannabis once or twice?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) smoke cannabis occasionally?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) smoke cannabis regularly?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) try ecstasy once or twice?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) take ecstasy regularly?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) try an amphetamine (uppers, pep pills, bennie, speed) once or twice?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(g) take amphetamines regularly?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(h) try synthetic cannabinoids once or twice?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

OC08 During the LAST 12 MONTHS have you experienced the following?

Mark all that apply.

	Never	Yes, while using alcohol	Yes, while using drugs	Yes, but NOT while using alcohol/drugs
(a) Physical fight.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(b) Accident or injury.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(c) Damaged or lost objects or clothing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(d) Serious arguments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(e) Victimized by robbery or theft.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(f) Trouble with police	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(g) Hospitalised or admitted to an emergency room because of severe intoxication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(h) Hospitalised or admitted to an emergency room because of accident or injury.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(i) Engaged in sexual intercourse without a condom	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(j) Been a victim of unwanted sexual advance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(k) Deliberately hurt yourself.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(l) Driven a moped, car or other motor vehicle	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(m) Been involved in an accident while driving yourself	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
(n) Been swimming in deep water (swimming pool, river, lake or sea)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4

The next questions ask about Social Media

C37 During the LAST 30 DAYS, how many hours (if any) did you spend on the Internet on Social Media communicating with others on the Internet? [for example WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook, Skype, Blogs, Snapchat, Instagram, Kik etc]

	None	Half an hour or less	About 1 hour	About 2-3 hours	About 4-5 hours	6 hours or more
(a) On a school day	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) On a non-school day (weekend, holidays)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

C38 How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements on Social Media communicating with others on the Internet? [for example WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook, Skype, Blogs, Snapchat, Instagram, Kik etc] Mark one box for each line.

	Strongly agree	Partly agree	Neither nor	Partly disagree	Strongly disagree
(a) I think I spend way too much time on Social Media	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) I get in a bad mood when I cannot spend time on Social Media	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) My parents say that I spend way too much time on Social Media.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

The next questions ask about gaming

C39 During the LAST 30 DAYS, how many hours (if any) did you play games with other people using a computer, tablet, console, smartphone or other electronic device (war, strategy and games where you are the shooter)?

	None	Half an hour or less	About 1 hour	About 2-3 hours	About 4-5 hours	6 hours or more
(a) On a school day	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) On a non-school day (weekend, holidays)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

C40 During the LAST 7 DAYS, on how many days (if any) were you playing games with other people using a computer, tablet, console, smartphone or other electronic device (war, strategy and games where you are the shooter)?

1 None
 2 1 day
 3 2 days
 4 3 days
 5 4 days
 6 5 days
 7 6 days
 8 7 days

C41 How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about gaming on a computer, tablet, console, smartphone or other electronic device?

Mark one box for each line.

	Strongly agree	Partly agree	Neither nor	Partly disagree	Strongly disagree
(a) I think I spend way too much time playing games.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) I get in a bad mood when I cannot spend time on games	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) My parents say that I spend way too much time on gaming.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

The next questions ask about gambling for money (slot machines, playing card or dice, lotteries, sport bookmakers, etc) both on the Internet and not on the Internet (in traditional settings)

C42 How often (if ever) did you gamble for money in the LAST 12 MONTHS?

- 1 I have not gambled for money during the last 12 months
- 2 Monthly or less
- 3 2-4 times a month
- 4 2-3 times or more a week

C43 How much time (if any) did you spend gambling for money on a TYPICAL DAY in the LAST 12 MONTHS?

- 1 I have not gambled for money during the last 12 months
- 2 Less than 30 minutes
- 3 Between 30 minutes and 1 hour
- 4 Between 1 and 2 hours
- 5 Between 2 and 3 hours
- 6 3 hours or more

C44 How often (if ever) did you gamble for money more than 2 hours (on a single occasion) in the LAST 12 MONTHS?

- 1 I have not gambled for money during the last 12 months
- 2 Never
- 3 Less than monthly
- 4 Monthly
- 5 Weekly
- 6 Daily or almost daily

C45 If you have gambled for money in the LAST 12 MONTHS, which games have you played?

Mark one box for each line.

	I have not played these games	Monthly or less	2-4 times a month	2-3 times or more a week
a) Slot machines (fruit machine, new slot etc).....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) Playing card or dice (poker, bridge, dice etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) Lotteries (scratch, bingo, keno etc).....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) Betting on sports or animals (horses, dogs etc) ...	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4

C46 If you have gambled for money in the LAST 12 MONTHS, how often did you use the INTERNET?

- 1 I have not gambled for money during the last 12 months
- 2 I never used the Internet to gamble for money
- 3 Seldom
- 4 Sometimes
- 5 Mostly
- 6 Always

Now think again about gambling for money in general:

C47 Have you ever felt the need to bet more and more money?

- 1 No
2 Yes

C48 Have you ever had to lie to people important to you about how much you gambled?

- 1 No
2 Yes

The next questions ask about your parents. If mostly foster parents, step-parents or others brought you up answer for them. For example, if you have both a stepfather and a natural father, answer for the one that is the most important in bringing you up

C49 What is the highest level of schooling your father completed?

- 1 Completed primary school or less
2 Some secondary school
3 Completed secondary school
4 Some college or university
5 Completed college or university
6 Don't know
7 Does not apply

C50 What is the highest level of schooling your mother completed?

- 1 Completed primary school or less
2 Some secondary school
3 Completed secondary school
4 Some college or university
5 Completed college or university
6 Don't know
7 Does not apply

C51 How well off is your family compared to other families in your country?

- 1 Very much better off
2 Much better off
3 Better off
4 About the same
5 Less well off
6 Much less well off
7 Very much less well off

C52 Which of the following people live in the same house in which you stay most of the time?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 I live alone
2 Father
3 Stepfather
4 Mother
5 Stepmother
6 Brother(s)
7 Sister(s)
8 Grandparent(s)
9 Other relative(s)
10 Non-relative(s) (e.g. when living in a boarding school or equivalent)

C53 How often do the following statements apply to you?

Mark one box for each line.

	Almost Always	Often	Some times	Seldom	Almost never
a) My parent(s) set definite rules about what I can do at home.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
b) My parent(s) set definite rules about what I can do outside the home	<input type="checkbox"/>				
c) My parent(s) know whom I am with in the evenings	<input type="checkbox"/>				
d) My parent(s) know where I am in the evenings	<input type="checkbox"/>				
e) I can easily borrow money from my mother and/or father	<input type="checkbox"/>				
f) I can easily get money as a gift from my mother and/or father.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

C54 We are interested in how you feel about the following statements.

Read each statement carefully. Indicate how you feel about each statement.

Mark one box for each line.

	Very strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	Very strongly agree
a) My family really tries to help me	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) I get the emotional help and support I need from my family.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) I can talk about my problems with my family	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) My family is willing to help me make decisions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C55 We are interested in how you feel about the following statements.

Read each statement carefully. Indicate how you feel about each statement.

Mark one box for each line.

	Very strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	Very strongly agree
a) My friends really try to help me.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) I can count on my friends when things go wrong	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) I have friends with whom I can share my joys and sorrows.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) I can talk about my problems with my friends	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

C56 Does your mother or your father know where you spend Saturday nights?

- 1 Know always
- 2 Know quite often
- 3 Know sometimes
- 4 Usually don't know

C57 If you had ever used cannabis, do you think that you would have said so in this questionnaire?

- 1 I already said that I have used it
- 2 Definitely yes
- 3 Probably yes
- 4 Probably not
- 5 Definitely not

The next questions are about yourself and what you think about others

O01 Which of the following best describes your average grade at the end of the last term?

- 1 Highest marks
- 2 etc...

O02 How satisfied are you usually with ...

Mark one box for each line.

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Neither nor	Not so satisfied	Not at all satisfied	There is no such person
(a) your relationship with your mother?	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) your relationship with your father?	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) your relationship with your friends?	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

O03 What do you think your mother's reaction would be if you do the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	She would not allow it	She would discourage it	She would not mind	She would approve of it	Don't know
(a) Get drunk.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) Smoke cigarettes.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) Use cannabis.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) Use ecstasy.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

O04 What do you think your father's reaction would be if you do the following things?

Mark one box for each line.

	He would not allow it	He would discourage it	He would not mind	He would approve of it	Don't know
(a) Get drunk.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) Smoke cigarettes.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) Use cannabis.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) Use ecstasy.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

O05 How many of your friends would you estimate

Mark one box for each line.

	None	A few	Some	Most	All
(a) smoke cigarettes?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(b) drink alcoholic beverages (beer, cider, premixed drinks, wine, spirits)?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(c) get drunk?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(d) smoke cannabis?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(e) take tranquillisers or sedatives (without a doctor's prescription)?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(f) take ecstasy?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
(g) use inhalants?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

O06 This question is about alcohol consumption during the **LAST 7 DAYS**.

Please pay attention to the sizes of the bottles and glasses!

Please answer every question. If you have not had a beverage, indicate „0“.

a. On how many days (if any) have you had any alcoholic drink?

In the last 7 days I have had **alcoholic drinks** on days
(0 = none, 7 = every day)

b. How many bottles or glasses of beer have you had?

In the last 7 days I have had glasses or bottles of beer
(0 = haven't had any beer)

c. How many glasses of wine or sparkling wine have you had?

In the last 7 days I have had glasses of **wine or sparkling wine**
(0 = haven't had any wine or sparkling wine)

d. How many glasses of spirits have you had?

In the last 7 days I have had glasses of **spirits**
(0 = haven't had any spirits)

e. How many glasses of alcoholic mixed drinks have you had?

In the last 7 days I have had glasses of **alcoholic mixed drinks**
(0 = haven't had any alcoholic mixed drinks)

	1 small bottle or 1 small glass of beer = 0,33l	
	1 small glass of wine or sparkling wine = 0,1l	
	1 glass of spirits = 0,04l	
	1 glass of alcoholic mixed drink = 0,33l	

O07 Think back over the **LAST 30 DAYS**. On how many occasions (if any) have you bought beer, cider, alcopops, wine or spirits in a store (grocery store, liquor store, kiosk or petrol station) for your own consumption (off-premises)?

Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions					
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20 or more
(a) Beer.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) Cider	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) Premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(d) Wine	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(e) Spirits	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

O08 Think back once more over the **LAST 30 DAYS**. On how many occasions (if any) have you drunk **beer, cider, alcopops, wine or spirits in a pub, bar, restaurant or disco (on-premises)?**
 Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions					
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20 or more
(a) Beer.....	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(b) Cider	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(c) Premixed drinks (sprit, alcopops)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(d) Wine	<input type="checkbox"/>					
(e) Spirits	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	1	2	3	4	5	6

O09 Think of that last day on which you drank alcohol. Where were you when you drank?
 Mark all that apply.

- 1 I never drink alcohol
- 1 At home
- 1 At someone else's home
- 1 Out on the street, in a park, beach or other open area
- 1 At a bar or a pub
- 1 In a disco or club
- 1 In a restaurant
- 1 Other places

The next two questions are about energy drinks

O10 On how many occasions (if any) have you had any energy drink [e.g. Red bull / Monster Energy]?
 (Don't include so called "sports drinks" [e.g. Lucozade Sport])
 Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) In your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) During the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

O11 On how many occasions (if any) have you been drinking energy drinks and alcohol during a single session? (Don't include so called "sports drinks" [e.g. Lucozade Sport])
 Mark one box for each line.

	Number of occasions						
	0	1-2	3-5	6-9	10-19	20-39	40 or more
(a) In your lifetime.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(b) During the last 12 months	<input type="checkbox"/>						
(c) During the last 30 days.....	<input type="checkbox"/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Now follow some more questions about the Internet and ONLINE games

O12 Please read the statements below regarding Internet use.

Please indicate how often these statements apply to you. Mark one box for each line.

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Often	Very often
a) How often do you find it difficult to stop using the Internet when you are online?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
b) How often do you continue to use the Internet despite your intention to stop?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
c) How often do others (e.g. parents, friends) say you should use the Internet less?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
d) How often do you prefer to use the Internet instead of spending time with others (e.g. parents, friends).....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
e) How often are you short of sleep because of the Internet?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
f) How often do you think about the Internet, even when not online?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
g) How often do you look forward to your next Internet session?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
h) How often do you think you should use the Internet less often?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
i) How often have you unsuccessfully tried to spend less time on the Internet?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
j) How often do you rush through your (home) work in order to go on the Internet?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
k) How often do you neglect your daily obligations (work, school or family life) because you prefer to go on the Internet?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
l) How often do you go on the Internet when you are feeling down?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
m) How often do you use the Internet to escape from your sorrows or get relief from negative feelings?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
n) How often do you feel restless, frustrated, or irritated when you cannot use the Internet?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

O13 Please read the statements below regarding online gaming. The question REFERS TO ONLINE GAMES exclusively, but we use the expression 'game' in each statement for simplicity's sake. Please indicate how often these statements apply to you. Mark one box for each line.

	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Mostly	Always
a) When you are not gaming, how often do you think about playing a game or think about how would it feel to play at that moment?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
b) How often do you play longer than originally planned?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
c) How often do you feel depressed or irritable when not gaming only for these feelings to disappear when you start playing?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
d) How often do you feel that you should reduce the amount of time you spend gaming?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
e) How often do the people around you complain that you are gaming too much?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
f) How often do you fail to meet up with a friend because you were gaming? ..	<input type="checkbox"/>				
g) How often do you daydream about gaming?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
h) How often do you lose track of time when gaming?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
i) How often do you get restless or irritable if you are unable to play games for a few days?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
j) How often do you unsuccessfully try to reduce the time you spend on gaming?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
k) How often do you argue with your parents because of gaming?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
l) How often do you neglect other activities because you would rather game? ..	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

The next questions are about PERFORMANCE ENHANCERS

M01 Have you ever use in your life on your own initiative (without been prescribed by a doctor) any stimulant substance with the purpose to improve your performance in your study? For instance to keep you awake and studying during the whole night or to study faster. Don't include coffee, tea or cola refreshments, or energy drinks.

- 1 No
2 Yes

M02 If you have used such stimulant substance (without a doctor prescription) with the purpose to improve you performance in study; where did you obtain the substance/s?

Mark all that apply.

- 1 Never used
1 Offered by a family member, a friend or an acquaintance
1 By a street dealer
1 Through the internet
1 From a pharmacy without a medical prescription

S01 What are the rules or restrictions, if any, on cigarette smoking when you are in the family car?

- 1 No one is allowed to smoke
2 Smoking is allowed as long as the window is down
3 There are no rules or restrictions
4 I never drive in cars with people who smoke
5 Don't know

S02 What are the rules or restrictions on smoking cigarette in your house?

- 1 No one is allowed to smoke inside or outside the house
2 No one is allowed to smoke inside, but outside is OK
3 Adults are allowed to smoke anywhere in the house
4 Adults are allowed to smoke in some rooms
5 There are no rules or restrictions on smoking
6 Something else (please state) _____

S03 Are you a smoker who is interested in quitting in the next month?

- Yes
 No

Are you willing to set a quit date?

- Yes
 No

How Ready Are You? (circle the appropriate number)

Sliding scale

1 = not at all 10 = Completely

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10